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PROJECTED IDENTITIES:
THE ROLE OF “PERFECT BLUE” IN UNDERSTANDING
BODY POLITICS WITHIN JAPANESE IDOL CULTURE

Thesis in Globalization and Its Malcontents

Supervisor
Prof. Ivo Quaranta

Presented by
Seyedeh Marzie Sajadi

Co-Supervisor
Prof. Maria Elena Tisi

Session III

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To Women, Life, Freedom

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Abstract

This thesis examines the complex intersections of body politics, media, and identity construction within Japanese idol culture through a critical analysis of Satoshi Kon's animated psychological thriller *Perfect Blue*. Drawing from discourse analysis, cultural studies, and embodiment theory, it explores how the idol's body becomes a site of social control, cultural projection, and ideological reinforcement in post-war Japan. The study situates the protagonist's psychological unraveling within a broader framework of collective memory, national identity, and the "history of the body" in Japan—a concept shaped by mythology, language, cultural norms, and historical traumas.

Through critical engagement with theoretical frameworks from Foucault, Bourdieu, Althusser, and constructivist discourse analysts, this research interrogates how Japanese idol culture constructs idealized female bodies through fantasy, surveillance, and symbolic discipline. The research will also provide an overview of the Japanese pop idol culture and its formation through a fantasy. The research will analyse the function of this fantasy and how it has contributed to the development of pop idol culture in Japan.

The thesis highlights how cultural memory and historical narratives are inscribed on the body, with traditions such as the samurai ethos, geisha performance, and ritual aesthetics continuing to shape the national imaginary. The protagonist—an idol-turned-actress—embodies the conflict between selfhood and collective memory, symbolizing Japan's struggle with preserving and transforming its cultural memory.

By situating *Perfect Blue* as both a product and critique of Japanese visual culture, this research argues that collective memory is not only preserved but performed and contested through the body. Ultimately, the thesis contributes to interdisciplinary conversations around identity, trauma, and embodiment in late-capitalist societies, revealing how national ideologies are reproduced and subverted through media and performance.

A Preface to The Enigma

The following case report is based on an article written by BBC correspondents On February 2013:

«In February first, 2013, a 20-year-old Japanese pop star has shaved her head (cutting one's hair is seen as an act of remorse in Japanese culture) and offered a filmed apology after breaking her management firm's rules by spending a night with her boyfriend. A sobbing Minami Minegishi apologized to her fans and said she did not want to leave the band AKB48¹, in the video seen by millions on YouTube.² The production company behind AKB48 said Minegishi had failed to abide by its cardinal rule - no dating. In the video posted on AKB48's official website, she said she had made the decision to shave off her long hair to show contrition for her "thoughtless and immature" actions. "I was supposed to set an example for younger members, but my actions were extremely careless and senseless, my mind has gone completely blank. I don't know what I can do or what I should do, but I couldn't bear to do nothing. I don't believe just doing this means I can be forgiven for what I did, but the first thing I thought was that I don't want to quit AKB48", she said". »³

AKB48, a popular Japanese girl group with members aged from early teens to mid-twenties, has gained a big following for their catchy pop music and projected image of innocence. However, their suggestive lyrics and outfits suggest a more mature side. They mainly appeal to male fans and focus on fan interaction, organizing events like "handshake" meetups. Fans can vote in an annual election through ballots in the CDs, determining who gets prominent roles in group projects like singles and music videos.⁴

A year after this international headline in 2014:

«Two other members of the popular Japanese pop group AKB48 were injured after a man attacked them with a saw. Rina Kawaei, nineteen years old, and Anna

¹ A Japanese idol girl group

²@Sandwellnews, www.youtube.com, YouTube video, February 2, 2013, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HF2y45Jl_sl

³ "BBC", AKB48 pop star shaves head after breaking band rules, Britain, 2013, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-21299324>

⁴ Akiko Fujita, "Pop Star Shaves Head in Remorse for Dating", Reported in ABC News, New York City, 2013 <https://abcnews.go.com/blogs/headlines/2013/02/pop-star-shaves-head-in-remorse-for-dating>

Iriyama, eighteen years old, were meeting with fans in the northern city of Takizawa on Sunday when a man lunged forward and slashed them. »⁵

In May 2016:

«Mayu Tomita, a twenty-year-old Japanese pop idol from AKB48 group, was stabbed in the neck and chest area multiple times by twenty-seven-year-old fan Tomohiro Iwazaki. Iwazaki, had sent multiple "obsessive comments" to her blog and Twitter account. He reportedly sent her some books and a watch. The watch was sent between January and February 2016, and it was returned to the sender in April, after which he sent her around 400 hostile tweets. On May 21st, 2016, around 5:05 PM Iwazaki confronted Tomita in front of a small concert venue near a train station before an event titled Solid Girls Night in Koganei, Tokyo, where she was performing later that evening with other singers. Iwazaki had asked her why she returned the gifts he sent her but stated that he "lost control" when Tomita did not give him a clear explanation. When Tomita turned around, he stabbed her from behind in chest and neck area 61 times with a pocketknife containing an 8.2 cm blade. Prosecutors alleged that he had yelled, "You should die, die, die!" as he stabbed her. Eyewitnesses called the police after hearing Tomita scream for help, and Iwazaki was arrested. Iwazaki told the police that he "intended to kill" Tomita and had prepared a knife beforehand. When Tomita had called the police before being stabbed, the emergency dispatcher had sent the police to her home instead of tracing the location of her cell phone. »⁶

The phenomenon of pop idol groups has not only captured the hearts of millions but has also woven a narrative around the concept of an “innocent and perfect body.”⁷ The allure of these idols, epitomized by groups such as AKB48, goes beyond their catchy tunes and choreographed performances. It delves into the projection of an image that demands purity, adherence to societal norms, and an unblemished persona. However, beneath the surface of this seemingly

⁵ “BBC”, Japan girl group AKB48 attacked by man with saw, Britain, 2014, <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-27572723>

⁶ The Japan Times "Stabbed idol in critical condition; fan faces a charge of attempted murder". The Japan Times. May 22, 2016. Retrieved January 24, 2019. <https://www.japantimes.co.jp/news/2016/05/22/national/crime-legal/female-idol-stabbed-multiple-times-by-purported-fan-at-event-in-western-tokyo-police/#.XEn01-TsaUk>

⁷ Mariko Oi, “The dark side of Asia’s pop music industry”, BBC news, Britain 2016. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-35368705>

idyllic world lies a complex web of expectations, scrutiny, and, at times, disturbing consequences.

The lens through which we explore this intricate interplay between societal expectations and individual experiences is provided by the unsettling incidents that have transpired within the pop idol culture in Japan. These incidents, broadcasted on AKB48's official website, serves as a stark illustration of the stringent norms imposed upon these idols, whose projected image of innocence is juxtaposed with more mature undertones in their music and performances. The consequences of deviating from these prescribed norms are not confined to public expressions of contrition. These events transcend the realm of isolated incidents, offering a disconcerting glimpse into the darker consequences of an industry that thrives on projecting an image of perfection.

As we navigate through these distressing narratives, the focus shifts from the external manifestations of societal pressure to the internal struggles faced by individuals. The transition to the realm of mental health is seamlessly bridged by the exploration of Satoshi Kon's animated masterpiece, "*Perfect Blue*." This cinematic gem delves into the complexities of identity, reality, and societal expectations through the lens of its protagonist, Mima. In juxtaposing the real-life incidents of pop idols with the fictional yet profoundly evocative narrative of Mima, we are compelled to confront the recurring theme of individuals oscillating between societal expectations and the turbulent realms of personal identity.

The world that "*Perfect Blue*"⁸ introduces us to is not much different from where we live. This anime has been directed by Satoshi Kon which is based on the novel with the same title "*Perfect Blue: Complete Metamorphosis*" by Yoshikazu Takeuchi.⁹ According to Darzen (2003) most of Kon's works "bounce perception against reality, bounce the way people are against the way people seem to be, and keep bouncing until something explodes. He then turns the explosion into art".¹⁰

At the heart of the world represented by "*Perfect Blue*" stands Mima Kirigoe. A young member of a Japanese idol's group. In the anime's opening scene, she announces her decision to transition from being an idol singer to pursuing an acting career, a choice that disappoints her

⁸ Satoshi Kon, "*Perfect Blue*", 1997

⁹ Yoshikazu Takeuchi, *Perfect Blue: Complete Metamorphosis* (Tokyo: Seven Seas Entertainment, 1991)

¹⁰ Patrick Drazen, *ANIME EXPLOSION: The What? Why? & Wow of Japanese Animation* (Berkeley, California: Stone Bridge Press, 2003), 302.

dedicated fans. This resistance to change becomes intertwined with her inner turmoil and leading to a mental controversy within herself. This controversy is gradually gaining physical form and illusion, in the form of ghostly Mima that is wearing the old clothes of her idol pope, appears in her daily life.¹¹

The illusion first occurred in the reflection of the subway glass and then and then extends to auditory experiences. Over time, reality begins to spin out and the boundaries between reality and illusion soon become nearly indistinguishable with scenes blending into one another. As this unsettling change continues, Mima begins to lose her grasp on who she actually is and what her life is about, all the while being pursued by what seems to be a violent stalker, adding to the tension and confusion about what's real.¹²

Colors are significant in these eighty minutes of runtime anime. As the anime goes forward and the illusion intensifies, the colors become brasher and nervier to the extent that they really irritate the eyes. However, this process does not materialize inconsiderately. Satoshi Kon without any clumsy exposition moves us forward step by step with Mima. He does not impose information on us. The five minutes none-paused continuity that we are surveilling Mima alone in her apartment, details of her room, her fish tank, the posters, the play station under the TV, her computer, the conveys her duality between enthusiasm, while she was performing as a pop idol, and her simplicity, while she was living her regular life back and forth. Also, the rest of the details help us to have a more realistic connection with Mima even though these details do not give us any direct information about her.¹³

As the anime progresses, Mima must play the role of a dancer who has been gruesomely gang-raped in a strip club where she works. A visual metaphor that supposed indicates Mima's transformation. Erotic scenes, constant screams, colors, and music impose on us the tension that Mima is suffering from. Later, more scenes embody Mima in an extremely sexualized way. Although each time that Mima has depicted as a sexual object, we are observing her through other's cameras, photo frames, and eyes. The eyes perceive her in a way that she did not choose, and that perception becomes Mima's reality.¹⁴

¹¹ Wolf, Super Eyepatch, [www.youtube.com](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MJmK5SOeQBc&t=12s), YouTube video, May, 13, 2017.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MJmK5SOeQBc&t=12s>

¹² Satoshi Kon, "Perfect Blue", 1997

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Ibid

As the story moves on, time goes out of a linear satiety in this work and turns into fragments of imagination and reality. Such a perception of time is quite different from the modern subject's perception of time because for the subject of modernity, time is interconnected pieces that can be calculated and measured and have a linear course. The disruption of this seemingly linear, as it happens in the anime, produce an ill subject who loses the ability to speak and has to patch together the fragments of time, each of which plays the role of memories.¹⁵

The cuts ramp up jarringly so that neither Mima nor the audience can comprehend which version of reality she is in. Distinguishing what is real and what is not becomes indistinguishable up to the point that Mima starts to self-infliction to grasp reality. She also follows the online accounts that document her daily life, to find out which reality she is in, is real. However, there are other elements such as Mima's stalker and the concurrent murders that amplify these illusions, deepening the complexity of her experience.¹⁶

The central argument of this paper is fairly straightforward; describing the Japanese pop idol culture and explaining how this culture has been formed through fantasy as well as analyzing the function of this fantasy. Taking this argument a step further, the purpose of this article was to critically assess the Japanese's understanding of the body as the field of discursivity of the Japanese Myth, language, history, and culture. Since myth, language and two other elements represent and reproduce the culture of the society in each era, it can be a good platform for studying and analyzing the concept of the body and its various conceptualizations.

It does so largely through an analysis of the discursive field which includes the context that Japanese pop idol culture has been born in and the conditions that led to possibilities for action, to unravel the origins and enabling conditions of Japanese pop idol culture. Jackson (2011) argued that using this approach, «the central analytical focus moves from linear causal investigation to “how possible” questions».¹⁷

Expanding on Jackson's perspective, such an analysis requires a focus on the role of language and myth factors as well as comprehensive exploration of the paths through which language

¹⁵ Arash Heydari, “Melancholia: Tarkovsky, Freud and Benjamin”, *Academyhonar* (Spring 2014): 7.

<http://academyhonar.com/branches/sociology-of-art/2433-tarkovsky.html>

¹⁶ Wolf, Super Eyepatch, www.youtube.com, YouTube video, May, 13, 2017.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MJmK5SOeQBc&t=12s>

¹⁷ Jackson, Richard. ‘Culture, Identity and Hegemony: Continuity and (the Lack of) Change in US Counterterrorism Policy from Bush to Obama’. *International Politics* 48, no. 2–3 (March 2011): 390–411, 393. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ip.2011.5>.

and myth contribute to the cultural hegemony of the concept of body in Japan and also how it becomes hegemonic, as posited by.¹⁸ Furthermore, the investigation extends to the interconnection of pop idols with well-known stereotypes of chastity and purity in the Japanese context and how it embedded in the fantasy that has been constructed around body axis, as noted by scholars like.¹⁹

The study aims to illuminate the intricate paths through which this cultural phenomenon attains dominance, emphasizing the dynamic interplay between language, myth, and the formation of cultural narratives. The study delves into the ways in which pop idols become deeply intertwined with established notions of purity and chastity, contributing to the construction of a cultural narrative that shapes public perceptions.

There are several theoretical frameworks that can be used to do this analysis, and among them constructivist approaches stand out as particularly illuminating. Employing the analytical instruments provided by constructivism, we can investigate the discursive “conditions of possibility” for policy choices by studying the various ways through which beliefs, standards, identities, language, and other discursive practices act as an influential social structure that restrain and facilitate the choices of actors.²⁰

Drawing on the work of scholars like Jackson (2011), the constructivist lens unveils a nuanced understanding of policy formation by directing our attention to the intricate web of discursive practices. These practices, in turn, act as dynamic forces that both constrain and facilitate the choices made by key actors within the policymaking process. By adopting a constructivist perspective, we navigate beyond traditional analyses and venture into the realms of meaning-making, social interaction, and the construction of shared realities. This approach not only opens avenues for comprehending the intricacies of policy choices but also sheds light on the underlying mechanisms that contribute to the construction of political and social landscapes.²¹

¹⁸ Jørgensen, Marianne, and Louise Phillips. *Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method*. 6 Bonhill Street, London England EC2A 4PU United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2002. 2. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849208871>.

¹⁹ Wald, Gayle ‘Just a Girl? Rock Music, Feminism, and the Cultural Construction of Female Youth’, 2021. 585-610. 588.

²⁰ Jackson, Richard. ‘Culture, Identity and Hegemony: Continuity and (the Lack of) Change in US Counterterrorism Policy from Bush to Obama’. *International Politics* 48, no. 2–3 (March 2011): 390–411. 406. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ip.2011.5>.

²¹ Jørgensen, Marianne, and Louise Phillips. *Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method*. 6 Bonhill Street, London England EC2A 4PU United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2002. 5. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849208871>.

The starting point of these approaches is sharing the same philosophical lineage with the “structuralism and post-structuralism linguistic philosophical claim”; Central to these approaches is the fundamental notion that our access to reality is always through language and the way we talk about the world of identities and social relations does not reflect them in a neutral way, but plays an active role in creating and changing them.²² At the core of the philosophical assumptions underpinning these approaches lies an exploration of how key entities, such as “language” and “the subject,” are to be understood and conceptualized.

It goes beyond mere linguistic analysis to delve into the profound implications of these linguistic constructs on our understanding of the world. This departure from linguistic neutrality aligns with the acknowledgment that language is not merely a tool for reflection but a dynamic force shaping and reshaping our social realities²³. In addition, these approaches share a common overarching objective: the pursuit of critical research.²⁴

This critical lens has to directs us to identify the power relations embedded within society. Identifying and understanding power dynamics becomes a crucial step toward developing normative perspectives to criticize these relations. Through this process, the aim is not only to unveil existing power structures but also to investigate the possibilities for social changes.²⁵

Delving into the core tenets of these approaches reveals a commitment to moving beyond surface-level analyses and encourage to embark on a profound engagement with the philosophical underpinnings of language, subjectivity, and power dynamics. Adopting the critical research methodologies signifies a departure from passive observation. Scholars using these approaches aim not only to comprehend societal structures but also to actively contribute to the discourse on normativity and social transformation.²⁶

This commitment implies a responsibility to question the status quo, critique prevailing power structures, and actively contribute to envisioning and fostering societal change. Through critical research methodologies, scholars become agents of transformation, navigating the intricate intersections of language, subjectivity, and power to forge paths toward a more nuanced, equitable, and socially just future. In essence, these approaches transcend academic

²² Ibid. 3.

²³ Ibid. 5.

²⁴ Ibid. 2.

²⁵ Ibid. 9.

²⁶ Ibid. 12.

inquiry; they become vehicles for intellectual activism, positioning scholars as catalysts for change in the ongoing discourse on societal norms and transformation.²⁷

The methodological approaches that implemented to investigate language, particularly through disciplines like discourse analysis, focus on different ways through which myth and cultures use language as a tool for intentional and strategic communication. The examination of language goes beyond mere semantics, delving into the intentional selection of words, the crafting of narratives, and the instrumental use of language to formulate and maintain a hegemonic “regime of truth” within society.²⁸

The “regime of truth” refers to the accepted knowledge and principles that govern and define what is considered true within a particular society or community at a given time. It goes beyond individual truths and encompasses the broader structures and systems that shape and control the production and dissemination of knowledge. Foucault argued that truth is not a universal and unchanging concept but rather a product of historical, cultural, and social conditions. Different societies or institutions may have their own regimes of truth, influencing what is accepted as knowledge, what is considered normal or deviant, and how power operates within those systems²⁹. This concept, in short, refers to the dominant narratives and discourses that shape prevailing norms and ideologies, effectively defining what is considered truthful or acceptable within a given cultural context.³⁰

In the context of this article, these theoretical approaches serve as analytical lenses through which the intricate relationship between language and the concept of the body in Japan is explored. The study focuses on how language becomes a powerful tool for formulating and maintaining societal perceptions and expectations surrounding the body. The utilization of discourse analysis allows for a granular examination of linguistic elements, unveiling the deliberate choices made in the construction of narratives that contribute to the establishment and reinforcement of cultural norms associated with the body.

The term “regime of truth,” as conceptualized by Michel Foucault, becomes particularly pertinent in understanding how language operates as a mechanism of power in the discourse

²⁷ Fairclough, Norman. *Critical Discourse Analysis: The Critical Study of Language*. 2. ed., [Nachdr.]. London: Routledge, 2013. 28.

²⁸ Michel Foucault, *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*: New York: Vintage Books, 1979.

²⁹ Fontana, Alessandro, and Pasquale Pasquino. *Truth and Power*. New York: Pantheon Books. 131.

³⁰ *Ibid.* 133.

surrounding the body. It reflects the ways in which certain truths, ideologies, and norms are promoted and sustained through linguistic practices.³¹ In the case of Japan, the article relies on these theoretical frameworks to construct a set of arguments that not only draw attention to but also critically analyze the language intricately woven into the societal discourse on the body.

The deliberate choice of words, the construction of narratives, and the strategic deployment of language within the cultural context become focal points for the exploration of societal expectations and perceptions related to the body.³² By relying on these theoretical approaches, the article seeks to uncover the subtle yet influential ways in which language participates in shaping and reinforcing the cultural understanding of the body in Japan. It is through this analytical lens that the article aims to contribute to a deeper comprehension of the intricate interplay between language, myth, culture, and the conceptualization of the body within the Japanese societal framework. This led us to the concept of the “history of body”.

The “history of body” in Japan is a concept that refers to the intersection of biology and history in Japanese culture. It is an understanding of the body as shaped by social, cultural, and historical forces, as well as biological ones. In recent decades, the concept has gained attention in academic circles for its potential to shed light on the complex ways in which cultural myths and ideologies shape our understanding of the body and the self. This thesis seeks to explore the “history of body” in the context of the Japanese pop idol culture, as depicted in the animated psychological film “*Perfect Blue*” by Satoshi Kon.

The reason of introducing the anime “*Perfect Blue*” is to witness the validity of the earlier assertion I made. There may be dissenting opinions regarding the idea that the oscillation between reality and ideas, between roles and expectations, between the future and the present, or between determinism and free will constitutes natural fluctuations and conflicts within the human experience. Why should these pressures be displayed in such a distinctive and peculiar manner? Why should we illustrate these pressures unsolvable and leave them on the border of reality and fantasy? What I am trying to show here is that These are not isolated events in Japan; rather, they underscore a profound societal issue that distinguishes Japan’s cultural landscape and invites critical examination. Therefore, Japan itself is exactly the thing that distinguishes

³¹ Ibid. 114.

³² Ibid. 119.

“*Perfect Blue*” and the experience of Mima oscillations from the other films addressing similar themes.

Anime, a form of Japanese animated entertainment, has been an increasingly popular cultural phenomenon on the global screen since the 1960s.³³ Its influence has been particularly notable in the United States, where it has become a prominent feature of children’s television programming. According to Denison (2007) watching Japanese anime is like reading a compelling novel that transports you into a world full of fascinating details. This unique medium has captured the imaginations of viewers around the world with its complex storylines, imaginative characters, and stunning visuals.³⁴

Anime is a rich and diverse medium that defies simple definition. Often dismissed as “Japanese cartoons,” such a characterization fails to capture the depth and variety that anime encompasses. Western attempts to explain anime often rely on comparisons to American animation, particularly Disney, but these comparisons fail to appreciate the full spectrum of anime, which includes everything from children’s classics to romantic comedies to post-apocalyptic fantasies and psychological ones like “*Perfect Blue*”.³⁵

What sets anime apart from other forms of animation is its ability to reflect and engage with Japanese culture in ways that are uniquely its own. Anime is deeply rooted in the social and historical context of Japan, drawing on myth, folklore, and tradition to create complex narratives that explore universal themes of love, loss, and the search for identity. At the same time, anime is a form of popular culture that reflects the social and cultural dynamics of Japan, but it also serves as a site of cultural resistance that offers an alternative to global hegemony.³⁶

In this context, the study of anime provides a valuable lens through which to examine the intersections of culture, technology, and globalization. By analyzing the themes, motifs, and techniques of anime, we can gain insight into the complex ways that global and local cultures interact in the contemporary world. Ultimately, anime is more than just entertainment; it is a

³³ Patrick Drazen, ANIME EXPLOSION: The What? Why? & Wow of Japanese Animation (Berkeley, California: Stone Bridge Press, 2003), 302.

³⁴ Phillips, Alastair, and Julian Stringer, eds. Japanese Cinema: Texts and Contexts. London: Routledge, 2007. 201.

³⁵ Napier, Susan J. Anime from Akira to Princess Mononoke. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US, 2001. 6.

<https://doi.org/10.1057/9780312299408>.

³⁶ Ibid. 8.

cultural phenomenon that offers a unique perspective on the challenges and opportunities of our globalized world.³⁷

As a cultural force, anime offers a fascinating window into the complexities of globalization and cultural exchange in the 21st century. Through the study of anime, we can gain insight into the ways that global and local cultures intersect and shape one another. Anime serves as a powerful site of cultural resistance, offering an alternative to the dominant global culture that is often dominated by American mass media. At the same time, anime has become a truly global medium, with fans and creators from all over the world engaging with its themes, styles, and stories.³⁸ As McDonald (2006)³⁹ notes:

«If the American film is strongest in action, and if the European is strongest in character, then the Japanese film is richest in mood or atmosphere, in presenting characters in their own surroundings. »⁴⁰

³⁷ Ibid.9.

³⁸ Ibid. 10.

³⁹ MacDonald, Keiko I. *Reading a Japanese Film: Cinema in Context*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2006.

⁴⁰ Richie, Donald. *Japanese Cinema: Film Style and National Character*. Garden City, New York: Anchor Books, 1971. XIX.

Chapter one

A Political Use of Psychoanalysis

« Death is not desired, but what is desired is dead, already dead: images. »

Deleuze and Guattari (1983).⁴¹

1.1 Pop Idol: Image, Desire, and Death

On November 22, 2010, fans all over Japan were excited to get their hands on “Tomochin!!,” a collection of pictures featuring Itano Tomomi, a famous member of the popular girl group AKB48. What made this photo book special was that a big part of it, 43 percent to be exact, was not just regular pictures but manga – a delightful fusion of visual storytelling akin to comic books. These manga parts showed drawings of Itano in various scenarios, weaving a fanciful narrative around her persona and told a made-up story about her. The decision to incorporate manga into the photo book marked a departure from traditional idol-centric merchandise, introducing a novel form of multimedia storytelling.⁴²

The manga segments delved into a fictional realm, presenting a creative departure from the usual portrayal of idols. This departure sparked discussions and intrigue among fans and critics alike, as the fusion of real and fabricated images became a subject of fascination and conversation within the AKB48 community. Interestingly, “Tomochin!!” was not an isolated experiment. Several months prior, other members of AKB48 had already begun venturing into the realm of manga, becoming characters in their own series. This evolution marked a strategic move by the idol group to diversify their presence in popular media, transcending the boundaries of conventional music and photography.⁴³

While the incorporation of fiction into the narrative of an idol’s image may make some individuals uneasy, scholars like Galbraith and Karlin (2012) says: «fiction is part of the makeup of an idol. The association of real and fictional images exposes how idols are made up

⁴¹ Deleuze, Gilles, and Félix Guattari. *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1983. 431.

⁴² Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 256.

⁴³ *Ibid*, 256.

and how they are imagined». ⁴⁴ Photo book serves as a tangible manifestation of the multifaceted nature of idols. It goes beyond conventional visual representations, offering fans a richer, more immersive experience by engaging with the idol not just as a performer but as a character in a narrative.

AKB48 is a Japanese idol group and one of the country's most popular and successful pop music acts. The group follows the concept of "idols you can meet," emphasizing accessibility and interaction with fans. AKB48, which stands for Akihabara48 (referring to the Akihabara district in Tokyo), was formed in 2005 and operates with a large rotating cast of members. They are known for their singles, theater performances, and a strong fanbase. The group's popularity extends beyond music, with members participating in various media activities, such as television, film, and commercials. AKB48 has significantly influenced the idol culture in Japan.

This chapter delves into the intricate processes surrounding the creation, dissemination, and reception of female idols as visual representations. It scrutinizes how these images are produced, circulated, and, crucially, consumed and engaged with by audiences. The idol's image serves as a focal point for desire, transforming into a commodity in its own right. Constantly visible and exposed, the idol attains a sense of "realness", becoming the foundation for viewers' feelings of intimacy. ⁴⁵

Importantly, this perceived reality exists independently of the actual, tangible reality. Drawing on John Fiske's concept of "inescapable intertextuality" ⁴⁶. This situation is described as a scenario where all texts reference one another rather than an external reality. It's not suggesting that reality doesn't exist, but it emphasizes that what is accessible in cultural products is a constructed version of reality, and it must be comprehended on its own terms. ⁴⁷ In simpler terms, it suggests that images are not isolated entities but are created and interpreted in relation to other images, and the idea of reality is often perceived as an image in itself. ⁴⁸

⁴⁴ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 256.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* 257.

⁴⁶ Fiske, John. *Television Culture; popular pleasures and politics*. London: Routledge, 1999. 116.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.* 117.

⁴⁸ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 258.

Exploring the dynamic realm of pop idols involves navigating between fictional and nonfictional contexts, where performances seamlessly intertwine with both real and onscreen lives. The private lives of idols and celebrities emerge as reservoirs of knowledge and truth, becoming focal points for journalistic discourse on celebrity culture. In this landscape, the creation of intertextual meanings takes center stage, blurring the boundaries between reality and representation.⁴⁹ This unique form of intertextuality in Japanese media requires a profound familiarity with not only the performances but also the circulating gossip and trivia on wide shows⁵⁰. Consequently, Japanese idols, more than their global counterparts, grapple with the challenge of shedding their “real-life” persona when in the spotlight, often being perceived not as portraying characters but as extensions of themselves.⁵¹

The pop idol phenomenon, deeply entrenched in the concept of “kawaii” or cuteness, operates within a meticulous framework where the preservation of an idealized image is of paramount importance. Central to this phenomenon is a stringent condition imposed on those participating in it – a no-dating policy, applicable to both male and female idols.⁵² Far from being an arbitrary rule, this no-dating policy is intricately tied to how pop idols navigate their lives both in reality and onscreen⁵³. The rationale behind this seemingly strict constraint lies in the imperative for idols to consistently embody ideals of innocence and purity,⁵⁴ crucial for maintaining the carefully constructed illusions that captivate their fanbase.⁵⁵

No-dating rule becomes a vital element in the overarching narrative of pop idols as it reinforces the perception of Japanese female artists as embodiments of girliness, innocence, and purity.⁵⁶ This intentional constraint is not a mere imposition, but a strategic choice made by the industry to align with the cultural expectations of its audience. By adhering to the no-dating policy, idols become symbols of an unattainable purity, creating a fantastical allure that resonates with fans who seek an escape into the dreamlike world these idols represent.

⁴⁹ Ibid. 32.

⁵⁰ Fiske, John. *Television Culture; popular pleasures and politics*. London: Routledge, 1999. 109.

⁵¹ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 33.

⁵² Mariko Oi, “The dark side of Asia’s pop music industry”, BBC news, Britain 2016.

<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-35368705>

⁵³ Wald, Gayle, ‘Just a Girl? Rock Music, Feminism, and the Cultural Construction of Female Youth’, 2021.

⁵⁴ Ibid

⁵⁵ Mariko Oi, “The dark side of Asia’s pop music industry”, BBC news, Britain 2016.

⁵⁶ Wald, Gayle, ‘Just a Girl? Rock Music, Feminism, and the Cultural Construction of Female Youth’, 2021.

As succinctly put by Oi (2016); «They are known as idols and their job is to sell dreams».⁵⁷ This essential requirement aligns seamlessly with our earlier discussion, shedding light on the nuanced interplay between how idols are depicted in real and fictional settings, and underscoring the broader cultural significance embedded in the “kawaii” phenomenon. It is about selling a carefully crafted fantasy to their audience. The restriction on dating plays a pivotal role in upholding this dreamlike quality, as it perpetuates the illusion that these idols are unblemished by the complexities of romantic relationships, and therefore, remain wholly devoted to their craft and their fans.

This essential requirement not only underscores the meticulous management of an idol’s public image but also reveals the nuanced interplay between their portrayal in real and fictional settings. The constraints imposed on idols contribute to a broader cultural significance embedded in the “kawaii” phenomenon. The notion of cuteness, innocence, and purity becomes not just an aesthetic preference but a strategic element in the construction and maintenance of the pop idol persona. In essence, the no-dating policy becomes a symbolic tool, shaping the narrative of pop idols as ethereal figures, perpetuating a sense of wonder and enchantment that captivates audiences and defines the unique landscape of the Japanese pop music industry.

On June 9, 2011, amid reports of nuclear contamination in earthquake-hit Japan, the AKB48 General Election seized the spotlight in the mass media. Representing the third iteration of this unique event for the all-girl idol group established in 2005, the election unfolded as a colossal promotional and marketing campaign. Voting rights extended not only to fan-club members but also to those who had purchased their 21st single, “Everyday, Kachūsha,” which rapidly sold 1,334,000 copies within a week—a new record for single sales in Japan. The election results were unveiled during a live ceremony at the renowned Budōkan, a venue graced by some of the world’s most famous musical acts. The ceremony was broadcast live to 86 theaters (97 screens) across Japan, spanning from Hokkaido to Okinawa, and even reaching audiences in Hong Kong, Taiwan, and South Korea. The fervor of the fans extended beyond mere enthusiasm; it evolved into a media event and a public spectacle.⁵⁸

The elevation of AKB48 members to the esteemed status of “national idols” (kokumin-teki aidoru) marked a cultural phenomenon that transcended the boundaries of entertainment,

⁵⁷ Mariko Oi, “The dark side of Asia’s pop music industry”, BBC news, Britain 2016.

⁵⁸ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 19.

permeating the collective consciousness of the Japanese populace. The annual AKB48 General Election, a pivotal event in this cultural spectacle, garnered extensive coverage from various media platforms, including print and television outlets. The election, which saw the participation of nearly 200 members, unfolded as a dramatic narrative that captivated the nation. The media's comprehensive coverage played a pivotal role in disseminating the unfolding drama to the public. Approximately 150 outlets provided regular updates on the election, ensuring that the anticipation and excitement surrounding the event reached every corner of Japanese society. The narrative was not confined to traditional media alone; online platforms, cell phone news feeds, and even commercial and news segments on trains became conduits for delivering the latest developments to a diverse audience.⁵⁹

The ubiquity of the AKB48 General Election was such that it became a topic of conversation in various social spheres. Friends, family members, coworkers, and schoolmates engaged in discussions, sharing insights, predictions, and personal preferences regarding the potential winners. The event became a cultural touchstone, shaping dialogues and fostering a sense of collective participation among the Japanese people. On the day of the General Election, the streets of Tokyo buzzed with the names of AKB48 members, transforming the cityscape into a vibrant tapestry of fan enthusiasm. The cultural phenomenon reached its zenith, making it nearly impossible to escape the influence of the event. The names of the candidates echoed through the air, resonating in public spaces, entertainment venues, and even casual conversations, highlighting the profound impact of AKB48 on the cultural landscape.⁶⁰

The profound impact of idols in Japan can be traced to the carefully cultivated and promoted individuals who fall under this category, encompassing singers, models, and media figures. Regardless of gender, idols are characterized by their projection of a youthful and appealing image, making them exceptionally attractive to a diverse range of demographics and societal groups. From music to photo albums, fashion, and accessories, idols are meticulously packaged to maximize consumption and serve as a currency of exchange in the promotion and advertising of various products and services. For the Japanese consumer deeply immersed in a culture of celebrity, the idol is synonymous with consumption. Idols serve as a form of currency in the promotion and advertising of various products and services, making them integral to the economic and cultural landscape. The idol industry thrives on creating and marketing a

⁵⁹ Ibid. 50.

⁶⁰ Ibid. 50.

carefully curated image, carefully tailored to cater to the preferences and aspirations of their target audience.⁶¹

Within the Japanese media landscape, structured around the phenomenon of idols, consumers are positioned as fans. The idol-fan dynamic is not merely transactional but rather an intricate relationship where consumers become emotionally invested followers. Idols, as objects of desire, transcend their roles as mere entertainers; they become fantasy figures, ideal constructs that serve as a “mirror” reflecting profound affective or emotional meanings for the fan-consumer. This unique cultural dynamic places Japan in a league of its own regarding the role of celebrities. Nowhere else on the globe does celebrity culture play such a central, conspicuous, and significant role in shaping societal norms and consumer behavior. The Japanese consumer, deeply immersed in a culture of celebrity, views the idol not just as an artist but as a symbol of aspiration and a conduit for emotional connection. The idol becomes an integral part of the consumer’s identity, influencing choices, preferences, and even lifestyle.⁶²

Pop idols in Japan have a captivating history that traces its roots back to the aftermath of World War Two, a time when the United States exerted a significant cultural influence on the country, persisting even after the official end of the occupation in the 1950s. In the wake of this foreign presence, there was a notable surge in the influx of American pop culture, which prompted the emergence of pop idols as a seemingly harmless and uplifting form of entertainment for the recovering Japanese society. During this transformative period, Japan sought to navigate its own cultural identity while incorporating elements of Western influence. Recognizing the appeal of pop idols as charismatic figures, Japan embarked on the mission to create its own version of these cultural icons.⁶³

The objective was not only to offer a form of entertainment but also to serve as a means of cultural expression and a reflection of the nation’s shifting values. One of the intriguing aspects of this phenomenon was the deliberate effort to replace Western idols with homegrown talent, featuring clean-cut Japanese singers who embodied the essence of purity and wholesomeness. This strategic move was a manifestation of Japan’s desire to align with its “conservative social

⁶¹ Ibid. 20.

⁶² Ibid. 20.

⁶³ Patrick Drazen, *ANIME EXPLOSION: The What? Why? & Wow of Japanese Animation* (Berkeley, California: Stone Bridge Press, 2003).

mores,”⁶⁴ providing a cultural product that resonated with the values and sensibilities of the Japanese populace in the post-war era. By distancing themselves from the Western influence that had permeated their society, Japan crafted a unique and distinctly Japanese version of pop idols. These entertainers not only represented a form of escapism for the public but also became symbols of resilience, hope, and cultural pride. This transformative journey reflects the dynamic interplay between global and local forces, showcasing how pop idols became a cultural bridge connecting the past to the present in Japan’s post-war history.

The term “idol” (アイドル) found its way into the cultural lexicon of Japan with the release of the French film *Cherchez l’idole* in 1963, later titled “In Search of an Idol” (アイドルお探す) when presented to Japanese audiences. However, it was in 1971 that the concept truly took root, and this year is often acknowledged as the “first year of the idol era” (アイドル岩塩). This marked the beginning of a cultural shift that would profoundly influence the entertainment landscape in Japan. The 1980s emerged as a significant period, now famously referred to as the “golden age of idols” (アイドルの黄金時代).⁶⁵

During this era, an astonishing 40 to 50 new idols would make their debut annually, signifying a cultural phenomenon that captured the imagination of the Japanese public. This surge in idol popularity coincided with Japan’s transition to a post-industrial society, a period marked by the bubble economy of the late 1980s. This economic phase was characterized by an emphasis on information and consumption.⁶⁶

The idol system matured against the backdrop of dynamic changes in Japanese media and entertainment. Celebrity culture, particularly the idol phenomenon, emerged as a crucial tool for organizing audiences and consumers across various platforms, including television, music, and advertising. Idols became cultural symbols, embodying the aspirations and desires of a society in flux. The emergence of idols during this golden age was not merely a reflection of musical tastes but a response to the evolving socio-economic landscape. Idols provided a form

⁶⁴ Bullock, Julia C. *The Other Women’s Lib: Gender and Body in Japanese Women’s Fiction*. Honolulu: University of Hawai’i Press, 2010. 13.

⁶⁵ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 23.

⁶⁶ *Ibid*, 23.

of escapism and fantasy. During the post-war period, Japan faced a pressing need for economic growth and recovery.⁶⁷

In this context, the emergence of idols, particularly female idols like those of AKB48, played a crucial role in fostering economic activity and capturing the imagination of the Japanese public. These idols were strategically presented as “idols that you can meet,” creating a unique and intimate connection with fans. This marketing strategy, marked by the practice of selling the same product multiple times, became synonymous with AKB48’s success. The group ingeniously packaged their CD singles with distinct posters, encouraging fans to collect them all for the opportunity to attend exclusive events.⁶⁸

The idol phenomenon of the 1980s represents more than a mere trend; it reflects a seismic shift in the way Japanese society consumed entertainment and engaged with cultural symbols. The idols of this era were not confined to music; they permeated every facet of daily life, from television screens to magazine covers, becoming an integral part of the consumer experience. The “golden age of idols” thus stands as a testament to the adaptability of Japanese pop culture and its ability to mirror, influence, and shape the societal landscape during a transformative period.

The economic impact of AKB48’s activities transcended conventional models, delving into innovative marketing approaches that revolutionized the music industry. One notable strategy that underscored their financial success was the introduction of handshake events intricately tied to CD purchases. This approach not only served as a lucrative source of revenue but also created a profound sense of intimacy between fans and their cherished idols.⁶⁹

The handshake events, where fans could meet and greet their favorite idols in person, created a unique dynamic that went beyond the traditional boundaries of the music business. Fans were incentivized to purchase multiple copies of CDs to gain more opportunities for these personal interactions. This not only boosted sales but also established a tangible connection between the fans and the idols, elevating the entire fan experience.⁷⁰

⁶⁷ Ibid. 45.

⁶⁸ Ibid. 45.

⁶⁹ Ibid. 48.

⁷⁰ Ibid. 48.

Despite the occasional controversies that peppered AKB48's journey, such as the cancellation of a special event due to antitrust concerns, the economic model persisted. The intertwining of votes with emotional investment through CD purchases became a cornerstone of the fan-idol relationship. The act of buying CDs transformed from a mere transaction into a gesture of devotion, a tangible expression of support that went beyond the realm of conventional music consumption.⁷¹

On various online platforms, certain fans advocate for the principle of "one man, one vote." However, as expressed by an AKB48 member, if we consider "votes as your love," then the rationale becomes apparent. According to this philosophy, an individual could demonstrate a more profound affection for an idol by purchasing multiple CDs and allocating a corresponding number of votes, directly linking the intensity of their love to their financial commitment.⁷²

In essence, this correlation of votes with emotions reflected a form of commodity fetishism within the fan community. The act of purchasing CDs became a symbolic representation of emotional investment, transforming the tangible product into a conduit for expressing adoration and support. AKB48's economic model, thus, not only redefined the traditional music industry approach but also highlighted the intricate and nuanced ways in which fans could forge emotional connections with their idols through the commodification of their affections.⁷³

Within this cultural landscape, the emergence of "national idols" stands out as a phenomenon where symbolic figures transcend their roles as mere entertainers to become representatives of the collective ethos, inspiring sentiments that resonate with the wider populace. The question of whether these idols can truly detach their actions from their carefully crafted images poses a complex challenge, particularly when their advocacy becomes intertwined with self-promotion, serving as a strategic tool to garner attention, enhance public visibility, and ultimately drive sales. However, the crucial point lies in recognizing that idols can function as political commodities akin to their role as economic commodities. They both shape and are shaped by the issues at hand, with the audience engaging with and through idols in the consumption of these concerns.⁷⁴

⁷¹ Ibid. 48.

⁷² Ibid. 48.

⁷³ Ibid. 48.

⁷⁴ Ibid. 50.

1.2 Pop Idol Culture: The Clash Between Fantasy and Reality

What pop idols represent in the coordinates of “other” desire?

This section delves into the intricate dynamics of idol media, exploring the multifaceted layers of desire and consumption that envelop surround this complex cultural phenomenon. In conversations with men, a recurring theme emerged— a pronounced emphasis on “purity”, within the context of idol imagery, despite the images carrying evident sexual undertones. This paradox reveals the multifaceted nature of the idol-fan relationship and the intricate dance between desire and societal expectations.⁷⁵

The gaze in these images perpetuates a continuous movement, navigating the delicate balance between maintaining an illusion of innocence and the subtle exploration of more sensual elements. This oscillation is particularly notable, shifting seamlessly between the face and thighs, embodying a decentered eroticism that titillates without overtly crossing societal boundaries. This oscillation creates a dynamic where reassurance and approval become intertwined elements, as fans seek a delicate equilibrium that fulfills both their desire for allure and their societal yearning for purity.⁷⁶

Interestingly, despite the overtly sensual nature of some idol images, the men engaging with this media rarely categorized idol photographs or image videos as explicit material for personal gratification. Even though they acknowledged participating in such activities, they were quick to differentiate idol media from conventional pornography.⁷⁷

According to their perspective, pornography served a more direct and efficient purpose for those needs, highlighting the distinctive and complex nature of idol media consumption.⁷⁸ This unique perspective underscores the multifaceted role that idol media plays in the lives of fans. It serves not merely as a conduit for sexual gratification but as a complex tapestry of desire, approval, and reassurance.

The men engaging with idol media navigate a delicate balance between societal expectations and personal desires, finding a space where the allure of the idol can be appreciated without being overtly labeled as explicit material. The dynamics at play within the world of idol media

⁷⁵ Ibid. 271.

⁷⁶ Ibid. 271.

⁷⁷ Ibid. 272.

⁷⁸ Ibid. 272.

unveil a complex interplay between societal norms, individual desires, and the intricate dance of visual representation. The images, carefully curated to embody both innocence and sensuality, become a focal point for fans seeking a unique form of gratification that transcends traditional categories. In exploring the distinct nature of idol media consumption, we uncover a rich tapestry of desire, approval, and societal negotiation that defines this unique cultural phenomenon.

The pleasure derived from engaging with idol media manifests in diverse and meaningful ways, with enthusiasts often articulating their experiences through three common lenses: Firstly, the act of engaging with idol media is described as providing a sense of “healing” (癒やされる). In this context, idol content offers a therapeutic escape from the stresses of daily life. The portrayal of idols in serene or exotic environments becomes a form of visual and emotional respite, creating a tranquil space where fans can temporarily detach from their hectic routines.⁷⁹

Secondly, fans express that idol media brings forth a surge of “energy” (元気が出る). The youthful and exuberant depictions of idols engaging in activities such as running, jumping, and eating inject a sense of vitality and joy into the viewer's experience. These depictions become a source of infectious positivity, uplifting the spirits of fans and providing a vibrant counterbalance to the challenges they may face in their own lives.⁸⁰

Thirdly, the consumption of idol media enables viewers to witness the idol’s “growth” (成長). This aspect fosters a sense of connection and closeness as fans follow the idol’s journey over time. The intertextual meanings developed across various works contribute to a nostalgic consumption, creating a narrative thread that fans can trace from the idol’s early appearances to their present moment. This sense of continuity deepens the emotional bond between the fan and the idol, forging a connection that transcends the boundaries of time and space. Fans frequently depict idols and the relationships they share with them as inherently “pure” (純粋).

This purity is not merely a reflection of the idol’s image but is imbued with a sense of innocence, sincerity, and unblemished joy that resonates with fans. The concept of purity becomes a

⁷⁹ Ibid. 272.

⁸⁰ Ibid. 272.

cornerstone of the fan-idol dynamic, contributing to the overall positive and uplifting experience that fans seek in their engagement with idol media.⁸¹

In summary, the pleasure derived from idol media goes beyond the superficial and enters the realms of emotional and psychological fulfillment. Whether providing healing, bringing energy, or enabling viewers to witness growth, idol media becomes a multifaceted source of joy and connection for fans. The inherent purity attributed to idols enhances the emotional resonance, creating a unique cultural space where fans find solace, inspiration, and a sense of shared growth with the idols they hold dear.

Lamarre's exploration of animated television characters provides a fascinating perspective on how images can transcend the confines of the screen and seamlessly integrate with various objects and contexts. He introduces the concept of "soulful bodies," suggesting that due to the visual limitations inherent in animated characters, these entities take on spiritual, emotional, or psychological qualities that are visibly present on their surfaces. This notion becomes particularly pertinent when examining the phenomenon of idols or animated characters, as their images possess a unique ability to transcend the screen and attach themselves to a myriad of commodities.⁸² The concept of "soulful bodies" implies that the animated characters or idols are not confined to the two-dimensional realm of the screen; instead, they carry a palpable essence that can be transported onto different surfaces.

Lamarre's notion of bringing movement to the image's surface is crucial in understanding how these animated characters become more than mere visual representations. They transform into portable animus, embodying a soulful image that has the capacity to attach itself to anything or anyone.⁸³ In the context of idols or animated characters, this phenomenon is vividly evident in their ability to captivate a range of commodities.⁸⁴ The image of an idol, for example, can traverse diverse surfaces, from merchandise such as posters, clothing, and accessories to digital platforms, creating an expansive network of soulful connections. The transfer and localization of soul, as Lamarre describes it, suggest that the essence of the animated character or idol is not static but dynamic, able to adapt and resonate with different objects and environments.

⁸¹ Ibid. 272.

⁸² Lamarre, Thomas. *The Anime Machine: A Media Theory of Animation*. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press, 2009. 201.

⁸³ Ibid. 206.

⁸⁴ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 283.

The idol's image, in this sense, becomes a versatile cultural currency that transcends the boundaries of traditional media. It migrates beyond the screen, finding a home on tangible items that fans can collect, wear, and interact with. This process of localization and transfer of soul is a testament to the profound impact these characters have on consumer culture, shaping not only visual aesthetics but also emotional and spiritual connections between the fan and the idol. In essence, Lamarre's concept of "soulful bodies" sheds light on the transformative nature of animated characters and idols. It invites us to consider these images not as static representations but as dynamic entities capable of infusing soul and essence into a wide array of commodities. This phenomenon captures the essence of the idol's cultural significance, extending their influence far beyond the confines of the screen and into the tangible, lived experiences of their devoted fans.

Drawing parallels between the idol as an image and the animated character as a soulful body may seem unfair, but Roland Barthes' perspective on photography provides an insightful lens for understanding the profound impact of these visual representations. Barthes (1983), likened all photography to spirit photography, suggesting that it captures what is absent or has already transpired, invoking a spirit or "soul." This perspective lays the groundwork for contemplating the idol's emotional resonance and its multifaceted existence as both a static image and a dynamic force.⁸⁵

While the concept of a soulful body captures the idea of animated characters carrying spiritual or emotional qualities on their surfaces, it may not fully elucidate the idol's emotional impact. Unlike animated characters, the idol's energy isn't solely propelled by residual traces from live performances or internal movements projected onto the surface. Instead, the idol's energy is continually revitalized by the fans themselves. Fans inject their own energy into the seemingly static image, channeling its effects through physical intimacies, rituals, and emotional engagements.⁸⁶

Fans play a pivotal role in drawing out internal movements within the idol's image. By investing their emotions, dreams, and desires, they become active participants in the idol's narrative. In this dynamic interaction, fans are not just passive consumers but contributors to

⁸⁵ Barthes, Roland. *Empire of Signs*. Hill and Wang, 1983. 14.

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*

the animation of the idol. The idol, therefore, exists in a state where it is both “dead” as a static image and “alive” in its pulsating affective force, fueled by the collective energy of its admirers.

In essence, the idol as an image transcends the boundaries between life and artifice. It becomes a complex entity that pulsates with the affective force generated by its movement, layered contexts, and embedded social relations. The idol is not a static representation frozen in time; it is a living entity brought to life by the dreams and desires of those who interact with its image. This dual nature, oscillating between stillness and animation, captures the essence of the idol's cultural significance, where the boundary between image and lived experience becomes fluid and permeable.⁸⁷

The central focus of this section is on the intricate web of production, circulation, and consumption that surrounds idols, unveiling the complex libidinal and material economy inherent in these images. It acknowledges the potential risk of equating idols with images, an equation that might inadvertently overlook the agency of women. However, the intention is far from complicity with any systematic denial of female agency. Instead, it seeks to underscore the existence of women and the agency possessed by idols within the complex economy of image production.

In Japan, the creation of fantasies becomes a thriving industry where the object of desire remains intentionally elusive, the climactic resolution is perpetually deferred, and the ongoing serialization of interactions is commodified as a seemingly harmless fantasy⁸⁸. This fantasy-making industry emerges as a powerful force, shaping the cultural landscape and influencing the dynamics of consumption. The analysis in this section draws from a broad spectrum of theoretical frameworks, including object relations, contemporary Freudian approaches, Lacanian psychoanalysis, and psychoanalytic psychotherapy, to unpack the complex layers of meaning embedded in the idol phenomenon.

By focusing on the libidinal and material economy surrounding idols, the analysis explores how these images become more than mere representations; they become conduits for desire, fantasy, and emotional investment. The intentional deferral of climactic resolution creates a continuous cycle of anticipation, keeping the audience engaged in an ongoing narrative that

⁸⁷ Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 283.

⁸⁸ *Ibid.* 274.

fuels the commodification of harmless fantasy. This cycle not only sustains the industry but also positions idols as active agents in shaping the desires and expectations of their audience.

It is crucial to recognize that this discussion does not seek to overlook or undermine the agency of women. On the contrary, it aims to shed light on the complex negotiation of agency within the idol industry. Idols, as women within this context, navigate and negotiate their agency within the constraints and opportunities presented by the image-making industry. Understanding this intricate dance between agency, desire, and fantasy is essential for grasping the dynamics of the idol phenomenon and its broader cultural implications.

Nearly four decades ago, Jenson (1992) highlighted a prevalent theme on how the literature on fandom was haunted with fans often characterized as individuals exhibiting excessive and obsessive behavior. The stereotype of the fervent fan, at that time, was often associated with lonely, socially awkward men.⁸⁹ This stereotype is vividly portrayed in the film “*Perfect Blue*,” where the character of the stalker aligns with this prevailing image. In one of the initial scenes of the movie, as Mima performs on stage, a pivotal moment unfolds when the stalker is shown holding an image of her.⁹⁰ This scene serves as a revelation that the stalker has developed a deep attachment to the represented image of Mima.

The attachment that the stalker forms with the image of Mima is explored in Freudian terms, where a connection is made between the stalker's libido and the represented image of Mima as a love-object.⁹¹ This attachment gives rise to a fantasy, described as «the imaginary part-object which stands for the unattainable object of desire, » and this fantasy revolves around the idol image.⁹² Freudian psychoanalysis provides a lens to understand the complex dynamics at play in the stalker's behavior. The attachment formed between the stalker's libido and Mima's image illustrates the way in which fans can invest their desires and fantasies into the representation of an idol. The idol becomes a vessel for the fan's unattainable object of desire, a symbolic figure onto which they project their emotional and libidinal energies.⁹³

⁸⁹ Lewis, Lisa A., ed. *The Adoring Audience: Fan Culture and Popular Media*. London ; New York: Routledge, 1992. 18.

⁹⁰ Satoshi Kon, “*Perfect Blue*”, 1997

⁹¹ Sigmund Freud, *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia* (London, England: Penguin Books, 2005). 44.

⁹² Stewart, Elizabeth. *Catastrophe and Survival: Walter Benjamin and Psychoanalysis*. London: Continuum, 2010. 33.

⁹³ Sigmund Freud, *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia* (London, England: Penguin Books, 2005). 44.

This dynamic is reflective of broader discussions around fan behavior and the emotional investment fans make in the objects of their admiration. It goes beyond the surface level of fandom, delving into the deeper psychological dimensions where individuals form intimate connections with representations of their idols. In the context of “*Perfect Blue*,” this exploration of fan psychology adds layers of complexity to the narrative, underscoring the intricate interplay between desire, fantasy, and the idol image in the minds of fans.

This psychoanalytic exploration sheds light on the profound and disturbing nature of our relationship with sexuality, as Freud emphasized the centrality of sexuality in constructing fantasies about love and the pursuit of satisfaction in intimate connections. Freud’s insights resonate, revealing the intricate ways in which the human psyche grapples with desire and the construction of fantasies. In these fundamental assumptions about the self, intricate culturally specific images come into play, shaping our understanding of internal and external boundaries, the primary forms of motivation, and how these motivations manifest.⁹⁴

The preceding discussion about the image of the idol introduces a nuanced layer, where the idol’s image is intricately intertwined with the concept of purity. In this context, the core specter of sexuality, around which various fantasies are constructed, transforms into a gaze directed at an image. The complex interplay of cultural perceptions, motivations, and self-disclosure becomes entwined with the necessity for the idol's image to embody purity. This redirection shifts the focus from explicit sexuality to a gaze fixated on an idealized representation⁹⁵, a theme intimately connected to the stalker's fixation on the idol image of Mima. Consequently, Stalker fails to perceive the disparity between this constructed image and the actual reality, as articulated by Freud’s concept of the “real slight”.⁹⁶ It's crucial to clarify that by “real slight,” we refer not to an ongoing and tangible reality, but rather the acknowledgment of something beyond the confines of fantasy.

The construction of an idealized, pure image of the idol creates a perceptual filter through which fans, including the stalker in the case of Mima, engage with the object of their desire. The idol becomes a vessel for the projection of fantasies, providing a space where the complexities of real-life interactions are replaced by an idealized and controlled narrative. The disconnect between this constructed image and reality, as highlighted by the concept of the

⁹⁴ Parker, Ian. *Japan in Analysis: Cultures of the Unconscious*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008. 2.

⁹⁵ Ibid

⁹⁶ Sigmund Freud, *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia* (London, England: Penguin Books, 2005). 200.

“real slight,” underscores the challenge in navigating the boundaries between fantasy and the tangible, lived experience.

When Mima undergoes a transition from being an idol to an actor, taking on a role that involves a rape scene, a profound collision occurs between the realms of fantasy and reality in the film “*Perfect Blue*”.⁹⁷ This collision is reminiscent of Freud’s notion that such clashes arise «through the influence of a real slight or disappointment on the part of the beloved person. »⁹⁸ Stalker, having formed an intense attachment to the idol image of Mima, experiences a rupture as the character he adores is placed in a situation that challenges the idealized fantasy. The emergence of this gap in Stalker’s perception symbolizes a disturbance in the special cultivated object-relation he had developed with the idolized Mima. Freud’s notion that such disruptions occur due to a “real slight” is reflected in Stalker’s experience, where the idealized image of Mima clashes with the unsettling reality portrayed in the rape scene. This clash serves as a sudden realization «that object-relation had been subjected to a shock,»⁹⁹ challenging the fantasy that Stalker had invested in and revealing the inevitable imperfections and dissonances between the idol’s projected image and the idol’s real-life roles.

Faced with the unsettling reality, Stalker chooses to avoid direct confrontation, preferring to circle around the gap that has emerged. This avoidance is deeply rooted in the fear that acknowledging the real slight would quash the desire. as the essence of desire thrives on dissatisfaction. As Stewart (2010) suggests, «human desire has to make restitution and to make whole.»¹⁰⁰ This prompts Stalker’s desire to persistently rotate around the unfulfilled gap rather than confronting the disruptive reality. Stewart’s assertion aligns with Stalker’s persistent circling around the unfulfilled gap. Rather than directly confronting the discomforting truth, Stalker opts for a continuous rotation, perpetuating a cycle where desire remains intact by avoiding a direct encounter with the disruptive reality. This cyclic motion serves as a coping mechanism, allowing Stalker to maintain the illusion of the idealized Mima while shielding himself from the disconcerting realities of her on-screen roles.

This process can be readily reconstructed and be understood by tracing its steps. Initially, an object-choice takes place, forming a connection between one’s libido and a specific person.

⁹⁷ Satoshi Kon, “*Perfect Blue*”, 1997.

⁹⁸ Sigmund Freud, *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia* (London, England: Penguin Books, 2005). 200.

⁹⁹ *Ibid*, 200.

¹⁰⁰ Stewart, Elizabeth. *Catastrophe and Survival: Walter Benjamin and Psychoanalysis*. London: Continuum, 2010. 12.

However, the influence of a “real slight” or disappointment from the beloved person (the chosen object of desire) causes a shock to this object-relation. Unlike the “usual” response of withdrawing the libido from the object and redirecting it to a new one, a different outcome emerged, contingent on various conditions.¹⁰¹

In this case, object investment weakened and was put on hold. Rather than being displaced onto a different object, the free libido retracted into the ego. Despite returning to the ego, this emotional energy (libido) does not find an immediate outlet or purpose. Consequently, the ego starts identifying with the abandoned object, as there is a void created by the weakened emotional connection. This identification results in the object’s shadow casting upon the ego, enabling a specific agency to criticize the ego as if it were the abandoned object. This transformation turns the loss of the object into a loss of ego, converting the conflict between the ego and the beloved person into a dichotomy. This description resonates with Freud’s insights from “*On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia*.”¹⁰²

After the widespread publication of Mima’s erotic photos in magazines, Stalker’s desire becomes even more intensely exposed to this real slight. This heightened exposure leads to a state of madness and a psychotic catastrophe, which is a form of confrontation with the Real in life.¹⁰³ In response to this turmoil, Stalker embarks on a violent spree, directing his aggression towards those whom he perceives as responsible for tarnishing his elevated and idealized perception of Mima.¹⁰⁴ The underlying logic driving this desire is rooted in obsession, and the inherent logic of obsession is centered around reproduction.¹⁰⁵ This obsessive cycle doesn’t have an output and requires pure violence often «accompanied by excessive passion and suffering.»¹⁰⁶

Stalker consistently subjects Mima to various forms of direct and indirect pressure, insinuating that she is no longer the person she should be or once was. This campaign of pressure reflects his desperate attempt to regain control over the shattered fantasy he had constructed around Mima. The exposure of Mima’s erotic photos serves as a catalyst, shattering the illusions

¹⁰¹ Sigmund Freud, *On Murder, Mourning and Melancholia* (London, England: Penguin Books, 2005). 200.

¹⁰² *Ibid.*, 200.

¹⁰³ Stewart, Elizabeth. *Catastrophe and Survival: Walter Benjamin and Psychoanalysis*. London: Continuum, 2010. 137.

¹⁰⁴ Satoshi Kon, “Perfect Blue”, 1997.

¹⁰⁵ Freud, Sigmund. *Three Essays on the Theory of Sexuality: The 1905 Edition*. Translated by Ulrike Kistner. Edited and Introduced by Philippe Van Haute and Herman Westerink. London, New York: Verso, 2016. 121.

¹⁰⁶ Stewart, Elizabeth. *Catastrophe and Survival: Walter Benjamin and Psychoanalysis*. London: Continuum, 2010. 9.

Stalker had held onto and forcing him to confront the harsh realities of Mima's public image versus his idealized imagination.¹⁰⁷

In this descent into madness, the psychotic catastrophe represents a collision with the raw, unaltered aspects of reality that Stalker had been avoiding. The violent spree becomes a desperate and destructive attempt to restore the transcendental imagination of Mima, even if it means inflicting harm on those who, in Stalker's distorted perception, stand in the way of this restoration. The logic of obsession, in this context, spirals into a self-perpetuating cycle where desire intensifies without finding a constructive outlet. This lack of a clear resolution amplifies the intensity of Stalker's actions, driving him to resort to extreme measures. The insistence on subjecting Mima to various forms of pressure reflects Stalker's desperate attempt to mold her back into the idealized figure that existed within the realm of his obsessive imagination.¹⁰⁸

The examination of stars and celebrities within the realm of fan studies, as extensively discussed often overlooks the intricate dynamics of how fans autonomously engage with images.¹⁰⁹ These images, rather than being accurate representations of external realities, serve as idealized depictions Jacques Lacan, a psychoanalyst, linked this idealized image of the external other to a concept known as the "mirror stage." This oversight becomes particularly apparent when delving into the realm of male fans, where psychoanalytic theories, such as Jacques Lacan's "mirror stage," offer compelling insights. Lacan's concept posits that the formation of the Ego is a process deeply rooted in objectification. When an infant encounters its reflection in the mirror, this image serves as a pivotal element in constructing a unified sense of self.¹¹⁰ However, concurrently, this process involves a misrecognition of an entirely autonomous and whole self.

In the context of fan engagement, individuals interact with images of stars and celebrities, constructing a perception that aligns with Lacan's notion of the mirror stage. Fans often encounter these idealized images, projecting onto them their desires, aspirations, and a sense of identification. Much like the infant encountering its reflection, fans use these images as mirrors to form a unified sense of self in relation to the admired celebrity. The images of stars and celebrities, curated for public consumption, serve as distorted mirrors reflecting idealized versions of the external other. Fans engage in a process of misrecognition, projecting onto these

¹⁰⁷ Satoshi Kon, "Perfect Blue", 1997.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid

¹⁰⁹ Dyer, Richard, and Paul McDonald. Stars. New ed. London: BFI Publishing, 1998.

¹¹⁰ Lacan, Jacques, and Alan Sheridan. *Écrits: A Selection*. London: Routledge, 2001. 1-6.

images a sense of completeness and perfection that may not accurately represent the complex realities of the individuals behind the celebrity persona. The mirror stage concept becomes a useful framework for understanding how fans construct a sense of self through their interactions with these images.

Lacan's ideas extend to the broader structure of male desire, proposing that humans, grappling with an inherent sense of lack or incompleteness, seek to remedy this by forging images of themselves as complete entities through attachment to external objects. This intricate interplay between the construction of self and external objects is fundamental to the structure of male desire. Lacan's assertion that "the woman does not exist" or exists as a "symptom of man" underscores the idea that the feminine is constructed to ensure the ontological consistency of the masculine.¹¹¹

In Lacanian psychoanalysis, the concept of "lack" is pivotal to understanding desire. Humans, according to Lacan, grapple with a fundamental sense of inadequacy or incompleteness, a lack that originates from the very nature of language and the symbolic order. In their quest to address this lack and attain a sense of completeness, individuals construct idealized images of themselves. This process is not isolated but intricately entwined with external objects, such as the images of stars and celebrities.

In the context of male desire, this process of self-construction becomes particularly pronounced. Men, in their pursuit of completeness, often project their aspirations, desires, and ideals onto external objects, including the idealized images of women. The external object, in this case, serves as a mirror or a canvas upon which men paint their notions of completeness and perfection. The woman, within this framework, becomes a symbolic representation, a construct designed to facilitate the sense of ontological consistency within the masculine identity.

Lacan's assertion that "the woman does not exist" does not negate the existence of actual women but rather challenges the notion of an essential, fully comprehensible feminine identity. Instead, the feminine is posited as a symptom or a signifier within the structure of male desire. In Lacanian terms, this means that the construction of the feminine is contingent on its role in remedying the perceived lack within the masculine. The woman becomes a crucial element in

¹¹¹ Lamarre, Thomas. *The Anime Machine: A Media Theory of Animation*. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press, 2009. 236.

the symbolic order, a representation woven into the fabric of male desire to fill the void and ensure a semblance of completeness.

This intricate interplay between self-construction, external objects, and the symbolic role of the feminine not only sheds light on the structure of male desire but also underscores the complex and often illusory nature of gender dynamics. Lacan's insights invite us to critically examine the construction of gender identities, the symbolic roles assigned to different genders, and the ways in which individuals navigate their desires and sense of self within this intricate web of symbolic meaning. Saitō Tamaki explains:

«Desire directed at the *object a* incarnates desire as an illusion within the symbolic world [...] The male follows a chain of metaphors directed towards the desired *object a* that he cannot attain. In the process, he constructs the illusion called knowledge. What he tries to possess (e.g., the illusion of the woman) is actually a stand-in for the singular *object a* that perpetually eludes his grasp.»¹¹²

Within the Japanese cultural context, the phrase “sōzō suru (想像する),” meaning “to imagine” and homonymous with “to create,” encapsulates a nuanced understanding of a complex process. This dual meaning emphasizes that the act of imagination is not merely a mental exercise but also a creative force, contributing significantly to the construction of both the other and the self. Consequently, the pursuit of objects, even upon their possession, sets in motion a perpetual cycle of desire, acquisition, and an enduring sense of lack.¹¹³

The term “sōzō suru” carries a depth that extends beyond the mere act of conjuring mental images. It underscores the creative power embedded in the act of imagination, suggesting that when individuals engage in envisioning or creating mental images, they are actively participating in a process that shapes not only their perceptions of external objects but also their own self-concept. This dualistic nature of “sōzō suru” illuminates the paradoxical nature of desire and acquisition. The pursuit of objects, driven by the imaginative and creative forces at play, is marked by a perpetual cycle. Even upon obtaining the desired objects, the sense of fulfillment remains elusive, as the imaginative aspect of desire persists, perpetuating a continuous loop of wanting, acquiring, and feeling incomplete.

¹¹² Galbraith, Patrick W., and Jason G. Karlin, eds. *Idols and Celebrity in Japanese Media Culture*. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire ; New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2012. 268.

¹¹³ *Ibid.* 269.

This cultural insight challenges conventional notions of possession and satisfaction, suggesting that the act of imagination is a potent force that transcends material acquisition. The constant interplay between imagining and creating implies an ongoing process of self-construction and perception of the external world. In this intricate dance, desire becomes not just a yearning for physical possession but a deeper engagement with the creative forces that shape one's identity and understanding of the surrounding reality.

In essence, “sōzō suru” unveils a profound cultural perspective on the dynamics of desire and imagination. It invites contemplation on the dual nature of the creative act, emphasizing that the imaginative process, far from being confined to the mind, actively participates in shaping the ongoing construction of self and other. The recognition of this process sheds light on the complex and ever-evolving relationship between desire, imagination, and the persistent quest for a sense of completeness within the Japanese cultural context.

In a pivotal scene towards the conclusion of the anime, the character of Mima’s manager assumes a crucial role in the unfolding narrative, revealing deeper layers of the story’s complexity. Throughout the film, the manager diligently works to preserve Mima’s perceived innocence, acting as a guardian within the realm of Mima’s professional life. Guiding Mima to what is purported to be “Mima’s room,” the manager’s intentions initially appear to be protective. However, as Mima spends more time in this space, she gradually discerns that it diverges significantly from her actual room.¹¹⁴

The manager’s role as a guardian is established through the careful curation of Mima’s public image. In the competitive and often cutthroat world of the entertainment industry, the manager is portrayed as a steadfast protector of Mima’s innocence and virtue. This strategic management is essential for maintaining Mima’s appeal as an idol, aligning with the expectations of her fan base and the broader cultural perception of pop idols as embodiments of purity.

The symbolic significance of “Mima’s room” within the narrative becomes apparent as the plot unfolds. This space is not merely a physical location but serves as a metaphorical representation of Mima’s constructed identity. The divergence between the purported “Mima’s room” and her actual room mirrors the dissonance between the idealized image projected to the public and the realities of her private life. It highlights the artificiality inherent in the construction of a

¹¹⁴ Satoshi Kon, “Perfect Blue”, 1997.

celebrity's persona, emphasizing the gap between the carefully crafted public image and the authentic, multifaceted individual behind it.

As Mima navigates this distorted version of her supposed sanctuary, the narrative explores themes of self-discovery and the consequences of adhering to societal expectations. The manager's seemingly protective intentions take on a more ominous undertone, revealing the manipulative nature of the entertainment industry and the toll it can take on an individual's sense of self. This narrative twist also underscores the broader commentary on the commodification of idols and the sacrifices they make for the sake of maintaining an idealized image. The manager, as a representative of the industry, becomes a compelling character through whom the complexities of fame, identity, and the blurred lines between reality and illusion are explored.

The turning point of this scene lies on the visual representation captured by the camera, unraveling a mesmerizing duality that holds profound implications for the narrative. A reflection in the mirror unveils a striking dual image, introducing a thematic complexity that reverberates throughout the story. In this reflective surface, Mima's manager is portrayed wearing Mima's former costume. This dual representation encapsulates significant thematic nuances within the narrative, exploring the intricacies of identity and perception.

Adding a layer of intricacy, the auditory dimension of this scene also unfolds in a twofold harmony. The girl standing in front of Mima embodies Mima herself, while the reflected figure in the mirror is none other than her manager, laboring under the misapprehension that she is the authentic Mima.¹¹⁵ This convergence of visual and auditory elements creates a surreal atmosphere, blurring the boundaries between reality and illusion, echoing the broader theme of the anime.

This interplay of reflections and voices contributes nuanced layers to the storyline, revealing the intricate relationship between perception and reality—a central theme that underscores the psychological depth of the anime. The symbolism inherent in this moment underscores the tension between external appearances and internal truths, enriching the narrative with profound psychological undertones.

¹¹⁵ Ibid

The misapprehension of the manager, believing herself to be the authentic Mima, introduces a layer of psychological tension. It delves into the theme of self-delusion and the internal conflicts faced by individuals navigating the demands of the industry. This revelation exposes the manager's own struggle with identity and the toll the performative aspects of her role have taken on her perception of reality. In essence, this scene becomes a microcosm of the anime's broader exploration of the psychological challenges faced by those in the spotlight.

The convergence of visual and auditory elements, coupled with the symbolism inherent in the reflected image, weaves a narrative tapestry that invites contemplation on the complexities of identity, perception, and the relentless pursuit of fame. The scene underscores the anime's thematic depth and its ability to navigate the intricate interplay between the seen and the unseen, the perceived and the actual, within the realm of celebrity culture.

This particular scene serves as a profound illustration of the manager's attempt to compensate for the loss experienced by the Id, utilizing theoretical insights from Freudian psychoanalysis to unravel its psychological complexities. Freud's elucidation of melancholia's painful disorder rested on the notion that individuals afflicted by it had reinstated a lost object within the ego. In simpler terms, Freud proposed that in those experiencing melancholia, the emotional investment in an object (object-cathexis) was replaced by an identification with that object, creating an internalized representation of it.

At that juncture, Freud didn't fully grasp the profound significance of this psychological process and its prevalence. Subsequently, he came to realize that such substitutions play a substantial role in shaping the ego's form, making a vital contribution to the development of what is commonly referred to as one's character. This insight has broad implications for understanding how individuals internalize and identify with lost or significant objects, influencing the formation of their personalities.¹¹⁶

Therefore, in Freudian terms, the manager embarks on an endeavor to address the loss experienced by the Id through a complex psychological process. This involves translating the object-cathexis, represented by Mima's features, into action—a process akin to appropriating the object's attributes as if they were inherent to the self. This mirrors Freud's notion of the ego presenting itself as a love-object to the id, urging it to recognize the ego as a viable and

¹¹⁶ Freud, Sigmund, and James Strachey. *The Ego and the Id*. The Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud. New York: Norton, 1989. 23.

lovable entity through a semblance to the lost love-object. The confrontation between the manager and Mima unfolds as a psychological drama wherein the manager simulates the ego's relationship with the lost love-object. Employing Freud's perspective, the manager implores the id, symbolized by Mima, to acknowledge the ego by highlighting the similarity between the ego and the lost object. Freud explains:

«When the ego assumes the features of the object, it is forcing itself, so to speak, upon the id as a love object and is trying to make good the id's loss by saying: "Look, you can love me too- I am so like the object." »¹¹⁷

In exploring the psychoanalytic framework, the anime scene featuring the manager echoes Freud's conceptualization of melancholia. The symbolic act of the manager donning Mima's former costume serves as a manifestation of her attempt to incorporate the lost object, Mima's past persona, into her own identity. The external representation through the costume acts as a surrogate for the internalized Mima, revealing the manager's complex psychological response to the perceived loss.

Freud's notion that such internalizations significantly contribute to the development of one's character aligns with the manager's actions, offering a lens through which to comprehend the intricacies of her behavior. This substitution of emotional investment with identification, as portrayed in the scene, sheds light on the manager's psychological process, where she seeks restitution for the perceived loss by assimilating aspects of Mima's past identity and attempting to fill the void within her own ego with elements of Mima's character.

This Freudian perspective enriches the understanding of the scene's profound implications by unveiling nuanced ways individuals grapple with loss. The internalized representations of significant objects become tools for shaping their characters. The scene serves as a compelling exploration of the psychological intricacies involved in the manager's attempt to reconcile with the shifting dynamics of the entertainment industry and the evolving identity of the idol she manages.

Freud's concept of object-cathexis, denoting emotional investment in a specific object, is evident in the manager's actions. Emotionally investing in Mima's past persona and features, the manager incorporates elements of Mima's character to bridge the gap created by the shifting

¹¹⁷ Ibid. 24.

dynamics in Mima's identity. This action becomes an attempt to reclaim control over the changing narrative and provides a solution to the perceived loss experienced by the Id.

In the Freudian framework, the scene unfolds as a symbolic negotiation between the manager and Mima. The manager, by mirroring Mima's features, aims to evoke a response from the Id that acknowledges the ego. This psychological drama represents the complex interplay between conscious and unconscious elements of the psyche. The scene, through a Freudian lens, becomes a poignant depiction of the ego's role in self-preservation and identity formation. The manager's strategy, rooted in Freudian dynamics, involves presenting the ego to the Id, seeking validation and recognition through a connection to the lost love-object. These psychological intricacies underscore the manager's profound efforts to navigate the complexities of fame, identity, and the relentless pursuit of a stable and recognizable persona within the turbulent realm of the entertainment industry.

However, the interaction between the manager and Mima escalates into a dispute, prompting Mima to flee to the street. As the manager catches up, a pivotal moment transpires: Mima forcibly removes the manager's wig, exposing her true identity. This action, while symbolic, carries profound psychological implications. The manager, confronted with her unmasked self, experiences a rupture in the carefully constructed identification with the object-cathexis inside the ego. The loss of the object—both symbolically and literally—shatters the manager's attempt at ego preservation.

In a desperate proposal to regain control and eliminate the "other" within herself, the manager rushes toward a fast-moving car, culminating in an act of suicide. Freudian theory sheds light on this dramatic act, interpreting it as the unconscious striving to get rid of that part of the ego that has been replaced by an identification with object-cathexis. This psychoanalytic interpretation unveils the intricate interplay of psychological forces, showcasing how the characters grapple with internal conflicts and attempts to navigate the intricate landscape of desire, identity, and loss.

Our exploration has thus far focused on uncovering the surface layer of anime to expose the foundations of pop idol cultures. However, the notions of sanctity and innocence in Japan represent just one facet of the fantasies projected by fans. Meanwhile, the character of Mima undergoes a profound transformation, and this metamorphosis is intricately linked to the deeply ingrained cultural ideals surrounding the sanctity of the body in Japan. This prompts us to delve

into a crucial inquiry: how does the disintegration of the body correlate with the disintegration of the mind in the context of Japanese culture? ¹¹⁸ This question serves as a gateway to our forthcoming exploration, where we aim to unravel the intricate processes that intertwine the disintegration of the body with the disintegration of the mind in Japan.

In Japan, cultural ideals regarding the sanctity of the body are deeply rooted in traditional beliefs and societal norms. The body is often seen as a vessel for purity and morality, and any deviation from this idealized image is met with societal scrutiny. This perception is mirrored in various cultural aspects, including the pop idol phenomenon, where maintaining an untarnished image is paramount. The exploration of Mima's transformation in the anime becomes a lens through which we can analyze the broader implications of how Japanese society links the physical and mental realms.

The inquiry into the interplay between the disintegration of the body and mind delves into the cultural construction of identity and the pressures individuals face in adhering to societal expectations. This exploration seeks to unravel the intricate mechanisms that contribute to the complex relationship between physical appearance and mental well-being in the Japanese cultural context. By understanding this connection, we can gain deeper insights into the societal influences that shape perceptions of self, identity, and the consequences of deviating from established norms.

The question that the next chapter aims to address to is: Due to which process the disintegration of the body is the disintegration of the mind in Japan context. ¹¹⁹

¹¹⁸ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> .

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

Chapter Two

Body as a Battlefield

« We believe in nothing other than our own bodies. The body is the truth. The pain of the body, desire of the body, anger of the body, ecstasy of the body, confusion of the body, sleep of the body—these are the only truths. »

Yoshikuni Igarashi (2000)¹²⁰

2.1 Introduction: Before Body Histories Unfold

The exploration of “history of the body” has a long history in anthropology. This history can be traced back to medical anthropology, a field with roots intertwining medicine and anthropology, has evolved over four decades into a rich synthesis of knowledge exploring the intricate relationship between health, medicine, and society.¹²¹ This interdisciplinary domain engages not only medical sociologists but also professionals from various realms such as physicians, nurses, psychologists, social workers, therapists, hospital administrators, health insurance companies, health economists, and more. The foundational insights provided by anthropology are integral to their research endeavors, patient care practices, and overall job performance.¹²²

Emerging in the post-World War Two era, medical anthropology has witnessed substantial growth, garnering a diverse community of practitioners and substantial research funding.¹²³ The field, thriving particularly in the United States and Europe, owes much of its development to the financial support provided by respective governments. The National Institutes of Health (NIH) in the U.S., notably, played a pivotal role, exemplified by the establishment of the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) fostering collaborative social and medical projects.¹²⁴

¹²⁰ Igarashi, Yoshikuni. *Bodies of Memory: Narratives of War in Postwar Japanese Culture, 1945 - 1970*. Princeton Paperbacks. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2000. 47.

¹²¹ McElroy, Ann, and Patricia K. Townsend. *Medical Anthropology in Ecological Perspective*. Sixth edition. Boulder, CO: Westview press, 2015.

¹²² Cockerham, William C., and Ferris Joseph Ritchey. *Dictionary of Medical Sociology*. Westport, Conn: Greenwood Press, 1997.

¹²³ *Ibid*, XII

¹²⁴ *Ibid*, XII

In Europe, a similar pattern emerged with government funding acting as the initial catalyst for those entering the field of medical anthropology. Affiliation with university anthropology departments was not a predominant factor, and ties to the broader discipline of anthropology were often described as weak. The prevalent employment trend leaned toward applied roles, typically in research within medical institutions.¹²⁵ Taking cue from Dorinda Outram:

«Modern histories of the body originated during the same era as the high point of European Fascism. The 1930s and 1940s saw an intense focus in many of the social issues which fed into historical enquiry on the social functions of the human body»¹²⁶

In anthropology, Margaret Mead and Gregory Bateson explored the connection between cultures and physical expression. Simultaneously, social psychologists undertook the mapping of aggressive and inferior gestures. The publication of Sigmund Freud's "Civilization and Its Discontents," among other works, prompted a shift in focus towards ideas that could integrate physical control and self-image with prevailing social structures¹²⁷.

Robert Straus' distinction between sociology in medicine and sociology of medicine delineates the field's dual focus. Sociology in medicine entails applied research addressing specific health problems, often in collaboration with healthcare professionals, with direct applicability to patient care. On the other hand, sociology of medicine delves into the broader sociological perspective, examining the organization, role relationships, norms, values, and beliefs shaping medical practice as a facet of human behavior.¹²⁸

Micro-level studies in medical settings, particularly those rooted in British medical sociology, emphasize everyday interactions within professional practices. This tradition, drawing from symbolic interactionism and ethnomethodology, provides detailed ethnographic accounts of relationships among patients, practitioners, and others in medical organizations, offering insights not typically found in American literature.¹²⁹

¹²⁵ Ibid, XII

¹²⁶ Outram, Dorinda. *The Body and the French Revolution: Sex, Class and Political Culture*. New Haven, Conn.: Yale Univ. Press, 1989.7.

¹²⁷ Ibid, 7.

¹²⁸ Straus, Robert. 'The Nature and Status of Medical Sociology'. *American Sociological Review* 22, no. 2 (April 1957): 200. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2088858>.

¹²⁹ Cockerham, William C., and Ferris Joseph Ritchey. *Dictionary of Medical Sociology*. Westport, Conn: Greenwood Press, 1997. XXII

As medical anthropology continues to gain prominence globally, with increasing importance in Russia, Eastern Europe, and Japan, the field's interdisciplinary nature positions it as a vital contributor to understanding health, medicine, and society as the world progresses into the twenty-first century.¹³⁰

The explorations into medical anthropology or more specifically, the body, its social representations, and its political significance were not confined to academic discourse alone. Instead, they accurately reflected an external reality. The political landscape during the Fascist era in Europe was notably characterized by its physicality. The intentional use of physical violence as a political tool, genocidal policies based on racial theories of physical characteristics, and the creation of a mass political audience through the constant projection of national leaders' appearance, voice, and gestures in large-scale rallies defined this era, setting it apart from any that had preceded it.¹³¹

Moving from the study of medical anthropology, we now shift our focus to exploring the body as a phenomenon closely tied to identity and serving as a social sign. To better understand this, it's essential to explore the interconnected history of the body and mind as a dualism.

2.2 Beyond Dichotomy: Rethinking the Interplay of Body and Mind

For centuries, Descartes' philosophy introduced a fundamental dichotomy between the body and mind. According to Cartesian dualism, the mind and body are separate entities with little interaction. The mind, associated with thought and consciousness, was considered as distinct from the physical body, perceived as a mechanical, material entity. This dualistic approach has had a profound impact on Western philosophy and science, has become deeply ingrained in Western culture.¹³²

Descartes' mind / body split, initially rooted in philosophical discourse, has become deeply ingrained in Western culture. This division, formalized within Cartesian dualism, has not only shaped philosophical arguments but has also permeated and normalized dominant cultural

¹³⁰ Ibid, XXVI

¹³¹ Outram, Dorinda. *The Body and the French Revolution: Sex, Class and Political Culture*. New Haven, Conn.: Yale Univ. Press, 1989.7.

¹³² Cregan, Kate. *The Sociology of the Body: Mapping the Abstraction of Embodiment*. 1 Oliver's Yard, 55 City Road, London EC1Y 1SP United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2006.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446214978>.

attitudes in the West for centuries, perpetuating a dichotomy that affects how we perceive and address health and well-being and impacting cultural attitudes worldwide.¹³³

According to Cartesian dualism, since there is little to no interaction between the mind and body, it implies that these two aspects can be studied separately by distinct disciplines. In this framework, the body falls under the purview of the natural sciences, including medicine, while the mind or *Geist* is the subject of the humanities or cultural sciences (*Geisteswissenschaften*).¹³⁴ This dualistic approach in Western science has led to various forms of reductionism, where mental events, spiritual life, and culture are often explained solely in terms of material causes.¹³⁵

Everyday language and health discourse often reinforce this division by dismissing certain conditions as being “only in the mind,” such as anorexia, repetitive strain injury, miner’s lung, or agoraphobia. Even the concept of “psychosomatic illness” tends to perpetuate the mind-body duality, suggesting that the illness is “only in the mind.” Consequently, the Cartesian division in medical sciences has allowed the treatment of bodily issues with minimal consideration for social or psychological factors, particularly in cases of psychosomatic conditions.¹³⁶

The devaluation of the body as an unworthy partner for the mind traces its roots from classical philosophy, with figures like Plato and Augustine, and persists through the lens of Cartesian dualism. These philosophical perspectives provide guidelines on gaining control over the body, ultimately aiming to learn to live without it. This normalization of the mind's superiority over the body has endured as a pervasive cultural norm.¹³⁷

¹³³ Cregan, Kate. *The Sociology of the Body: Mapping the Abstraction of Embodiment*. 1 Oliver’s Yard, 55 City Road, London EC1Y 1SP United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2006.

<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446214978>. 169.

¹³⁴ Turner, Bryan S. *Regulating Bodies: Essays in Medical Sociology*. 0 ed. USA and Canada: Routledge, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203214183>, 32.

¹³⁵ *Ibid*, 32.

¹³⁶ *Ibid*, 32.

¹³⁷ Cregan, Kate. *The Sociology of the Body: Mapping the Abstraction of Embodiment*. 1 Oliver’s Yard, 55 City Road, London EC1Y 1SP United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446214978.172>.

As far back as Plato, the body was seen as something that is inimical to knowledge. In the Republic, for example, we learn that we must control the body with the mind—keep it in check lest it overtake us.¹³⁸ Elizabeth Spelman writes:

«According to Plato, the body, with its deceptive senses, keeps us from real knowledge; it rivets us in a world of material things which is far removed from the world of reality; and it tempts us away from the virtuous life. »¹³⁹

The soul is the one that gains knowledge, not the body. The concept of self is also located within the soul, even if it's not explicitly identified as the soul, and the body is only connected to it incidentally or externally, as Kasulis describes it. According to Descartes, the body is an inactive object, brought to life and understood by the mind, but it doesn't possess cognitive abilities on its own. It's not a body that knows; instead, it's a body that is known, just one object among many in a mechanical world.¹⁴⁰

In the essay titled "*A Tale of Two Bodies: The Cartesian Corpse and the Lived Body*," the exploration of seventeenth-century medicine reveals a predominant focus on the deceased or inanimate body rather than the lived body. The medical paradigm of the time is grounded in the notion that understanding the functioning of the living body is best achieved by studying its non-living counterpart. According to Descartes, the body operates as an automaton, propelled by mechanical forces, with the living body perceived as essentially akin to a functioning mechanism. The conceptualization of the lived body, with its subjective and experiential dimensions, gained philosophical significance much later, particularly with the emergence of phenomenology, existentialism, and feminist philosophy.¹⁴¹

In this context, structuralism emerges as a significant contributor to the discourse on the body by challenging the foundational assumptions of rationalism rooted in Cartesian dualism. French postwar philosophy, characterized by a rejection of the mind-body split, found a voice in existentialism. Within this philosophical current, the notion emerged that individuals are fundamentally defined by their choices in knowledge and being. Structuralism furthered this

¹³⁸ McCarthy, Erin. *Ethics Embodied: Rethinking Selfhood through Continental, Japanese, and Feminist Philosophies*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2010. 36.

¹³⁹ Spelman, Elizabeth V. 'Woman as Body: Ancient and Contemporary Views'. *Feminist Studies* 8, no. 1 (1982): 109. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3177582>. 111.

¹⁴⁰ McCarthy, Erin. *Ethics Embodied: Rethinking Selfhood through Continental, Japanese, and Feminist Philosophies*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2010. 36.

¹⁴¹ *Ibid*, 37.

discourse by analyzing the body as a metaphor within language, a perspective notably emphasized by Michel Foucault. This multifaceted critique challenges the enduring legacy of Cartesian dualism in shaping our understanding of the mind / body relationship.¹⁴²

These more recent philosophical movements have underscored the importance of the lived body in ethical and epistemological inquiries, challenging the historical dominance of the Cartesian perspective in medical and philosophical discourse.¹⁴³ The exploration of the body within the realms of medicine, politics, and religion is based on the belief that the traditional separation of mind and body, and the general neglect of human embodiment, pose significant theoretical and practical challenges in the social sciences.¹⁴⁴ In the next section, the post-Foucauldian body histories is in focus.

2.3 Beyond the Flesh: The Political Body in Focus

This initial overview of the “history of body” needs clarification, considering two significant and interconnected intellectual advancements. Firstly, there is the widespread influence of Michel Foucault’s examination of power and knowledge. This influence has shaped various research topics and viewpoints in the exploration of mental health and illness¹⁴⁵, particularly since the English publication of “*Madness and Civilization*” in 1965¹⁴⁶. Secondly, a vital development closely tied to an appreciation of Foucault’s social philosophy is the gradual emergence of the sociology of the body as a foundational framework for medical sociology.¹⁴⁷ A significant shift towards understanding the body, influenced by Michel Foucault’s work, gained traction in Europe.¹⁴⁸

These two important shifts — the influence of Foucault on social science and the emergence of the sociology of the body — have redirected the focus from medical sociology to the broader

¹⁴² Outram, Dorinda. *The Body and the French Revolution: Sex, Class and Political Culture*. New Haven, Conn.: Yale Univ. Press, 1989. 19.

¹⁴³ McCarthy, Erin. *Ethics Embodied: Rethinking Selfhood through Continental, Japanese, and Feminist Philosophies*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2010. 37.

¹⁴⁴ Turner, Bryan S. *Regulating Bodies: Essays in Medical Sociology*. 0 ed. USA and Canada: Routledge, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203214183>, 32.

¹⁴⁵ Petersen, Alan R., and Robin Bunton, eds. *Foucault, Health and Medicine*. London ; New York: Routledge, 1997.

¹⁴⁶ Foucault, Michel. *Madness and Civilization: A History of Insanity in the Age of Reason*. New York: Vintage Books, 1988.

¹⁴⁷ Petersen, Alan R., and Robin Bunton, eds. *Foucault, Health and Medicine*. London ; New York: Routledge, 1997.

¹⁴⁸ Cockerham, William C., and Ferris Joseph Ritchey. *Dictionary of Medical Sociology*. Westport, Conn: Greenwood Press, 1997.

realm of the sociology of health and illness. This shift involves a critical exploration of disease categories as tools for moral control over individuals and populations. A central idea driving this change is the recognition that the body is shaped by historical factors.¹⁴⁹

The post-Foucauldian era has witnessed a significant focus on the “histories of the body,” emphasizing the intricate relationship between the physical body and politics. The body, full of specific political meanings, becomes a central point in discussions surrounding carnality and sexuality. This emphasis on the body serves as an overtly counterhegemonic stance, challenging the dominance of the national body. Importantly, these characterizations extend beyond the confines of mere physicality, finding relevance in broader contexts.¹⁵⁰

The refusal to subordinate individual desires to national agendas emerges as a revolutionary act and a form of protest. Examining earlier historical periods, such as eighteenth-century France, reveals the symbolic significance of the king’s body representing the state. Treason during this time was construed as a physical offense against the monarch’s body, resulting in correspondingly physical and agonizing punishments, as vividly described in Foucault’s “*Discipline and Punish*.”¹⁵¹

The slogan of “the body is historical” can be also traced back to Bryan Turner’s (2008), who initiated this sociological debate, in his book called “*The Body and Society*”, exploring how medical knowledge is used to socially control the human body.¹⁵² To works like “*Sociological Theory and Medical Sociology*”¹⁵³ edited by Graham Scrambler’s (2022), and Uta Gerhardt’s (1989) “*Ideas about Illness*” contribute to the theoretical richness of the field.¹⁵⁴ At the same time, even though they have different views, feminist historians have created a special history about the female body.¹⁵⁵

The body has served as a focal point for military discipline and has been subjected to scrutiny in both the medical and governmental contexts. Broadly speaking, health operates as a form of

¹⁴⁹ Petersen, Alan R., and Robin Bunton, eds. Foucault, Health and Medicine. London ; New York: Routledge, 1997.

¹⁵⁰ Slaymaker, Douglas. The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>.

¹⁵¹ Ibid, 11.

¹⁵² Turner, Bryan S. The Body & Society: Explorations in Social Theory, 3rd ed. Nottingham Trent University. London: Sage Publications, 2008.

¹⁵³ Scrambler, Graham. Sociological Theory and Medical Sociology. United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis, 2022.

¹⁵⁴ Gerhardt, Uta. Ideas about Illness. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 1989. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-20016-0>.

¹⁵⁵ Outram, Dorinda. The Body and the French Revolution: Sex, Class and Political Culture. New Haven, Conn.: Yale Univ. Press, 1989

control, particularly concerning the quality of the labor force.¹⁵⁶ The body's significance is evident in works such as "*Discipline and Punish*"¹⁵⁷ and "*The History of Sexuality*"¹⁵⁸ by Foucault, where he explores the body's connection to medicine and its role in shaping the self within a Christian framework.

Foucault was concerned with how bodies are produced, regulated, and represented under the watchful eye of disciplinary surveillance.¹⁵⁹ He articulated thoughts regarding the body, highlighting that:

«Historians long ago began to write the history of the body. They have studied the body in the field of historical demography or pathology; they have considered it as the seat of needs and appetites, as the focus of physiological processes and metabolisms, as a target for the attacks of germs and viruses; they have shown to what extent historical processes were involved in what might seem to be the purely biological bases of existence... But the body is also directly involved in a political field; power relations have an immediate hold on it; they invest it, mark it, train it, torture it, force it to carry out tasks, to perform ceremonies, to emit signs. This political investment of the body is bound up, in accordance with complex reciprocal relations, with its economic use; it is largely as a force of production that the body is invested with relations of power and domination; but, on the other hand, its constitution as labor power is possible only if it is caught up in a system of subjection. The body becomes a useful force only if it is both a productive body and a subjected body. »¹⁶⁰

In 1980, Bourdieu highlighted the importance of the body in discussions about power dynamics. He explained how socio-political power primarily affects the body, leading people to perceive the dominance of power as a natural aspect. Bourdieu argued that this belief, termed "practical belief," is not just a mental state but a condition of the body itself. He introduced the concept of "bodily hexis," describing it as the embodiment of political mythology—a lasting disposition that influences how individuals stand, speak, and, consequently, feel and think. Bourdieu used

¹⁵⁶ Petersen, Alan R., and Robin Bunton, eds. Foucault, Health and Medicine. London ; New York: Routledge, 1997.

¹⁵⁷ Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*. Vintage Books, 1995.

¹⁵⁸ Foucault, Michel. *The History of Sexuality, Volume 1: An Introduction*. New York; Vintage Books, 1990.

¹⁵⁹ Turner, Bryan S. *The Body & Society: Explorations in Social Theory*, 3rd ed. Nottingham Trent University. London: Sage Publications, 2008.

¹⁶⁰ Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*. Vintage Books, 1995, 25.

the terms “mythology” and “belief” interchangeably to refer to discourses essential for certain social groups to establish dominance over others.¹⁶¹

In subsequent years, the concept of the body has gained prominence in medical anthropology, offering a compelling perspective on the socially constructed nature of disease categories. It sheds light on how medicine regulates individuals by controlling their bodies and contributes to fresh insights into the intersections of sexuality and medicine. Despite being overlooked as a theoretical subject for decades, the question of the human body has recently become a critical issue in the social sciences. Several significant publications in this area have given rise to a new sub-field of anthropology.¹⁶²

In the initial sections of this chapter, I have provided an introduction to emerge of the concept body in medical anthropology. The chapter will continue with defining the term “history of the body” and a comprehensive exploration of how this concept is established in Japan. A critical examination is undertaken to explain the multifaceted nature of the history of the body in Japan, particularly in relation to four constructive layers—Japan’s mythology, language, history and culture. These layers serve as essential elements in shaping and defining the concept of the body within the broader societal context. Finally, the chapter ends with a delve into the interconnection between the “history of the body” and the possibilities of psychological disorders, adding a psychological aspect to our understanding of this concept.

2.4 What is “History of the Body” and why is it Important?

The seemingly simple questions of “What is the body?” and “What is embodiment?” have consistently and enduringly taken center stage in both academic and public discourse for significant reasons.¹⁶³ Nevertheless, attempting to provide precise definition for these concepts proves to be a challenging endeavor.

Friedrich Nietzsche, a German philosopher known for his critiques of traditional European morality and religion, had a complex and nuanced view on various topics, including the act of defining. In his works, Nietzsche often challenged the idea of fixed, universal definitions,

¹⁶¹ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women’s Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> .

¹⁶² Petersen, Alan R., and Robin Bunton, eds. *Foucault, Health and Medicine*. London ; New York: Routledge, 1997.

¹⁶³ Turner, Bryan S. *Regulating Bodies: Essays in Medical Sociology*. 0 ed. USA and Canada: Routledge, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203214183>.

especially when it came to concepts like morality and truth. He argued that definitions are not objective and absolute but are shaped by the perspectives and interests of those who create them. Nietzsche was critical of the notion that there are inherent meanings to concepts that can be universally agreed upon.¹⁶⁴ He says: «all concepts in which an entire process is semiotically concentrated elude definition; only that which has no history is definable.»¹⁶⁵

One key concept in Nietzsche's philosophy is "perspectivism," which suggests that all knowledge is subjective and influenced by one's perspective or point of view. This perspective extends to the act of defining, as he believed that individuals and cultures define concepts based on their unique experiences, values, and needs. Nietzsche's work encourages a critical examination of the processes involved in defining concepts and an acknowledgment of the influence of personal, cultural, and historical perspectives on these definitions. In alignment with Nietzsche's perspective on the subjective and multifaceted nature of definitions, I refrain from providing a fixed definition but instead aim to elucidate the various possible interpretations and implications associated with the concept.

The "history of the body" refers to the conceptualization of the human body as an entity shaped not only by biological factors but also by historical, social, and cultural forces. This interdisciplinary approach recognizes that the physical attributes, health conditions, and even genetic expressions of individuals are influenced by the historical contexts in which they live. The term encompasses research areas such as genetic anthropology, epigenetics, bioarcheology, medical anthropology, and the study of historical trauma. Understanding the "history of the body" involves exploring how historical events, cultural practices, and social structures leave lasting imprints on the human body across time, contributing to a holistic comprehension of human health and well-being.¹⁶⁶

The concept of the "history of the body" is important because it broadens our understanding of the human body beyond purely biological considerations. It recognizes that the body is not a static entity but is dynamically influenced by historical, cultural, and social contexts. This interdisciplinary perspective allows researchers to explore the complex interplay between

¹⁶⁴ Selden, Raman, Peter Widdowson, and Peter Brooker. *A Reader's Guide to Contemporary Literary Theory*. 5th ed. Harlow, England ; New York: Pearson Longman, 2005.

¹⁶⁵ Nietzsche, Friedrich. *On the Genealogy of Morality*. Edited by Keith Ansell-Pearson, translated by Carol Diethe, Cambridge University Press, 1994, 2007.

¹⁶⁶ Turner, Bryan Stanley. *Routledge Handbook of Body Studies*. Routledge International Handbooks. Abingdon, Oxon New York: Routledge, 2012.

genetics, environment, and historical experiences in shaping health outcomes. By studying the “history of the body”, scholars can uncover how historical events, societal structures, and cultural practices contribute to patterns of health and disease.

This approach is particularly relevant in addressing health disparities, understanding the impact of historical traumas on health outcomes, and developing more inclusive and culturally sensitive healthcare practices. Moreover, the “history of the body” provides insights into the resilience and adaptation of populations over time, offering a richer understanding of human evolution and the intricate connections between biology and culture. Overall, this concept fosters a more comprehensive and nuanced approach to human health, emphasizing the interconnectedness of biological, historical, and cultural factors.

The concept of the “body” as a representation, especially reflecting fundamental societal aspects, has a longstanding history. Anthropologists, particularly influenced by Mary Douglas, have examined the body as a narrative of social processes and structures. In contemporary social theory, driven by the rise of “deconstructionism” in the works by Paul de Man and Jacques Derrida, there’s a trend to view the body as a text or the consequence of a discourse. The body is seen as socially constructed through various discourses—medical, moral, artistic, commercial. These notions problematize the traditional view of “the body” as a neutral, scientifically observable living organism. Social constructionism questions the idea that the body is solely shaped by scientific discourses, challenging claims of expert knowledge.¹⁶⁷

The central concern in “*Regulating Bodies*” revolves around comprehending the historical development of body discourse, acknowledging how our perspectives are socially constructed, and balancing this awareness with an understanding of the lived body’s phenomenological nature. What I am trying to do in this section is to navigate the tension between recognizing the impact of social constructions on our understanding of the body and maintaining an appreciation for the subjective, personal experience of the lived body.¹⁶⁸

The body, conceived as a potentiality, suggests that it undergoes a developmental process shaped by cultural influences and social interactions. This perspective challenges the idea of a strict separation between acquired and innate behaviors, as well as between culture and nature. Taking a cue from Oliver Sacks (1981), who notes that walking, fundamentally a spinal reflex,

¹⁶⁷ Turner, Bryan S. *Regulating Bodies: Essays in Medical Sociology*. 0 ed. USA and Canada: Routledge, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203214183>.

¹⁶⁸ *Ibid*, 6.

evolves through cultural elaboration to the point where an individual becomes recognizable by their distinctive gait, we see the body as a dynamic interplay of biological and sociocultural factors.¹⁶⁹

«Walking, at its most elementary, is a spinal reflex, but it is elaborated at higher and higher levels until, finally, we can recognize a man by the way he walks, by his walk.»¹⁷⁰

In the ongoing exploration within this chapter, the recurring challenge is to conceptually grapple with the body in various dimensions: as an organism, a potentiality, a system of representation, and a lived experience. The body is a complex entity that is both socially constructed and organically grounded. While the idea of the human body as a product of social construction is not novel to sociology, the term “fabric” takes on a profound significance. Delving into historical perspectives, medieval writers often employed architectural metaphors to elucidate the body's structure. In Old French, the term “panniculs,” used to describe the membrane, originates from “pan,” denoting a piece of cloth. This etymology paints a vivid picture of the membrane as akin to the fabric of a body. Thus, the multifaceted nature of the body unfolds, emphasizing its intertwined cultural, social, and biological dimensions.¹⁷¹

In this section, I am going to adopt a similar perspective on constructionism. I find no reason to question the idea that the body is socially constructed. However, it's important to acknowledge that certain conditions, may be more socially constructed than others. Additionally, topics with political implications are more likely to be recognized as socially constructed by humanitarians compared to conditions with less political charge. Importantly, it is a mistake to assume that different approaches to the body are referring to the same thing.¹⁷²

The foundation of this thesis lies in the belief that the concept of the “history of the body” holds practical significance for medical anthropology, serving as a valuable perspective in applied contexts. This viewpoint provides a nuanced and empathetic understanding of concerns such as pain, disability, and death.

¹⁶⁹ Ibid, 16.

¹⁷⁰ Sacks, Oliver: *Migraine: Evolution of a Common Disorder*. London and Sydney: Pan Books, 1981. 224.

¹⁷¹ Turner, Bryan S. *Regulating Bodies: Essays in Medical Sociology*. 0 ed. USA and Canada: Routledge, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203214183>, 17.

¹⁷² Ibid, 26.

Now, expanding our exploration to include Japan, we aim to investigate the concept of the body at the confluence of Japanese Myth, language, culture, and history. Recognizing the importance of the body, we embark on a study that extends beyond cultural boundaries, acknowledging the diverse ways in which the “history of body” shapes perceptions and experiences. This examination seeks to delve into the intricate interplay between Japanese mythology, the human body, and the cultural narratives that contribute to our understanding of self-identity and societal significance.

2.5 “History of the Body” in Japan

In traditional Japanese culture, there is a distinctive perspective on bodily expressions. This culture stands out as one of the few ancient societies that assigns significance to the body, considering it as both the cornerstone and reflection of the mind and soul.¹⁷³ Within this cultural tradition, the body is regarded as essential for acquiring knowledge, and Japanese philosophy places a strong emphasis on lived experience, considering the body to hold philosophical significance. Watsuji, for instance, underscores this perspective by critiquing the Western philosophical notion of separating the mind and body.¹⁷⁴ He notes that:

«What is not in accord with the concrete facts of experience is the view that something psychological, accompanied by no bodily events, and a process of the physical body entirely unrelated to bodily experiences subsist in the form of an opposition between body and mind existing independent of each other. »¹⁷⁵

Furthermore, the traditional Japanese culture has formalized and reinforced the perspective on the body through specific theories and rituals. Exploring Japanese theories, ancient myths, and patterns within this cultural context provides insights into comprehending this intricate relationship.¹⁷⁶

¹⁷³ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 16.

¹⁷⁴ McCarthy, Erin. *Ethics Embodied: Rethinking Selfhood through Continental, Japanese, and Feminist Philosophies*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2010. 37.

¹⁷⁵ *Ibid*, 37.

¹⁷⁶ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 16.

2.6 The Body at the Confluence of Japanese Myth

According to the Kojiki, the initial phase of the creation and formation of the land witnessed the emergence of five solitary deities, lacking spouses, resulting in a formless land likened to a jellyfish. Subsequently, six additional generations of gods followed, some of whom had spouses. The concluding pair of the seventh generation, Izanagi-no-mikoto and his spouse Izanami-no-mikoto, received the Heavenly Jeweled Spear from all the kami and were instructed to solidify the land. They accomplished this task by standing on the Heavenly Floating Bridge and stirring the liquid with the spear, causing droplets to form solid islands.¹⁷⁷ Therefore, they are one of the most important symbols of the origin of the land in Japanese mythology because they are the creators of the land.

The first time the body is discussed occurs when Izanagi notices the difference between his body and Izanami. Izanagi explained to Izanami:

«My body, formed though it be formed, has one place which is formed to excess. Therefore, I would like to take that place in my body which is formed to excess and insert it into that place in your body which is formed insufficiently and give birth to the land.»¹⁷⁸

Izanagi proposed a unique form of procreation to Izanami. They decided to walk around the pillar, meet again, and engage in conjugal intercourse. Izanami agreed, and the two deities decided to walk around the pillar. Izanagi walked from the left, and Izanami from the right, with the plan to meet again and engage in conjugal intercourse. As they circled around, upon meeting, Izanami exclaimed, «How wonderful! Such a handsome lad! » Izanagi, though delighted to see her, scolded her, stating it was inappropriate for the woman to speak first. Yet, they began the process of procreation, however, the outcome of this union was a «leech-child lacking arms or legs.»¹⁷⁹

Troubled by the situation, they sought advice from the senior deities, who explained that the issue arose because Izanami had spoken out of turn after circling the pillar. To rectify this, they repeated the process, ensuring the correct order of greetings. Consequently, Izanami

¹⁷⁷ Ashkenazi, Michael. Handbook of Japanese Mythology. Handbooks of World Mythology. Santa Barbara, Calif.: ABC-CLIO, 2003. 76.

¹⁷⁸ Ibid, 76.

¹⁷⁹ Ibid, 76.

successfully gave birth to the eight islands of Japan, followed by the emergence of numerous deities.¹⁸⁰

Following the birth of the fire deity, who unfortunately caused harm during delivery by burning Izanami's genitals, she passed away. In her final moments, she gave birth to additional deities formed from her organs and discharges. In total, she brought forth fourteen islands and thirty-five deities. Enraged by the unfortunate incident, Izanagi took the life of the newborn fire deity. Remarkably, even in death, the fire-deity's organs and the blood collected on Izanagi's sword gave rise to more deities.¹⁸¹

The second specific mention of the body goes back to the moment when Izanami dies and descends to the underworld. Following Izanami death, Izanagi desired to visit his wife in the land of *yomi*, the underworld. Upon meeting her in the grand hall of the underworld, she expressed willingness to return to the land of the living, but with the condition that she obtains permission from the *kami*, deity of the underworld. Izanagi's patience is the condition, he is asked not to look at Izanami until the *kami* has allowed her to return to Izanagi.¹⁸² It continues:

«Izanagi broke his word to wait patiently, spied on her, and discovered her putrefied body being eaten by maggots. He fled, and she, accompanied by the maggots who had turned into snake-thunder deities and her servants, pursued. He blocked the way after him with a rock, but Izanami cursed Izanagi and his people that one thousand people would die every day. Izanagi averted the curse by blessing humanity with 1,500 births every day.»¹⁸³

In my view, this myth bears a distinct resemblance to the ancient Greek myth of Orpheus and Eurydice. However, it's essential to note the considerable differences in their cultural contexts. To underscore the importance of Japanese mythology in exploring the concept of the "body," I will commence by citing the passage from the tenth book of Ovid's "Metamorphoses," on Orpheus and Eurydice, a literary work by the Roman poet:

«From the happy union of Iphis and Ianthe on Crete, Hymenaeus flies to Thrace and the doomed marriage of Orpheus and Eurydice. Not long after the wedding

¹⁸⁰ Ibid, 76.

¹⁸¹ Ibid, 76.

¹⁸² Ibid, 76.

¹⁸³ Ibid, 76.

Eurydice dies of a snakebite. Orpheus descends to the Underworld and pleads for her restoration in a song so moving that Pluto grants his wish, on condition, however, that the bard precede his wife back to the upper air and not look back at her until he has left the realm of the dead. Orpheus cannot restrain himself and looks back too soon, thereby losing Eurydice a second and final time. Inconsolable, he then mourns for years and ends by refusing to marry again. »¹⁸⁴

Both Orpheus and Izanagi share a common trait of impatience, neglecting the crucial law of the underworld, which advocates patience when undertaking visits to the realm of the deceased. This virtue of patience carries a symbolic weight in mythological discourse, suggesting that the living must exercise patience, waiting until their own death to reunite and interact with the dead. Orpheus may have refrained from looking back, but until his death, Eurydice would have continued to walk behind him on the path leading back to the world of the living. Similarly, it's possible that Izanagi did not break the law, but then until his demise, he could have remained in anticipation of the underworld *kami's* permission.

The thematic parallel in both myths lies in the shared human experience of yearning for reunions with departed loved ones, underlining the universal significance of patience in these narratives. However, a substantial cultural contrast surfaces in the narratives: the Japanese story emphasizes the subjectivity of the body, assigning it a pivotal role, while the Greek narrative downplays its importance. In the myth of Orpheus, the body takes a secondary role, with the central focus revolving around Orpheus' acts of rebellion and expressions of love. In contrast, in the Japanese narration, the body itself becomes the focal point, positioned at the core of the narrative. This distinction highlights not only the cultural diversity in mythological storytelling but also sheds light on the different cultural values attached to the significance of the body in these ancient narratives.

In the Japanese narrative, the divine body starts to decay, creating a disturbing image. Although the soul remains, the physical form becomes unstable and undesirable. Even Izanagi, who was initially eager, leaves and goes back to the world of the living when he sees Izanami's deteriorating body full of worms. The representation of a decaying body carries an inherent

¹⁸⁴ Anderson, William Scovil, ed. *Ovid's Metamorphoses, Books 6-10*. American Philological Association. Series of Classical Texts. United States: University of Oklahoma Press, 1972. 475.

fear, prompting a preference to remain in the underground realm. This narration contains a fear of the corpse and the return of the dead.

The narrative may point to an understanding of the inevitable decay and degradation inherent in the nature of a body. Initially praised in its youthful, vibrant, and beautiful state, the body takes on an alarming and horrifying aspect in old age and eventual decay. This interpretation places the body at the forefront of Japanese myth, emphasizing its central role in expressing these cultural anxieties about mortality and the transformative nature of the physical form over time.

This centrality of body gains further significance in this myth considering Bourdieu's discussion that «practical sense is not a state of mind but rather a state of the body» evolving into a “permanent disposition.” This profound insight delves into the lasting impact of embodied experiences on individuals and their intricate connection to the development of practical understanding. In Bourdieu's framework, practical sense is deeply ingrained in the body as a set of durable dispositions and habits, shaping how individuals navigate their social worlds.¹⁸⁵

The transformation of practical sense into a permanent disposition aligns seamlessly with Bourdieu's concept of bodily hexis—This means a durable way your body is organized and its deployment in the world.¹⁸⁶ Bourdieu highlights:

«Bodily hexis is political mythology realized, embodied, turned into a permanent disposition. A durable way of standing, speaking, walking, and thereby of feeling and thinking.»¹⁸⁷

The body, functioning as an archive of deeply rooted dispositions, becomes a living testament to the historical context that has shaped it. This dynamic relationship extends beyond mere reflection, as the body actively perpetuates historical legacies through its practices and perceptions.¹⁸⁸

¹⁸⁵ Bourdieu, Pierre, John B. Thompson, and Gino Raymond. *Language and Symbolic Power*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2009. 13.

¹⁸⁶ *Ibid*, 13.

¹⁸⁷ Bourdieu, Pierre. *The Logic of Practice*. Translated by Richard Nice. 69-70

¹⁸⁸ Bourdieu, Pierre, John B. Thompson, and Gino Raymond. *Language and Symbolic Power*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2009. 13.

The ongoing process of production and reproduction, where history becomes an inherent part of the body and incorporation is continually actualized, unfolds seamlessly without explicit articulation in language. This underscores the deeply embedded nature of practical sense and its enduring impact on individuals, illustrating how the body, as a site of incorporated history, becomes a conduit for the perpetuation of cultural and historical influences in a way that surpasses explicit institutional practices or language articulation.¹⁸⁹

In the context of Japanese mythology, where the body is a central theme and plays a significant role in cultural narratives, there is an implicit connection to the idea of practical sense as a state of the body. The mythological stories may reflect and perpetuate certain attitudes and dispositions toward the body, influencing how individuals in that cultural context perceive, respond to, and navigate the world around them.

The centrality of the body in Japanese mythology, with its themes of decay, transformation, and the fear of the corpse, can be seen as a cultural expression that shapes the practical sense of individuals within that society. The mythological narratives become a repository of ingrained dispositions, influencing how individuals stand, speak, walk, feel, and think—an embodiment of the cultural and historical context. Therefore, the body's centrality in Japanese mythology aligns with the idea that practical sense is not just a state of mind but rather a state of the body—a lasting and ingrained way of being in the world.

In conclusion, the exploration of the body in mythology reveals a profound connection between cultural narratives and embodied dispositions. The myths examined illustrate how the body is not merely a physical entity but a symbolic and cultural construct, embodying fears, transformations, and the enduring impact of historical contexts. Meantime, the body's significance links to how we engage with language. As Pierre Bourdieu states:

«The relation to the body is a fundamental dimension of the habitus that is inseparable from a relation to language and time.»¹⁹⁰

Habitus is a set of dispositions that guide people to behave and react in specific ways. These dispositions lead to regular patterns in how individuals act, see things, and feel about them. Importantly, these patterns are not consciously planned or controlled by specific rules. They

¹⁸⁹ Ibid, 13.

¹⁹⁰ Bourdieu, Pierre. *The Logic of Practice*. Translated by Richard Nice. 1980. 72.

develop naturally as a part of how individuals are inclined to approach life based on their ingrained habits.¹⁹¹

This statement emphasizes that our connection to the body is a crucial aspect of habitus and can't be simplified to a mere “body image” or “body concept.” These terms refer to subjective perceptions of one’s body, often influenced by external representations and feedback from others. In essence, the statement highlights the complexity of our embodied experiences, rejecting the reduction to simplistic views of our bodies.¹⁹²

As we transition to the topic of the body in language, it becomes evident that the body’s significance extends beyond the mythical realm and delves into a complex interplay of dispositions, practices, perceptions, and attitudes that are tightly linked to how we engage with language.

2.7 The Body at the Confluence of Japanese Language

“The limits of my language mean the limits of my world.”

Ludwig Wittgenstein

In the specific context of the body, this section sheds light on the intricate relationship between language and bodily experiences. It emphasizes that the meaning of terms like “body” is not inherent but actively constructed through linguistic articulations, revealing the polysemic nature of language. This section challenges the idea that language merely reflects reality; instead, it asserts that discourse actively shapes and constructs our reality, influencing our understanding of physical experiences.

Before the World War Two, the portrayal of bodies in Japan had an air of mystical and was generally esteemed. These valued bodies differed significantly from the notion of physical form. Traditional Japanese culture, to underscore this contrast, enriched its vocabulary for describing the body, introducing multiple signifiers (forms) for the body contents (signifié) that endure today, symbolizing distinctions between bodies considered praiseworthy and those associated

¹⁹¹ Bourdieu, Pierre, John B. Thompson, and Gino Raymond. *Language and Symbolic Power*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2009. 12.

¹⁹² Bourdieu, Pierre. *The Logic of Practice*. Translated by Richard Nice. 72.

with material and physical attributes. This indicates the exploration of body representations takes center stage.¹⁹³

One such term that took a specific connotation in the postwar period is “*Nikutai*” (肉体). *Nikutai* signifies explicitly carnal body, emphasizing the physical aspects as the foundation of individual identity, encompassing health, desires, afflictions, and the unavoidable embrace of mortality. *Nikutai* is multifaceted in its semantic dimensions: firstly, in the exploration of the physical body within a range of works; secondly, in the personal and physical context, contrasting with the non-physical or and aligning somewhat with the concept of "spiritual". Illustrating the body not solely as the container for physical existence but also as the realm for understanding sexual desires; and lastly, on a social and external level, it contrasts with *Kokutai* (国体), the body politic.¹⁹⁴

Nikutai is rooted in the initial definitions of the term “*niku*” (肉), signifying meat, muscle, or flesh, coupled with “*tai*” (体), representing the body, signifies the corporeal nature of the body and operates along the second axis of body meanings with embodying bodily desires. The authoritative Japanese dictionary, *nihon kokugo daijiten*, defines *nikutai* as “the body comprised of meat/muscle (肉),” considering “*karada*” (体) as one synonym. It qualifies *nikutai* specifically as “the body [*karada*] of sexual desire.” *Nikutai* is also given a different aspect, consistently used when discussing the (female) body in states of illness, weakness, pregnancy, and childbirth, a portrayal far from the sensual body imagined by the flesh writers.¹⁹⁵

The postwar usage of the term *nikutai* reflects a nuanced evolution, drawing on a historical context to distinguish it from other terms for the body, such as *karada* or *shintai* (身体). Iwaya Daishi acknowledges that during this period, *nikutai* carried a loaded connotation, emphasizing that “before the war we would not have used *nikutai* but *shintai* [when referring to the body].”¹⁹⁶

¹⁹³ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 21.

¹⁹⁴ Slaymaker, Douglas. The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>. 8.

¹⁹⁵ Ibid, 8.

¹⁹⁶ Quoted in Okuno Takeo, “Tamura Taijirō,” in Okuno Takeo sakka ron shū, 5 vols, Tokyo: Tairyūsha, 1977, 3: 250.

This body was banished from all traditional and official representations of Japanese culture before the war: from traditional shows of national costumes, rituals, paintings and even dolls.¹⁹⁷ Although this assertion might appear somewhat schematic it suggests that the reluctance of the Japanese to engage with, represent, or embody their identity through *nikutai* reflects a societal aversion to the carnal and sexual aspects of the body.¹⁹⁸

Shintai also serves as a synonymous term for the “body,” frequently included in dictionary definitions alongside *nikutai*. In philosophical discussions, particularly in phenomenology, *shintai* is the preferred term. This distinction becomes evident in the nuanced meanings of baseness and carnality associated with *nikutai* compared to the more clinical usage of *shintai* in philosophical writings. While *shintai* conveys a sense of a solid object akin to physical science, *nikutai* tends to evoke subjective and emotion-laden responses in living entities. *shintai*, subjectively speaking, often carries a more refined register of discourse than *nikutai*.¹⁹⁹

The philosophical description of *shintai* extends to its overlap with the native Japanese term *karada*, synonymous with the English concept of “body.” *Shintai*, in its philosophical context, refers to the phenomenological body – the body as a material object, a thing within a society where individuals are mutually aware of and therefore, aware of the self. This concept of the individual “self” mixes the Japanese *seishin* (or spirit, 精神), often synonymous with *seikaku* (or personality, 性格), including the notions of soul or spirit. *Shintai*, then, is a composite of *nikutai* and *seishin* or spirit, combining material and non-material aspects. It represents the physical body that incorporates both spirituality and essentiality, blending the physical and the personality.²⁰⁰

The contrast between *seishin* (or spiri) and *nikutai* (or carnal bod) has deep historical roots demonstrated in a nineteenth century. For instance, the categorization of love by Tsubouchi Shōyō's, a Japanese author, during the Meiji era assigned the lowest rank to the pleasure of the flesh *nikutai* and physical enjoyments. Tsubouchi argued that prioritizing external physical attraction while neglecting internal attributes mirrored the base and uncivilized sexual attraction observed in animals.

¹⁹⁷ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 22.

¹⁹⁸ Slaymaker, Douglas. The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>. 8.

¹⁹⁹ Ibid, 9.

²⁰⁰ Ibid, 9.

According to his scheme, societal progress involved a transition from physical and carnal love to true love and affection, aligning with a civilized and modern society that values the spiritual and cerebral over the physical. This perspective, avoiding exclusivity in platonic aspects, emphasizes a balance between the physical and the spiritual, the internal and the external – a pursuit for equilibrium persisting beyond the war.²⁰¹

In a broader context, this dichotomy between *seishin* (or spirit) and *nikutai* (or carnal bod) assumes significance in its resistance to wartime ideology, where *seishin* (or spirit), frequently used in propagandist clichés such as “spirit of the Imperial nation” or “the spirit of the military nation”, symbolizes an undifferentiated mass. The post war writers, by emphasizing the body’s central role in individual and national identity, mirror postwar endeavors to come to terms with the war years, involving both the repression of the body through disavowal and its expression through carnality.²⁰²

In essence, the pre-war traditional macro-cultural discourse in Japan did not seek to embody Japanese identity in *nikutai*. Rather, it centered on the engagement with *seikaku* (or personality), *seishin* (or spirit) and *kokutai* (national body, 国体). The first two terms, *seikaku* (or personality) and *seishin* (or spirit), were employed in a physical sense, describing a body devoid of blood, flesh, and bones – a body untouched by natural desires and the unrestrained human experience. Such a body that, for instance, would not hunger in the conventional sense, or its hunger would hold an aesthetic significance. It is a body unfamiliar with sexual desire, or if present, this desire held a poetic quality. These were bodies shrouded in mystical and sanctity.²⁰³

On the other hand, *kokutai* (国体) is a Japanese term that can be translated as “national body” or “national polity.” It was a concept with deep historical and cultural significance in Japan, particularly during the prewar and wartime periods. *Kokutai* stands in opposition to *nikutai*, refers to the unity of the Japanese state, combining political, social, and spiritual elements into a singular entity. The emperor played a central role in this concept, symbolizing the unity and continuity of the nation.²⁰⁴

²⁰¹ Ibid, 10.

²⁰² Ibid, 9-10.

²⁰³ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 22.

²⁰⁴ Slaymaker, Douglas. The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>. 11.

During the prewar and wartime eras, *kokutai* was often invoked to promote nationalist and imperialistic ideologies. It emphasized the unique and divine nature of the Japanese state, presenting it as a distinct and superior entity. The concept was used to justify authoritarian rule and imperial expansion.²⁰⁵ «The ideas of national structure and the infallibility of the emperor as the living god»²⁰⁶ as Shunsuke Tsurumi states. Certainly, the regulation of Japanese bodies was among the focal points of official propaganda. Yoshikuni Igarashi (2000) highlights:

«The distance between mind and body was collapsed in wartime efforts to create a nationalistic body. What was regarded as “unhealthy” – unproductive and unproductive – was branded as threatening national interests.»²⁰⁷

The heightened focus on the body during and after the war, as symbolized by the nationalistic discourse, contributed to a collapse of the distance between individual and national bodies. The emphasis on the national body, *kokutai*, had significant political implications, serving as a linguistic weapon and reinforcing notions of the unique Japanese government²⁰⁸ as well as imposing strict regulations on bodies, aiming to create obedient and patriotic bodies by intertwining nationalist ideology with bodily functions²⁰⁹. Shunsuke Tsurumi in this regard says:

«The concept of *kokutai*, or “national structure” derived from the fundamental insularity and isolation of the Japanese. The concept served as a powerful linguistic weapon both for attack and defence in the political arena of the period 1931-1945. Although the expression ‘national structure’ disappeared with Japan's defeat in 1945 and a new style of political argument was initiated by the United States occupation, the concept, if not the term, is still alive in a submerged form in Japanese politics... After the Meiji Restoration, “national structure” was used to signify the uniqueness of the existing government of Japan.»²¹⁰

²⁰⁵ Ibid, 11.

²⁰⁶ Tsurumi, Shunsuke, and Shunsuke Tsurumi. *An Intellectual History of Wartime Japan: 1931-1945*. Reprint. Japanese Studies. London: Routledge & Kegan, 1986. 41.

²⁰⁷ Igarashi, Yoshikuni. *Bodies of Memory: Narratives of War in Postwar Japanese Culture, 1945 - 1970*. Princeton Paperbacks. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2000. 49.

²⁰⁸ Tsurumi, Shunsuke, and Shunsuke Tsurumi. *An Intellectual History of Wartime Japan: 1931-1945*. Reprint. Japanese Studies. London: Routledge & Kegan, 1986.

²⁰⁹ Igarashi, Yoshikuni. *Bodies of Memory: Narratives of War in Postwar Japanese Culture, 1945 - 1970*. Princeton Paperbacks. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2000. 13.

²¹⁰ Tsurumi, Shunsuke, and Shunsuke Tsurumi. *An Intellectual History of Wartime Japan: 1931-1945*. Reprint. Japanese Studies. London: Routledge & Kegan, 1986, 33.

The *kokutai*, while synonymous with the government, also served as an all-encompassing system of imagery that, although submerged, continued to influence postwar political society with lingering mystical and spiritual connotations. This normalizing force, identified as the *kokutai*, was instituted in opposition to the individual body and vehemently punished any form of dissent.²¹¹

After Japan's defeat in World War Two and the subsequent occupation by allied forces, the concept of *kokutai* albeit in a submerged form, continuing to influence political discourse with mystical and spiritual overtones. The postwar period witnessed a resurgence of attention to the individual body, *nikutai*, marking a trend described as "bodyism," championed by literary figures like Sakaguchi Ango, Tamura Taijirō, and Tanaka Hidemitsu. The rejection of subordinating individual desires to national projects was seen as a revolutionary act and a form of protest against the overarching influence of the *kokutai*.²¹² Shunsuke Tsurumi noticeably puts:

«But after the defeat, and after the emperor's proclamation that he was only a human being, the idea of national structure also fell off like another layer of dandruff. Then all that finally remained was the body. This was the basis of what was called "bodyism", rampant in the period after the war and persisting in varied forms to this day. To be true to the needs of the body was proclaimed the supreme aim in the post-war literature. »²¹³

Therefore, the emperor publicly renounced his divine status, and Japan transitioned to a constitutional monarchy with a democratic framework. While the term *kokutai* persisted, its meaning shifted to align with the new political realities. In the postwar period, discussions about *kokutai* often revolved around its historical implications, its role in wartime propaganda, and its continued presence in Japanese political and cultural discourse. The term remains a complex and debated topic in contemporary Japan, with various interpretations and perspectives.²¹⁴

²¹¹ Slaymaker, Douglas. *The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction*. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>. 12.

²¹² *Ibid*, 12.

²¹³ Tsurumi, Shunsuke, and Shunsuke Tsurumi. *An Intellectual History of Wartime Japan: 1931-1945*. Reprint. Japanese Studies. London: Routledge & Kegan, 1986. 41.

²¹⁴ *Ibid*, 41.

The various representations of the body in postwar Japanese cultural media should be interpreted in light of the official narrative's attempt to create a body devoid of historical context. These images of the body also reflect the dual process of expressing and suppressing the past in postwar cultural discourse. The once-intact body of the nation underwent fragmentation during the transformative period of imperial Japan, and these fragmented bodily images were reassembled in the postwar era to articulate the new sense of nationhood. Metaphorically, body parts were stitched together to restore the nation's organic unity and overcome its trauma. However, the visible scar left by this suture on the discursive body served as a constant reminder of the underlying trauma. Japan's loss was both concealed and inscribed as a conspicuous sign on the surface of the body.²¹⁵

These different connotations of the body find resonance with Michel Foucault's exploration of the "history of the body." This intersection is evident in the political discourse surrounding *kokutai*, where the unified national body becomes a focal point for justifying political authority and constructing a specific national identity. Foucault's emphasis on discipline and punishment as tools of societal regulation aligns with *kokutai* historical role, particularly during the prewar and wartime periods, where dissent against the concept or actions perceived as conflicting with the national interest were met with severe consequences.²¹⁶

The transformation of *kokutai* post-World War Two reflects Foucault's ideas about shifts in historical perceptions of the body and power dynamics. Additionally, the notion of "bodyism" in postwar Japanese literature, resonates with Foucault's exploration of bodies as sites of resistance and identity, as these literary expressions engage with the body as a locus of rebellion against past authoritarian ideologies associated with *kokutai*. This dynamic interplay between *kokutai* and Foucault's "history of the body" underscores the complex relationship between political power, national identity, and individual bodies in Japanese history.²¹⁷

The concept of interpellation, by Althusser, finds resonance in the Japanese texts' exploration of how language positions individuals within certain roles or identities concerning the body, impacting actions and self-perception. Interpellation refers to the mechanism by which language shapes a social role for an individual, thereby rendering them an ideological subject.

²¹⁵ Igarashi, Yoshikuni. *Bodies of Memory: Narratives of War in Postwar Japanese Culture, 1945 - 1970*. Princeton Paperbacks. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2000. 14.

²¹⁶ Michel Foucault, *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*. New York: Vintage Books, 1979.

²¹⁷ Slaymaker, Douglas. *The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction*. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>.

The tension between different terms like *nikutai* and *shintai* in Japanese cultural discourse reflects the struggles and negotiations of meaning embedded in linguistic constructions.²¹⁸

Pierre Bourdieu's "*Language and Symbolic Power*" offers a nuanced exploration of language as a tool of social power and control. Bourdieu's work emphasizes how linguistic practices are deeply entwined with social hierarchies and power relations. He challenges traditional linguistic theories, proposing instead that language is a social-historical phenomenon. Bourdieu argues that linguistic expressions cannot be understood in isolation from their social contexts. He introduces the concept of the "linguistic habitus," a set of dispositions acquired through social interactions that shape language use. His work reveals how linguistic practices contribute to the maintenance and transformation of social structures, emphasizing the interplay between language, power, and society.²¹⁹

To connect this with the concept of body in Japanese literature and culture, Bourdieu's framework can be applied to understand how the language surrounding the body reflects and reinforces social and cultural norms. In Bourdieu's analysis, language is not just a means of communication but a medium of power. This concept can be extended to the discourse surrounding *nikutai* in postwar Japanese literature. The shift in language from more neutral or spiritual terms like *shintai*, or *seishin* to *nikutai*, with its carnal connotations, reflects a societal response to wartime experiences and ideologies. This linguistic evolution is an assertion of individuality and physicality against a backdrop of collective national identity *kokutai*, signifying a rebellion against the repressive, collective ideologies of wartime Japan.

This shift in linguistic preference encapsulates a profound power struggle, where language and its connotations become potent tools for the redefinition and reclamation of identity and autonomy. Drawing on Bourdieu's perspective, this linguistic transformation takes on added significance, serving as a powerful means of symbolic resistance and the reshaping of both social norms and individual identity. In this dynamic interplay between language and power, the act of adopting or discarding specific terms becomes a deliberate and strategic choice.

The choice of words and linguistic expressions becomes a battlefield where individuals and communities strive to assert their agency and reshape the narratives that define them, and it is

²¹⁸ Althusser, Louis. *On the Reproduction of Capitalism: Ideology and Ideological State Apparatuses*. London: Verso, 2014. 190.

²¹⁹ Bourdieu, Pierre, John B. Thompson, and Gino Raymond. *Language and Symbolic Power*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2009.

not merely a linguistic adjustment. As Bourdieu emphasizes, language operates as a symbolic field where individuals and communities engage in a continual negotiation of meaning, reflecting the broader socio-cultural landscape. Therefore, this linguistic evolution serves as a powerful means of expressing dissent, pushing back against existing norms, and forging new paths of self-expression and societal definition.²²⁰

The book “*Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method*” delves into the profound impact of language and discourse on shaping social reality, emphasizing their active role in constructing perceptions of the world, identities, and social relations. This, again, resonates with the nuanced concept of the body in Japan, by exploring diverse approaches, the book underscores the pivotal role language plays in structuring social interactions and unraveling power dynamics. It contends that our understanding of the world and our place within it is intricately linked to the discursive practices we engage in, highlighting the significant role language plays in shaping experiences and interactions.²²¹

Moreover, the book explores how discourse contributes to the construction of meaning surrounding the body. It contends that language doesn’t just express the self; it actively constructs the self. This goes with the main analysis of this thesis on ideologies shape the concept of body and the self; the individual becomes a medium for cultural language, shaping identity and subjectivity. This challenges the Western notion of the subject as an autonomous entity, suggesting that individuals are ideologically shaped through discourses.²²² The main character’s personal experience of distress and identity crisis therefore reflects broader social processes in Japan that could be also rooted in how language has been articulated.

Additionally, the book introduces the concept of intertextuality, emphasizing how texts and discourses are interconnected, shaping our understanding of the body and its significance. It suggests that various discourses, such as those related to *seishin* (or spirit), *nikutai* (or carnal bod), *seikaku* (or personality), *kokutai* (or national body) in Japanese language, play a crucial role in influencing societal norms and individual behaviors.

²²⁰ Ibid.

²²¹ Jørgensen, Marianne, and Louise Phillips. *Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method*. 6 Bonhill Street, London England EC2A 4PU United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd, 2002.

<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849208871>.

²²² Ibid.

Overall, the book provides a comprehensive exploration of the intricate relationship between language, discourse, and bodily experiences. It unveils the transformative role of language in constructing perceptions, identities, and actions, highlighting its multifaceted impact on our understanding of the body within the broader social context.

Furthermore, language carries a “symbolic” violence, embodying what Heidegger describes as “our house of being.” However, a more fundamental form of violence lies within language itself, stemming from its imposition of a specific universe of meaning, as explored so far. This inherent violence is rooted in language’s power to shape perceptions, construct realities, and prescribe particular interpretations. It operates beyond the explicit expressions of words, influencing the very framework within which individuals understand and navigate the world.²²³

In this sense, language exercises a profound authority in constructing not only communication but also the broader cognitive and cultural landscapes. The imposition of a predefined system of meaning can be seen as an act of violence on the diversity of human experiences and perspectives, limiting the possibilities of expression and understanding. Recognizing this fundamental linguistic violence calls for an interrogation of the structures that govern language and an exploration of alternative, more inclusive linguistic frameworks.²²⁴

One thing that should be kept in mind is the relationship between the signifier (signifiant) and the signified (signifié) is arbitrary and not inherent, as proposed by Ferdinand de Saussure. This means that the meaning we attach to words or signs is not naturally present in them but is a product of social conventions. Saussure’s key point is that the meaning of individual signs is determined by their relationship to other signs within a language system. A sign gains its specific value and meaning from its difference from other signs. The words and signs we use derive their meanings not from any inherent qualities but from the complex system of differences and associations established within a particular language and culture. This concept emphasizes the idea that language and meaning are socially constructed, not naturally occurring phenomena.²²⁵

This perspective has implications for the understanding of the body in Japan, particularly in the context of linguistic constructs. If we apply Saussure's ideas to the Japanese cultural

²²³ Zizek, Slavoj. *Violence: Six Sideways Reflections*. New York: Picador, 2008. 1.

²²⁴ *Ibid*, 2.

²²⁵ Saussure, Ferdinand de. *Course in General Linguistics*. Translated and annotated by Roy Harris. Bloomsbury, London, Sydney, New York, New Delhi.

discourse on the body, it becomes apparent that the meanings associated with body-related terms, such as *nikutai* and *shintai*, are socially constructed. The distinctions and nuances attributed to these terms are not inherent but arise from their relationships with other linguistic elements within the Japanese language. This sociolinguistic perspective challenges any essentialist notions about the body in Japan, suggesting that its meaning is contingent on the linguistic and cultural framework within which it is situated.²²⁶

2.8 The Body at the Confluence of Japanese Culture

The cultural expressions and symbols associated with the body in established Japanese customs and rituals seem to embody the concept of the ideal Japanese body. This ideal body is expected to exude a distinctive aesthetic that demands discipline and refinement, and the term that encapsulates this perspective is “mind-body.” This subordination of the body is a result of a combination of external authorities, societal norms, and influence from Buddhist monks. At times, these three aspects become so interconnected that they are indistinguishable.²²⁷ Zen master Dogen, for instance, says that «learning through the “mind” must be united with learning through the “body” (*shinjitsunintai* (真実忍耐) ... “truth” + “reality” + “human body,” literally “the real human body” ».²²⁸

To see the body at the confluence of Japanese culture it is essential to consider *bushido* (武士道) “Way of the Warrior”. According to some interpretations, *bushido* has been proposed as the fundamental “essence” of the Japanese people, serving as the “inspiring spirit” and “driving force.” *Bushido* is founded on eight fundamental principles: “courage, benevolence, politeness, selflessness, sincerity, honor, loyalty, self-control, and a strong sense of justice.”²²⁹ The ideal form of the Japanese body finds its embodiment in the cultural phenomenon like Samurai, geisha, accompanied by the serene elegance of the tea ceremony and the captivating allure of traditional theater. These exemplary bodies undergo rigorous training and specialized

²²⁶ Ibid.

²²⁷ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 30-34.

²²⁸ McCarthy, Erin. Ethics Embodied: Rethinking Selfhood through Continental, Japanese, and Feminist Philosophies. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2010. 39.

²²⁹ Benesch, Oleg. Inventing the Way of the Samurai: Nationalism, Internationalism, and Bushido in Modern Japan. First edition. The Past & Present Book Series. Oxford, England ; New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2014. 1.

education to achieve beauty and liberate the soul.²³⁰ In this section we are going to explore these four cultural elements.

2.8.1 Harakiri and Samurai

Harakiri (腹切), also known as *seppuku* (切腹), is a form of ritual of suicide that holds a prominent place in the Japanese code of bravery. The act is often associated with samurai, particularly during feudal Japan, and is considered a solemn method of maintaining honor and preserving one's dignity in the face of shame or defeat. The two terms, *seppuku* and *harakiri*, essentially refer to the same act but are distinguished by their pronunciation styles. In contemporary Japanese society, the official term is *seppuku*, while *harakiri* is used conversationally and not in formal or official contexts.²³¹

Harakiri is commonly discussed in Western literature, appearing in sources like the Encyclopedia Britannica, Nelson's Encyclopedia, and Webster's New International Dictionary. Webster's definition describes *harakiri* as suicide by the nobles and samurai in cases of perceived or actual disgrace. It involves disembowelment and is more formally referred to as *seppuku*. This practice was not only employed as an honorable death sentence for those violating certain laws of Tokugawa, military government of Japan during the Edo period from 1603 to 1868, but also served as a means to express resistance, remonstrance, loyalty, and affirmation of one's position.²³²

Harakiri was executed in a ceremonious manner, often with sympathy for the condemned individual, turning the act into a form of self-punishment and expiation. It was granted only to those deemed worthy of respect despite violating certain codes or regulations, and the condemned individual had the opportunity to strike the first blow toward their own death, making it a unique form of the death penalty within the cultural and historical context of Japan. *Harakiri* has its origins in feudal Japan, where it was practiced by samurai as a means of avoiding capture, expressing remorse for failure, or protesting against perceived injustices. Over time, it became formalized as a ritualized act with established procedures.²³³

²³⁰ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 37.

²³¹ Seward, Jack. HARA-KIRI Japanese Ritual Suicide. Rutland, Vermont & Tokyo, Japan: Charles E. Tuttle Company, 1972. 13.

²³² Ibid, 12-13.

²³³ Ibid, 17.

In February 1868, several Japanese soldiers from Bizen attacked the foreign settlement in Kobe, known as Hiogo at that time. The Bizen samurai held accountable for this act was commanded to perform *harakiri*. Lord Redesdale, who observed the ceremony, documented the event in his book, "Tales of Old Japan."²³⁴ An excerpt from the account reads as follows:

«[...] After an interval of a few minutes of anxious suspense, Taki-Zenzaburô, a stalwart man, thirty-two years of age, with a noble air, walked into the hall attired in his dress of ceremony, with the peculiar hempen-cloth wings which are worn on great occasions. He was accompanied by a *kaishaku*, (a person appointed to behead an individual who has performed seppuku), and three officers, who wore the *jimbaori* or war surcoat with gold-tissue facings. The office is that of a gentleman; in many cases, it is performed by a kinsman or friend of the condemned, and the relation between them is rather that of principal and second than that of victim and executioner.

With the *kaishaku* on his left hand, Taki-Zenzaburô advanced slowly towards the Japanese witnesses, and the two bowed before them, then drawing near to the foreigners they saluted us in the same way, perhaps even with more deference; in each case the salutation was ceremoniously returned. Slowly, and with great dignity, the condemned man mounted on to the raised floor, prostrated himself before the high altar twice, and seated himself on the left carpet with his back to the high altar, the *kaishaku* crouching on his left-hand side. One of the three attendant officers then came forward, bearing a stand of the kind used in temples for offerings, on which, wrapped in paper, lay the wakizashi, the short sword or dirk of the Japanese, nine inches and a half in length, with a point and an edge as sharp as a razor's. This he handed, prostrating himself, to the condemned man, who received it reverently, raising it to his head with both hands, and placed it in front of himself.

After another profound obeisance, Taki-Zenzaburô, in a voice which betrayed just so much emotion as might be expected from a man who is making a painful confession, but with no sign of either in his face or manner, spoke as follows:

²³⁴ Mitford, A.B., and Algernon Bertram Freeman-Mitf Redesdale. Tales of Old Japan: Folklore, Fairy Tales, Ghost Stories and Legends of the Samurai. Mineola, New York: Dover Publications, INC., 1876. 320-322.

“I, and I alone, unwarrantedly gave the order to fire on the foreigners at Kobe, and again as they tried to escape. For this crime I disembowel myself, and I beg you who are present to do me the honor of witnessing the act.”

Bowing once more, the speaker allowed his upper garments to slip down to his girdle and remained naked to the waist. Carefully, according to custom, he tucked his sleeves under his knees to prevent himself from falling backward; for a noble Japanese gentleman should die falling forwards. Deliberately, with a steady hand, he took the dirk that lay before him; he looked at it wistfully, almost affectionately; for a moment he seemed to collect his thoughts for a last time, and then stabbing himself deeply below the waist on the left hand side, he drew the dirk slowly across to the right side, and, turning it in the wound, gave a slight cut upwards. Through this sickeningly painful operation he never moved a muscle of his face. When he drew out the dirk, he leaned forward and stretched out his neck; an expression of pain for the first time crossed his face, but he uttered no sound. At that moment, the *kaishaku*, who, still crouching at his side, had been keenly watching his every movement, sprang to his feet, poised his sword for a second in the air; there was a flash, a heavy, ugly thud, a crashing fall; with one blow the head had been severed from the body. »²³⁵

This seemingly paradoxical act of willingly embracing such a painful and difficult death is rooted in the essence of *bushido*, a code that not only shapes the identity of the samurai but, on a broader scale, encapsulates the soul and identity of the Japanese people.²³⁶ In the context of *bushido*, the term “samurai” conveys a sense of submission, illustrating how these warriors were profoundly obedient to the command and discipline of *bushido*. Their willingness to endure immense pain, reaching the depths of their souls and resorting to *harakiri*, if necessary, reflects the commitment to this code of conduct. The samurai's body, according to *bushido*, embodies three fundamental features.

²³⁵ Mitford, A.B., and Algernon Bertram Freeman-Mitf Redesdale. *Tales of Old Japan: Folklore, Fairy Tales, Ghost Stories and Legends of the Samurai*. Mineola, New York: Dover Publications, INC., 1876. 320.

²³⁶ Benesch, Oleg. *Inventing the Way of the Samurai: Nationalism, Internationalism, and Bushido in Modern Japan*. First edition. The Past & Present Book Series. Oxford, England ; New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2014. 1.

Firstly, the samurai's body had to undergo rigorous training, cultivating courage and bravery within them. This intensive training not only physically prepared them but also fortified their mental resilience.

The second aspect emphasized the necessity for the samurai's body to be under the strict control of their mind, achieved through demanding exercises. A true samurai had to master the ability to conceal all emotions from their face and body, eliminating any signs of fear or distress caused by wounds. This stoicism was considered a manifestation of the principle of respect.

Lastly, the samurai's body needed to be in a perpetual state of readiness to face death at any moment, demonstrating an exceptional capacity to endure pain. *Harakiri*, as a practice emerging from this third characteristic, symbolized the ultimate manifestation of a samurai's preparedness to confront mortality.²³⁷

A samurai, whether self-imposed or commanded by his master, would enact self-punishment by performing the act of *harakiri*. This act symbolized the belief that his body, deemed unworthy of the samurai code, needed to be eradicated, and he would be buried with honor. The significance of *harakiri* lies not solely in the physical pain inflicted but rather in the harmony achieved between mind and body. Unlike the Christian interpretation of bodily suffering, *harakiri's* merit is not inherent in the pain itself but rather in the synchronization of mind and body.²³⁸

Some samurai would engage in battles, resisting death at the hands of their enemies. The sanctified body of a samurai was considered too sacred to be disfigured by enemies. Thus, it was considered irresponsible to allow a stranger to destroy the well-regarded samurai body and expose its vulnerability in combat. The samurai's body, through *harakiri*, transformed into an ideal form – a body so controlled by the mind that it could command its own death. Through *harakiri*, a samurai demonstrated that even in the face of the ultimate bodily suffering, his body remained subservient to the mind, retaining the ability to transcend the natural instinct to escape such pain.²³⁹

²³⁷ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 37.

²³⁸ *Ibid*, 39.

²³⁹ *Ibid*, 40.

2.8.2 Kimono and Geisha

Clothing serves as the juncture where the body, culture, and self-converge, defining the cultural and authoritative aspects of the body based on desires and expectations. Through the medium of clothing, authority establishes control over the people, using the body as a canvas to manifest its power dynamics and revealing the contrast or alignment with dominance. Cultures articulate the physical presence of bodies in society through clothing, evident in authoritative institutions like the military, schools, and certain governments that prescribe identical attire, symbolizing uniform tasks and identities before the wielders of power.

This uniformity carries profound significance, reflecting identical and akin identities with predefined roles in the hierarchical power structure. Thus, clothing becomes a carrier of deep cultural meaning, shaping the visual aesthetics of a society alongside architecture, nature, roads, and pathways, encapsulating the profound layers of cultural identity.²⁴⁰

Turning our attention to the traditional clothing of the Japanese people, the *kimono* (着物), considered the oldest and most authentic attire, encapsulates a cultural identity distinct from Western garments like pants, skirts, and shirts. Initially, the *kimono* presents itself as a flowing robe, extending from the shoulders to the feet, enveloping the entire body with generously loose-fitting sleeves. Its design features geometric patterns, and the sleeves and body panels share equal widths, determined by the size of the loom. When laid flat before wrapping, it forms four panels across the body.²⁴¹

According to Katherine Mezur, a prominent scholar, the *kimono* de-emphasizes the gendered aspects of the body. Whether wrapped or unwrapped, the *kimono* doesn't unveil the body's contours. Comprising multiple layers of mantles worn atop each other, the *kimono*

progressively conceals the body. It imparts a distinct shape to the wearer. In certain roles, the *kimono* actively shapes and embodies the body itself. *Kimono* presenting itself not merely as clothing but as a transformative cultural emblem. In this layered concealment, the *kimono* stands as a testament to the nuanced identity and tradition of Japan.²⁴²

²⁴⁰ Ibid, 40.

²⁴¹ Mezur, Katherine. *Beautiful Boys, Outlaw Bodies: Devising Kabuki Female-Likeness*. New York (N. Y.): Palgrave Mac Millan, 2006. 143.

²⁴² Ibid, 187.

The *kimono* conceals both the physical and sexual aspects of the body, embodying a unique aesthetic significance. This dress is not designed for *nikutai* (the carnal body) where dimensions are different in each person. With no buttons, absent of zippers or straps, it not only holds aesthetic importance but also eradicates the concept of “size” altogether.²⁴³ *Kimonos* defy standard sizing, avoiding the individualization of bodies based on shape and dimensions.

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Unlike clothing designed for the physical variations among individuals, *kimonos* aim to mold all female and male bodies into a uniform shape. In doing so, diverse bodies become part of a collective, symbolizing a non-material unity. The distinguishing factor among individuals shifts from the *kimono*'s model or size to the patterns adorning it. Therefore, an essential aspect of analyzing the *kimono* as a cultural sign lies in interpreting its designs.²⁴⁵

Traditional *kimono* designs draw inspiration from the beauty of nature in Japan, featuring poetic and symbolic representations of natural elements often hand-woven onto the fabric. Motifs such as cherry blossoms, water waves, mountain birds, sacred flowers, and ornate patterns abstractly adorn *kimonos*. Nature's significance in *kimono* patterns is underscored by the seasonal variations, with different motifs representing each season. The *kimono* serves as a cultural expression that covers the body's reality through multiple layers, weaving a poetic tapestry of nature's beauty. It symbolizes the dominance of culture over body. Recognizing this reveals profound meaning to the intricate interplay between culture, nature, and the body.²⁴⁶

Kimono serves as a manifestation of distinctive Japanese body in public spaces. Another aspect of the *kimono*, particularly women's *kimonos*, involves the “subjugation of the body”. The traditional *kimono*, primarily associated with elite classes, undergoes a detailed process. To begin with, the process involves tightly wrapping the body with snug bands, giving it a streamlined, column-like appearance. Afterward, additional layers are added, leading up to the

²⁴³ Hanako. *The Geisha Secret: Ancient Dating Rituals Proven to Win a Modern Man's Heart*. New York: FassFrankfurt Publishers, 2013. 13.

²⁴⁴ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 42.

²⁴⁵ Mezur, Katherine. *Beautiful Boys, Outlaw Bodies: Devising Kabuki Female-Likeness*. New York (N. Y.): Palgrave Mac Millan, 2006. 187.

²⁴⁶ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019. 42.

last one—the patterned dress. A waist dress is put on over this outfit. It's not meant to highlight the waist but to match the colors and patterns of the *kimono*.²⁴⁷

This arrangement creates a rhythm and harmony while hiding the gap between the waist hollow and chest ridge. The first tight bands and additional layers, however, impose constraints, make it hard to walk, sit, and stand easily. Taking big steps, running, or walking unevenly is limited, and sitting and standing are completely controlled by the dress. When sitting, you can't freely put your feet on the ground. This dress is carefully made to show authority over the body, creating a submissive form that consistently recalls its owner's control, refusing it the freedom of unrestricted movements.²⁴⁸

Samurai clothing allows more freedom compared to *kimonos*.²⁴⁹ Meanwhile, the *kimono*, as women's clothing, also plays a role in shaping the perception of the female body in Japanese culture. This definition becomes particularly evident in another cultural phenomenon known as *geisha*.

The cultural phenomenon of *geisha* (芸者) is another example that demonstrates the discipline of the body in Japan. The term “*geisha*” is a combination of two words: “*gei*,” meaning art, and “*sha*,” meaning individual.²⁵⁰ *Geisha* is a professionally trained female artist who resides and works in communities dedicated to the pursuit of pleasure. As Iwasaki and Brown said in 2002, “*Geisha* is like a flower, beautiful in her own way, and like a willow tree, gracious, flexible, and strong.”²⁵¹ Hanako²⁵² describes *geishas* this way:

«A man fortunate enough to be in the presence of the *geisha* was immediately mesmerized by her beauty. Her makeup was meticulously applied, accentuating her lips to create a perfect rosebud against her delicately painted white face. This enabled her to stand out when performing on a dimly lit stage. Her luxurious black hair was ornately styled and worn up, revealing the nape of her neck. She adorned herself with accessories – parasols, fans and handbags – crafted from handmade

²⁴⁷ Ibid, 42.

²⁴⁸ Ibid, 45.

²⁴⁹ Ibid, 46.

²⁵⁰ Ibid, 46.

²⁵¹ Iwasaki, Mineko, and Rande Brown. *Geisha: A Life*. New York, 2002. 10.

²⁵² Hanako. *The Geisha Secret: Ancient Dating Rituals Proven to Win a Modern Man's Heart*. New York: FassFrankfurt Publishers, 2013. 12.

paper, silk, and bamboo. There were many aspects that were integral to the *geisha*'s appearance, but her *kimonos* were the most critical. »²⁵³

Geisha, by wearing *kimono* hide their bodies more in each layer. *Kimono* is also exceedingly respected to them to the point that they referred to it as their soul.²⁵⁴ This emphasis on layered clothing mirrors the deeper cultural significance and discipline embedded in the art of the Geisha. Gender is concealed under layers of makeup, color, clothing, and roles. Every aspect of a woman's physique, including skin color, is concealed from view.²⁵⁵

Geishas still exist in Japan, and there are five schools across the country that continue to train them. Contrary to the misconception of geishas as prostitutes, they embody the ideal image of a female body according to traditional Japanese culture, situated at the enchanting intersection of Shintoism and Buddhism. Buddhism, characterized by sexual asceticism, and Shintoism, lacking clear moral principles, underwent transformations in popular culture, allowing men to confine their wives to domestic roles while seeking love and pleasure outside the home. Consequently, prostitution was not viewed as an unusual practice.²⁵⁶

The geisha seems to represent a unique synthesis of these cultural elements. It is believed that a woman's body outside the home can provide men with pleasure, but this pleasure is non-sexual and exclusive, centered around the enjoyment of beauty. Perhaps for this reason, the geisha stands distinct from the prostitute, embodying an artist. Despite certain periods where even the existence of prostitutes was prohibited, *geishas* were permitted. The body of a geisha is a female body constructed through culture, art, and an idealized vision of womanhood.²⁵⁷

There is no classification of geishas as ugly or beautiful, nor are there well-dressed or poorly dressed geishas. Every geisha is considered beautiful, yet their beauty is crafted, painted, and meticulously designed to embody female beauty.²⁵⁸ Arthur Golden, the author of the book of "Memoirs of a Geisha"²⁵⁹ in a part of the story says:

²⁵³ Ibid, 12.

²⁵⁴ Ibid, 12.

²⁵⁵ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 46.

²⁵⁶ Ibid, 46.

²⁵⁷ Ibid, 46.

²⁵⁸ Ibid, 47.

²⁵⁹ Golden, Arthur. *Memoirs of a Geisha*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 1997.

«In the years since, I've been called beautiful more often than I can remember. Though, of course, *geishas* are always called beautiful, even those who aren't. But when Mr. Tanaka said it to me, before I'd ever heard of such a thing as a *geisha*, I could almost believe it was true. »²⁶⁰

Understanding the role of a geisha can be challenging for cultures outside of Japan, as it is an exclusively Japanese phenomenon. This uniqueness stems from the fact that only Japanese culture could give rise to such a phenomenon—a showcase of female beauty that, through clothing and makeup, distances itself from the realm of the sexual and physical body.²⁶¹

This cultural phenomenon, aimed at providing pleasure to men, takes great care to ensure that this pleasure does not cross into the realm of physical intimacy. Perhaps, it is the peculiar combination of Shintoism and Buddhism that has led to the creation of such a distinctive cultural expression. Geishas hide their bodies under layers of clothing,²⁶² transforming themselves into mysterious figures.²⁶³

None of their physical attributes, including their skin color, is showed.²⁶⁴ They meticulously paint their entire faces and necks, treating their makeup as an art form that elevates them to the status of living artworks.²⁶⁵ Geishas serve as embodiments of feminine beauty and purveyors of dreams, managing to captivate without resorting to overtly sexual displays.²⁶⁶ It is a phenomenon designed for men's enjoyment, providing entertainment through the appreciation of beauty while consciously avoiding entering the realm of sexual boundaries.²⁶⁷

2.8.3 Temae and Tea Ceremony

Another cultural feature to illustrate the bodily discipline in Japan is tea ceremony. The “signifier” – the physical expressions and movements involved in the tea ceremony – manifests in the precise bodily movements dictated by the *temae* (点前). In other words, the specific,

²⁶⁰ Ibid, 27.

²⁶¹ Samini, Naghme. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 47.

²⁶² Ibid, 47.

²⁶³ Hanako. The Geisha Secret: Ancient Dating Rituals Proven to Win a Modern Man's Heart. New York: FassFrankfurt Publishers, 2013. 12.

²⁶⁴ Mezur, Katherine. Beautiful Boys, Outlaw Bodies: Devising Kabuki Female-Likeness. New York (N. Y.): Palgrave Mac Millan, 2006. 187.

²⁶⁵ Downer, Lesley. Women of the Pleasure Quarters: The Secret History of the Geisha. New York: Broadway Books, 2002. 86.

²⁶⁶ Golden, Arthur. Memoirs of a Geisha. New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 1997.

²⁶⁷ Samini, Naghme. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 48.

ritualized movements in the tea ceremony serve as a form of communication or expression, embodying the cultural and symbolic significance of the ceremony. *Temae*, meaning the sophisticated rules and highly formalized bodily movement during tea preparation, has been a foundational aspect of the tea ceremony since its beginning. Although the *temae* and their pedagogy have undergone changes over time, they remain a crucial element of the practice.²⁶⁸

The significance of *temae* becomes evident in the discussion about cultural and symbolic capital. In a society before capitalism, there are different kinds of valuable assets. “Symbolic capital” refers to the honor and prestige gained from successfully using various types of capital.²⁶⁹

In capitalist society, art falls into this category. “Cultural capital” on the other hand, is a type of knowledge that helps a person understand cultural relationships and artifacts.²⁷⁰ It is often passed down through families and education. Cultural capital can also be turned into economic capital, for example, turning educational qualifications into well-paying jobs.²⁷¹

In this context, the tea ceremony involves both cultural and symbolic capital. It requires knowledge, skills, and technical qualifications (cultural capital), and it brings honor and prestige (symbolic capital). For instance, when a tea ceremony practitioner buys an expensive cup of tea at a cultural festival or an art exhibition, it's not just about their economic wealth but also about demonstrating their understanding of cultural relations and artifacts in public spaces.²⁷²

The connection between *temae* and cultural capital is further supported by historical examples. In societies before capitalism, *temae* provided a means for nondominant social groups to gain symbolic-cultural capital by not only purportedly cultivated physical discipline but also claimed the development of mental control.²⁷³ Learning these formalized movements and the

²⁶⁸ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> . 2.

²⁶⁹ Bourdieu, Pierre. *The Logic of Practice*. Translated by Richard Nice. 1980. 118.

²⁷⁰ Bourdieu, Pierre. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. 11. print. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Univ. Press, 2002. 2.

²⁷¹ *Ibid*, 23.

²⁷² Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> . 4.

²⁷³ Bourdieu, Pierre. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. 11. print. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Univ. Press, 2002. 2.

mental control were a mean for nondominant but ambitious social groups to develop self-discipline associated with socially superior groups.²⁷⁴

Additionally, across various historical periods, these nondominant groups sought to legitimize their tea ceremony activities by constructing narratives and myths attributing its origins to prominent historical figures, political authorities, and significant religious and philosophical tenets. These myths served to establish a connection between practitioners of *temae* and illustrious impressive “ancestors” and deep thoughts to make them more respected. This respect wasn’t just for show - it helped them get what’s called symbolic-cultural capital, which is like getting recognition for being part of high culture.²⁷⁵

Over time, the tea ceremony became even more special, especially after World War Two, as it became part of our “tradition.” In the postwar period, women, particularly those in urban areas, were considered one of these “nondominant social group.” They, too, found empowerment through the tea ceremony, using it as a means to gain symbolic-cultural capital and challenge traditional gender roles. This illustrates how *temae*, with its dual role in imparting cultural and symbolic capital, has been a dynamic and transformative practice throughout different historical periods.²⁷⁶

So far what we discussed above is that «the body has always been a central concern of tea ceremony practitioners, regardless of gender and historical time»,²⁷⁷ as a means for “discipline” in Foucault’s sense²⁷⁸— that is, refinement of one’s body movement so as to control one’s mind. «The tea ceremony is bodily discipline’ to control one’s body movement so as to control one’s mind»²⁷⁹ to get to the symbolic-cultural capital.²⁸⁰

Within the tea ceremony, the practitioner communicates without words, relying solely on the language of the body. The guest, seated in silence, observes as the practitioner accurately prepares green tea in a specially selected room, obeying to thoughtful and precise movements. The ceremony unfolds without inessential gestures, strictly following established rules. The tea

²⁷⁴Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*: New York: Vintage Books, 1979.

²⁷⁵ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women’s Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> . 4.

²⁷⁶ Ibid, 4.

²⁷⁷ Ibid, 21.

²⁷⁸ Foucault, Michel. *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*: New York: Vintage Books, 1979.

²⁷⁹ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women’s Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> . 25.

²⁸⁰ Bourdieu, Pierre. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. 11. print. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Univ. Press, 2002. 2.

is poured into a bowl and presented to the guest, initiating a series of predetermined rituals. These rituals include specific actions such as not pouring the tea immediately, rotating the cup before drinking, refraining from making gestures, and maintaining a designated sitting posture.²⁸¹ As Kato (2004) says:

«The overwhelming control of body movement may make *temae* resemble a dance.²⁸²[...] It is also a noticeable characteristic of the control of body movement by *temae* that every act requires a “proper” posture of the overall body. Opening the sliding door, bowing, whisking tea powder with hot water – all these acts are not simply acts of the hands or the head but also acts of the properly straightened back, the elbows stuck out, or the fingers neatly put together. »²⁸³

The particular control of body movement in *temae*, as noted by Kato (2004), gives rise to a dance-like quality, emphasizing the importance of proper posture throughout each ceremonial act. This attention to bodily control echoes the broader notion that «where there is discipline, there are discourses that legitimate it. » The relationship between discourses and disciplined body-mind is reciprocal – the discourses both authorize and are reinforced by the disciplined body-mind. In this intricate interplay, the body, as a visible entity, essentially becomes the embodiment of the discourses that validate and sustain the discipline. Thus, the execution of *temae* becomes a tangible representation of the interconnected dynamics between bodily control and the legitimizing discourses associated with discipline.²⁸⁴

The origin of the tea ceremony can be traced back to the desire for both bodily and mental control. This inclination may find its roots in the Japanese way of thinking, which tends to associate the body with the mind, emphasizing bodily control as a means of achieving mental control, as reflected in the concept of *sahō*. Another motivating factor for nondominant individuals seeking bodily and mental control could be the association of such discipline with the dominant classes, including aristocrats, warriors, and priests.²⁸⁵

²⁸¹ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 49.

²⁸² Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> . 28.

²⁸³ *Ibid*, 31.

²⁸⁴ *Ibid*, 45.

²⁸⁵ *Ibid*, 47.

Bourdieu (1980) highlights the significance of the body in reinforcing discourses related to socio-political power. He asserts that power is exerted primarily on the body, creating a natural belief in the dominance of this power within people's minds. According to Bourdieu:

«Practical belief is not just a “state of mind” ... but a state of the body’²⁸⁶, and ‘bodily hexis, is political mythology realized, embodied, turned into a permanent disposition, a durable way of standing, speaking, and thereby of feeling and thinking. »²⁸⁷

In this context, mythology is interchangeable with belief, representing the discourses necessary for certain social groups to dominate others. The wish for mental control through bodily control, as manifested in the tea ceremony, can be seen as a response to these complex interconnections between the body, discipline, and social power.²⁸⁸

In conclusion, the cultural definition of the body in the context of the tea ceremony, as other cultural elements that we have discussed so far, was institutionally shaped to embody a set of specific characteristics – a body with complete control over its movements and parts, a preciously molded and highly structured form. This idealized body, the only one deemed worthy of visibility and recognition, became a symbol endorsed by the ruling class and the Japanese clergy. In this way, marginalized social groups found a means of legitimizing themselves while sidestepping the margins of societal discourse. Therefore, it is evident that both aristocrats and Buddhist clergy shared a common objective: the cultivation of a disciplined body and mind-body construction, serving as a unifying thread throughout this cultural practice.²⁸⁹

2.8.4 Traditional Japanese Theater

Exploring body discipline in Japanese culture extends to traditional performances, with the *noh* (能) a traditional form of Japanese musical drama. serving as a notable example. This performance style gained popularity since 14th century. The *noh* show was significantly shaped

²⁸⁶ Bourdieu, Pierre. *The Logic of Practice*. Translated by Richard Nice. 1980. 68.

²⁸⁷ *Ibid*, 69.

²⁸⁸ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> . 51-52.

²⁸⁹ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 51.

and expanded by the contributions of Kan'Ami and Zeami, a father-son duo integral to its establishment and growth.²⁹⁰

Noh performances feature principal actors wearing masks, engaging in dialogue either chanted by the actors or by a small on-stage chorus. Accompanied by drums and a flute, the dance in *noh* is characterized by its deliberate slowness and sedateness, involving circular movements with minimal foot elevation, occasionally punctuated by rhythmic stamping. Props are intentionally minimal, and the set design remains constant—a simple wooden backdrop decorated with a painted pine tree. The small stage is distinguished by a walkway extending from a greenroom to the main stage, adding to the unique aesthetics and intentional minimalism that define the *noh* tradition.²⁹¹

In the *noh* representation, bodies demonstrate complete control, with movements strictly limited and purposefully calculated. Every action, even the subtlest, occurs under the actor's deliberate guidance within the *noh* performance framework. Beginners in *noh* invest years mastering the art of withholding bodily movements, prioritizing restraint over acquiring a multitude of gestures.

This deliberate limitation of physical actions on the *noh* stage holds profound significance. Each movement carries meaning, marked by pauses in body parts, resembling a puppeteer manipulating a doll, where the actor becomes the puppeteer of his own body. In this realm, the body lacks the lifelike realism and intentionally eschews creating a sense of believability for the audience. Notably, the spectator seating area remains illuminated throughout the performance, and stage assistants openly move about, bringing and taking items and assisting the actors.²⁹²

In this acting approach, a proficient actor is not defined by the ability to convey emotions or enact realism, but rather by the mastery of controlling all body parts. The *noh* theater culture appears to devalue the authentic body—characterized by realistic clothing, movements, and facial expressions—because it is perceived as lacking control and driven by immediate impulses. Rooted in Zen Buddhism, which places equal importance on both body and ego

²⁹⁰ Cavaye, Ronald. *Kabuki: A Pocket Guide*. Singapore: Charles E. Tuttle, 1993. 15.

²⁹¹ *Ibid*, 15.

²⁹² Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 53.

control, this philosophy advocates for moderation, leading the *noh* actor's body to be revered and sanctified through restraint, avoiding unnecessary movements.²⁹³

Zeami, influential in shaping the concept of the play *noh* metaphorically likened the actor on stage to a "flower," emphasizing the process of "blooming" and referring to the actor as a "flower of mystery". This description highlights the mysterious power achieved through the disciplined control of every aspect of the body. The actor's body, disciplined and adhering to a specific predetermined format for all actions, is thereby endowed with a sense of purpose and existence.²⁹⁴

While *noh* stands as a transcendent performance with a restricted audience, *kabuki* (歌舞伎) emerges as a folk and widely embraced show, serving as the interconnection where popular culture and Japanese identity intertwine. Originating in 1603, *kabuki* has played a pivotal role in connecting popular culture and Japanese identity throughout the centuries, enduring into the 20th century with the advent of cinema and television. For nearly three centuries, *kabuki* has been celebrated as a paramount form of dramatic entertainment, captivating audiences from diverse backgrounds. As a show that more broadly unveils Japanese identity, *kabuki* has persisted as a significant cultural expression for people from all walks of life.²⁹⁵

For over four centuries, *kabuki* stood as the primary artistic expression of the merchant class, inherently a popular show that not only reflected cultural and contemporary tastes but also delved into political situations and socio-economic dynamics of its era.²⁹⁶ Although initially it was invented by a woman named Okuni, likely a former shrine maiden and possibly a prostitute, *kabuki* faced moral prejudices leading to the exclusion of women from the stage. The exclusion of women from the stage was justified through the ever-present overtones of prostitution, presented as a pretext for the ban on grounds of immorality.²⁹⁷ Consequently, men were expected to play both women's roles, *onnagata* (女形), and male roles "techiyaka".

In *kabuki* the objective was not to precisely replicate the female body on stage but rather to create a distinct third gender, neither effeminate nor masculine, with its own initial boy body aesthetic, incorporating specific theatrical elements and techniques. Thus, the *onnagata* did not

²⁹³ Ibid, 54.

²⁹⁴ Ibid, 54.

²⁹⁵ Cavaye, Ronald. *Kabuki: A Pocket Guide*. Singapore: Charles E. Tuttle, 1993. 16.

²⁹⁶ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 56.

²⁹⁷ Cavaye, Ronald. *Kabuki: A Pocket Guide*. Singapore: Charles E. Tuttle, 1993. 16.

strive to “represent” women; instead, they crafted their multifaceted “vision” of a constructed female-likeness. The portrayal of the female gender role in *kabuki* never aimed at imitating real women.²⁹⁸

This third body, albeit containing erotic aspects, possessed a perspective foreign to cultures outside Japan. While *kabuki* was intended to offer a form of lower-class sexual entertainment, it remained distant from the corporeal and material aspects of the body.²⁹⁹ The creation and preservation of this third body seemingly fulfilled a need within Japanese identity.

Even when women later entered the theatrical realm as actors, they endeavored to emulate the aesthetics of this third body.³⁰⁰ *Onnagata*, initially emerging out of necessity, gained popularity and established its own aesthetic. *Onnagata* performers had to convey masculine violence beneath their feminine appearance, evoking a profound sense of sadness and grief from the depths of the soul.

This delicate balance navigated the boundaries of gender representation on the *kabuki* stage. The perpetually inhabiting the boundary between man and woman, showcasing this ambiguity as a deliberate choice, ensuring that spontaneity and random actions were absent from their movements; the immediate emotions of the actors were carefully regulated, leaving no room for impulsive expression.³⁰¹

Comparing transcendent and elitist, *noh*, performances with popular, *kabuki*, shows, both presenting men in women’s roles. In the *noh* show, serene expressions and controlled movements dominate to the extent that the absence of the female body might not be as noticeable. Conversely, in *kabuki*, where there is a closer impression to everyday life, actors have the liberty to reveal themselves and articulate their body’s voice more prominently than in the *noh* show.³⁰²

Despite strict regulations in *kabuki*, actors find an opportunity to showcase themselves and make their body heard more effectively than in the *noh*. The absence of female actresses in *kabuki* cultivates a unique aesthetic that contrasts with *noh*. A woman on the *kabuki* stage is

²⁹⁸ Mezur, Katherine. *Beautiful Boys, Outlaw Bodies: Devising Kabuki Female-Likeness*. New York (N. Y.): Palgrave Mac Millan, 2006. 2.

²⁹⁹ *Ibid*, 138.

³⁰⁰ *Ibid*, 36.

³⁰¹ *Ibid*, 137.

³⁰² Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 57.

not expected to abandon all feminine elements, nor is she assumed to be a man assuming female roles like in comedies. She becomes a *onnagata*, a body adorned with both feminine and masculine movements, displaying feminine emotions in theatrical games, while exaggerated violence, characteristic of *techiyaka*, is tempered in their behavior.

The rationale behind the acceptance of this third body by the female form is deeply rooted in the male-centric foundation of traditional Japanese society. Recalling the influence of Buddhism on Japan, where women's bodies were considered polluting and a source of sin, the third body in *kabuki* seeks to establish a connection between the ideal woman of Shinto and the marginalized woman of Buddhism; a woman that is not a woman, but it's also not a man who pretends to be a woman. *Onnagata*, as Mezur articulates, emerges as a distinctive phenomenon specific to *kabuki*, possibly the most unique component.³⁰³

Even the supporting performers surrounding the *kabuki* scene were not permitted to act spontaneously or beyond the established framework. A liberated, abandoned, instinctive body, prone to unscripted movements, found no opportunity or desire to challenge the main presentations of Japanese identity and culture.³⁰⁴

In this section, our investigation delved into the profound implications for understanding the body within the cultural constructs of Japan, emphasizing the centralization of body discipline. Our investigation covered diverse realms, including the role of samurai, geisha and the intricacies of tea ceremonies, the distinctive roles played in traditional performances such as *kabuki*, and the emergence of the unique *onnagata* phenomenon, all indicative of a meticulous approach to body control that transcends conventional gender and identity boundaries. As we transition to the next phase of our exploration, our attention will pivot towards a more expansive study, where we will examine the body at the confluence of Japan's history.

2.9 The Body at the Confluence of Japanese History

In the wake of World War Two and Japan's defeat, the landscape of Japan underwent a profound transformation, reshaping not only its physical infrastructure but also the very essence of its cultural identity. A profound reevaluation of societal values and cultural norms emerged, impacting the sanctity attributed to the disciplined body. The World War Two era conducted in a discourse dominated by extreme patriotism, where the notion of a national body, *kokutai*,

³⁰³ Ibid, 58.

³⁰⁴ Ibid, 58.

as previously discussed, emerged as a central theme. As the country united under the banner of patriotism, alternative discourses, including Westernism and traditionalism, found themselves either reformed into this prevailing narrative or outright rejected.³⁰⁵

The body that gained prominence during this period, classified linguistically as a national body, *kokutai*, embodied the ideals of a soldier-like, patriotic, and brave persona. However, the roots of the traditional body, encapsulated in the concept of “body-mind,” were deeply entrenched in Japan's history, resisting complete displacement by the emergent national body. Interestingly, the historical connection between these two concepts found expression in the samurai phenomenon, a fusion of martial prowess and spiritual discipline. The samurai's body epitomized a duality—a manifestation of both patriotic vigor and a sacred, disciplined spirit—a blend that provided a unique foundation for the subsequent development of the discourse surrounding the national body over a fourteen-year period.³⁰⁶

Bodies in various roles like soldiers, parents, victims, enemies, and leaders are grouped based on moral and national standards, as Julia Bullock, a Japanese literature professor, explains this classification. She says that during wars, people must forget about their individual bodies, otherwise no one stands up, fight or follow the commands of the emperor or other leaders without personal desires or individual bodies getting in the way. The Japan point of view, the idea of a national body emerged by erasing individual bodies, giving it a strong political and national identity. Despite things like hunger, pain, wounds, and suicide being harmful to a person's physical body, they are seen as honorable for the national body.³⁰⁷

Military uniforms served as a practical method to transform individual bodies, *nikutai* (the carnal body) into a unified national body known as *kokutai* (the national body). When draped in identical clothing, these bodies adopt uniform identities, conforming to the desired image of those in power.³⁰⁸ Mythological concepts further strengthen these bodies, as seen in the case of suicide bombers who targeted American fleets, known as kamikaze. The term “kamikaze”

³⁰⁵ Ibid, 64.

³⁰⁶ Ibid, 64.

³⁰⁷ Slaymaker, Douglas. *The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction*. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. 2.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>.

³⁰⁸ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 65.

originates from the divine wind, a revered figure in Japanese mythology and One of the three most powerful myths of Japan as a nation.³⁰⁹

According to Ashkenazi, the implementation of kamikaze operations in the final months of World War Two wasn't a result of the Japanese army's weakness against the enemy. Japanese commanders were well aware that such tactics wouldn't defeat the formidable American forces.³¹⁰ Instead, the combination of the mythical name and the suicidal act aimed to convey a message beyond immediate military defeat. On another note, this approach was believed to potentially awaken war-related deities, *kami*, prompting their intervention and assistance.³¹¹ During the war, the individual's body seamlessly merged into the collective national body, reaching a saturation point with profound symbolic implications.

Conversely, *kami*, the deities associated with war reached a saturation point, embodying the concept that during times of war, an individual's body transformed into a manifestation of the national body. A body that seems to be devoid of flesh, skin, bones, and the concept of pain and suffering as it transitions into a societal symbol. Stripped of nerves and desires, it now serves a singular purpose—selfless dedication to the welfare of the country through sacrifice.

The essence of the national body, deeply intertwined with the cultural domains previously discussed, gained strength. It is crucial to recall that the synthesis of Buddhism and Shintoism, predating this era, envisioned an ideal body stripped of its physical significance, impervious to pain and suffering, driven by robust yet profoundly poetic desires. This moral and national perspective on the body during wartime extends beyond Japan and World War Two, manifesting as a common rejection of such attitudes in various conflicts throughout history.³¹²

Throughout the World War Two, the Japanese populace endured and persevered until the emperor's orders signaled the end. Men carried out suicide attacks under the emperor's command, and women participated in mass suicides, seemingly embracing the idea that the only path to spiritual salvation for their physical bodies was to conform to the societal roles dictated by the emperor's authority. Furthermore, the cultural foundations and infrastructures

³⁰⁹ Ashkenazi, Michael. *Handbook of Japanese Mythology*. *Handbooks of World Mythology*. Santa Barbara, Calif.: ABC-CLIO, 2003. 137.

³¹⁰ *Ibid*, 190.

³¹¹ *Ibid*, 95.

³¹² Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 66.

of Japan were so forceful that ordinary people found it relatively easy to accept these norms.

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It's noteworthy to consider the emperor's role in this context. The emperor remained an enigmatic figure. His body was regarded as symbolic—a representation of the child of God, to remain unseen. Even if Japan had emerged victorious in the war, the image and voice of Emperor Hirohito might still have remained concealed. Essentially, the Emperor's body constituted another aspect of the overarching symbolic body—a political entity enriched with sacred and mysterious components.³¹⁴

However, the devastating defeat of Japan at the conclusion of World War Two upended all established dynamics. The symbolic body, representing the child of God, lay defeated and humiliated. The Japanese people heard the emperor's voice as he conveyed the surrender declaration on the radio. Now, the once revered earthly body needed to traverse cities and villages, meeting war victims and issuing apologies. In a stark contrast, this diminutive figure with a troubled countenance had to stand alongside the towering and triumphant American General MacArthur, captured in a photograph intended to highlight the perceived weakness and smallness of the vanquished body on the world stage.³¹⁵

Let's observe General MacArthur commanding posture with his hands firmly on his waist, exuding strength, while the defeated emperor's hanging hands appear indecisive and idle. Additionally, compare the straight and unbent legs of the general with the slightly bent and unassertive posture of the Son of God. Despite both figures displaying a lack of overt emotion, the image of the American general next to the emperor is renowned and widely recognized in this picture. In essence, this portrayal captures the essence of humiliated bodies, drained of significance and authority, symbolizing the collapse of the body's meaning within the context of nationalism and nationality. It reflects the failure of myth, tradition, and history through those hanging hands and bent legs, contrasting the absence of these elements in the opposing figure.

If General MacArthur commanded the execution of the emperor, this humiliated body might have found itself in a more dignified state. Condemned to death, the emperor would have paid the ultimate price for the war's defeat. Such an execution could have perpetuated the

³¹³ Ibid, 66.

³¹⁴ Ibid, 67.

³¹⁵ Ibid, 67.

significance of the national body. The Kamikaze and other citizens who sacrificed themselves at the emperor's command had all contributed to shaping the narrative of the national body. The sacrifice for the country, even to the point of death, ensured that the national body remained indestructible. Beyond mere physical attributes like skin, flesh, and bones, it acquired symbolic meaning and became a lasting symbol. Through selfless death, this concept extended even beyond mortal existence.

Figure 1 Emperor Hirohito and General MacArthur meeting on the 29th of September, 1945, after Japan surrendered at the conclusion of World War Two.

Yet, in the aftermath of the war and during the initial years of occupation, everything crumbled. The war unleashed its most aggressive and evident assault on the bodies. Here I want to emphasize that in a culture like Japanese culture, the invasion and occupation of the body by war may carry more significance and be more open to interpretation than in other parts of the world, particularly in the West. In a society where there exists a direct link between the mind and the body, the degradation and collapse of the body could signify a corresponding decline in the mental state. It can be inferred that post-war and during the occupation, Japanese culture grappled with a challenging contradiction rooted in its originals. While ancient cultures

emphasized the value of maintaining control over the body, it was now in a state of ruin and disintegration—marking the pinnacle of this struggle and destruction.³¹⁶

2.9.1 The “Literature of the Flesh”

Following the conclusion of World War Two, the concept of “*nikutai bungaku* (肉体文学)” known as also termed “literature of the flesh,” surfaced as a reaction to the widespread dedication of soul and morality to the imperialistic national project experienced by Japanese citizens during the war, as outlined by Bullock.³¹⁷ This literary form aimed to break free from the constraints of both physical and emotional experiences. The inception of body literature can be traced back to 1947 with the launch of a Japanese magazine titled *nikutai*, which exclusively explored the sociology of the body.³¹⁸

Despite its brief publication span of only four issues, the magazine significantly influenced the proliferation of body-centric thinking and discourse among intellectuals. The manifesto in its inaugural issue emphatically declared, the editorial team of the *nikutai* journal, introduced at the beginning of this chapter, clearly expressed their intention to engage in a return to a more foundational aspect of Japanese culture. They aimed to reconnect with a physicality they believed had been overshadowed by excessively spiritualized and insubstantial wartime discussions. In their assessment, they asserted that nothing could be deemed reliable in the present circumstances.³¹⁹ According to them, the body serves as the starting point:

«We begin from the body [*nikutai*]; we do not start from ideals nor from matter. In the midst of all that is suspect in the current moment, the only existence that is not suspect is the here-and-now of the *nikutai*. We take this as the starting point for thinking.»³²⁰

The uncertainty emphasized in this manifesto is an undeniable and unavoidable reality in the post-World War Two. Everything lay in ruins. From grand beliefs like the divine status of the emperor to the perceived invincibility of the Japanese in warfare and the presumed autonomy

³¹⁶ Ibid, 71.

³¹⁷ Bullock, Julia C. *The Other Women’s Lib: Gender and Body in Japanese Women’s Fiction*. Honolulu: University of Hawai’i Press, 2010. 34.

³¹⁸ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 74.

³¹⁹ Slaymaker, Douglas. *The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction*. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. 17.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>.

³²⁰ Ibid, 18.

of Japanese men, all convictions were called into question. In the middle of this upheaval, the manifesto makes it evident that each individual's body emerged as the sole possession and the only connection to an undeniable reality.

The widespread deprivation, poverty, and destruction in the post-war world led to the prevalence of basic bodily needs such as hunger and cold. In these circumstances, the bodies, so to speak, became the voice where neither reason, myth, nor spiritual discourses could offer a redemptive narrative. During the war, particularly for men, bodies were strictly under command, necessitating the suppression of their voices. However, in the aftermath of the war and during the occupation, there arose a clamor from hunger-stricken and ailing bodies, predominantly voiced in literature, especially by men.³²¹

In the history of Japanese art and literature, it appears to be the first instance where the carnal body—composed of muscles, blood, flesh, skin, and desires—has gained recognition. This recognition may stem from the aftermath of the war when the concept of the national body faded into the shadows of defeat, revealing the physical body's afflictions: suppressed desires, wounds, pains, and disabilities. This stark comparison emerged between the sufferings of Japanese bodies and the robust, healthy, and towering conquerors. It signified a substantial transformation reflecting the values of militarism and traditional beliefs in both nations. The defeat in the Second World War marked not just the end of a continued conflict for Japan but also the disintegration of the entire tradition and ritual approach toward humanity in a broader sense and the body in a specific sense.³²²

Despite the initial manifestos aiming to liberate *nikutai* from national, local, or individual expectations and striving for identity freedom by releasing bodies from any form of control, particularly a departure from the culture of uniform clothing,³²³ the subsequent development of body literature as a genre seems to predominantly focus on the sexual body. It tends to overlook other facets of *nikutai*, such as the wounds, diseases, and sufferings endured by Japanese bodies during and after the war. Additionally, it's noteworthy that one of the

³²¹ Ibid, 22.

³²² Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 75.

³²³ Slaymaker, Douglas. The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. 17. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>.

occupiers' objectives was women's freedom, evident in the initial and straightforward steps toward sexual and physical liberation.³²⁴

However, the manner in which mediums like literature and cinema approach these freedoms—whether for the advancement of women's rights or to cater to men's satisfaction—gives rise to various perspectives, a topic I will delve into in Chapter Three within the feminist section.

In this chapter, our exploration into the “history of the body” has led us to perceive the body as a battlefield, studying the intricate interplay between the disintegration of the body and mind. Delving into the history of the body in Japan through the lenses of mythology, language (socio-linguistic approaches), cultural elements, and historical contexts, we aimed to unravel the cultural construction of identity and the societal pressures that shape individual experiences.

This comprehensive inquiry lays the basis for addressing the central question of our thesis: how the character of Mima in the *Perfect Blue* anime undergoes a profound transformation, and how it is intricately linked to deeply ingrained cultural ideals surrounding the sanctity of the body in Japan. By employing constructivist analytical tools, we gain a better understanding of why the discursive “conditions of possibility” for Mima make her more susceptible to schizophrenia after the rape scene. Our study emphasized the influential role of beliefs, standards, identities, language, and other discursive practices as social structures that both constrain and facilitate subject' choices.

By bringing these aspects to light, we aim to substantiate the claim made in the introduction, challenging the notion that the oscillation between reality and ideas, roles and expectations, and determinism and free will are mere natural fluctuations. Instead, we argue that Japan's unique socio-cultural landscape distinguishes *Perfect Blue* and Mima's experiences from other films in this genre, shedding light on the ongoing societal pressures and conflicts woven into the fabric of Japanese life.

In the upcoming chapter, we embark on a multifaceted exploration to unravel the central question of our thesis through the lenses of three distinct layers: semiology of memory, cinema, and feminism. We delve into the profound ways in which collective memory on the body, in the context of Japan, is both preserved and dynamically reshaped, reinforcing the centrality of the body in societal narratives. Acknowledging the influential role of media representations,

³²⁴ Ibid, 16.

specifically cinema, our investigation extends into the realm of how these representations intricately mold and contribute to the collective memory of societies.

By examining the interplay between semiotics and cinematic narratives, we aim to offer a comprehensive understanding of memory construction and reconstruction. As we transition to a feminist perspective, our exploration deepens to comprehensively analyze the social pressures on the gendered body, focusing on women's body. This multifaceted approach promises to illuminate the intricate connections between memory, cinema, and feminism in shaping perceptions of the body within broader social contexts.

Therefore, the question that the next chapter seeks to address is how the previously discussed concept of "the history of the body", as explored in Chapter Two, is reinforced through the construction of collective memory, particularly within the realm of cinema. Additionally, the chapter aims to investigate the heightened impact of these dynamics on women's bodies, delving into the intersectionality of memory, gender, and cinematic representation. By examining the interplay between the history of the body, collective memory, and cinema, we aim to elucidate the ways in which societal perceptions and expectations are shaped, with a specific focus on the experiences of women.

Chapter Three

Shaping Collective Memory and Identity

“Societies have always relied on memory in order to preserve their own identity.”

Umberto Eco (2015)³²⁵

3.1 Collective Memory and Identity

«As human, when we say “I”, we mean our memory. Memory is soul. If somebody loses his memory he becomes like a plant and he hasn’t got a soul anymore. Even for a believer, hell has no meaning without memory. Punishment lies in constantly remembering of the sin committed. Therefore, we are our own memory and shared memories mean common identity. »³²⁶

Memory studies delves into the recesses of our collective and individual recollections, offering insights into the stories we tell ourselves and the worlds we construct. Memories shape us. Memories aren’t just about remembering events; what memory captures, processes, and expresses are signs, not mere objects. memory, whether individual or collective, is fundamentally a semiotic phenomenon intricately linked with culture.³²⁷ Consequently, we can say individual memory is social, and the social memory is shared through communication, institutions, media, relations, interaction.

Memory is selective. We cancel or forget things we didn’t like. And we keep the memory of things we liked but in a distorted way. Semantic memory is what we know about the world, while incidental memory is what we learn from personal experience.³²⁸ Memory studies, within a semiotic framework, reveals the signs and symbols that carry and transmit memories, effectively weaving the narrative threads of our existence. Memory studies is a dynamic field of inquiry, holds a profound significance in unraveling the intricate tapestry of human identity and society.³²⁹

³²⁵ Eco, Umberto. "Sobre la memoria." Directed by Davide Ferrario. Three-part conversation, Bienal de Venecia, 2015. <https://vimeo.com/156102819>

³²⁶ Ibid.

³²⁷ Tamm, Marek, ed. Juri Lotman - Culture, Memory and History: Essays in Cultural Semiotics. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019. 9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14710-5>.

³²⁸ Eco, Umberto. "Sobre la memoria." Directed by Davide Ferrario. Three-part conversation, Bienal de Venecia, 2015. <https://vimeo.com/156102819>

³²⁹ Halbwachs, Maurice, Lewis A. Coser. On Collective Memory. The Heritage of Sociology. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 1992.

Semiotics, the study of signs and symbols, emerges as a potent lens through which we interpret and analyze the vast reservoir of human memory. It allows us to navigate the complex landscapes of collective memory, shedding light on the mechanisms through which societies remember, forget, and negotiate their pasts.³³⁰ Semiotics unveils the intricate dance between symbols, signs, and narratives that construct memory, echoing Lotman's notion of the semiosphere, where cultural communication and memory exchange transpire.³³¹

In the previous chapter we talked about how the sanctity of “body” in Japan is reinforced through different layers including cultural elements. In the realm of culture, memory serves as a dynamic force, functioning both to preserve existing information and to generate new texts. It is crucial to recognize that memory is not merely a passive repository for culture; rather, it plays an integral role in the mechanism responsible for generating cultural texts. These texts encompass a broad spectrum of cultural units, including but not limited to books, novels, architecture, paintings, objects, as well as various practices and behaviors.³³² Therefore, common memory and cultural texts are connected through their preservation.³³³

«From the point of view of semiotics, culture represents collective intelligence and collective memory, that is, a supra-individual mechanism for preserving and transmitting messages (texts) and for creating new ones. In this sense, the field of culture can be defined as a space of shared memory, within which certain common texts are preserved and actualized. Moreover, their actualization occurs within the bounds of a certain conceptual invariant, which allows us to say that a text in the context of a new age preserves its identity to itself in the face of various interpretations. »³³⁴

A dichotomy exists within memory's function, distinguishing between informative memory, focused on retaining information, and creative memory, dedicated to the generation of new and innovative cultural elements. If we think of culture as memory, it means culture is like a record

³³⁰ Chandler, Daniel. 2002. "Semiotics for Beginners." Retrieved from <http://visual-memory.co.uk/daniel/Documents/S4B/>.

³³¹ Lotman, Yuri M. *Universe of the Mind: A Semiotic Theory of Culture*, translated by Ann Shukman, introduction by Umberto Eco. I.B. Tauris & Co. Ltd, 1990.

³³² Tamm, Marek, ed. *Juri Lotman - Culture, Memory and History: Essays in Cultural Semiotics*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019. 9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14710-5>.

³³³ Eco, Umberto. "Sobre la memoria." Directed by Davide Ferrario. Three-part conversation, *Bienal de Venecia*, 2015. <https://vimeo.com/156102819>

³³⁴ Tamm, Marek, ed. *Juri Lotman - Culture, Memory and History: Essays in Cultural Semiotics*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019. 133. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14710-5>.

of what society has made and gone through. So, memory is like a collection of information that isn't passed down through our genes. But it is not just preservation; memory also it is also production of new information.³³⁵

Here an important question raises; does memory record everything? The answer is no, there's something called oblivion. In Lotman's view, oblivion has two sides: filtering and destruction.³³⁶ For instance, there is a static way to consider the past which is typical of reactionary groups. They "repossess" what is suitable for them. Revolutionary group, instead try to erase memory. «Forget everything that was before, let's start from scratch. »³³⁷

In a similar disposition, the three functions of invented traditions come into play. Firstly, they contribute to the establishment of social cohesion, acting as a symbolic framework that supports and defines social identities. Secondly, these traditions serve to legitimize authority, power, and the various institutions that govern a community. Lastly, invented traditions actively participate in the shaping of belief systems, values, and socially accepted behaviors, contributing to the collective ethos of a given society. In essence, they are dynamic elements that weave through the fabric of social life, shaping identity, authority, and cultural norms.³³⁸

Therefore, memory is a subjective and selective process intricately linked to the construction of identities. This reconstructive nature of memory allows individuals and social groups to shape their narratives according to their present symbolic needs. Social groups, in particular, actively engage in producing a past that aligns with their identity, turning memory into a dynamic and responsive process. The constant reconstruction of memory underscores its fluid nature, perpetually reshaped by the contemporary context.

A crucial aspect in this interplay is the emphasis on language, as it plays a central role in collective memory. Language not only serves as a vehicle for conveying memories but also acts as a fundamental tool in the construction processes. The cohesion of a collectivity relies on the shared language that binds its members and shapes the collective memory, highlighting

³³⁵ Ibid, 134.

³³⁶ Lotman, Yuri, Boris Uspenskij, and Vitaly Mihaychuk. "On the Semiotic Mechanism of Culture." *New Literary History* 9, no. 2 (Winter 1978): 211-232, in *Soviet Semiotics and Criticism: An Anthology*.

³³⁷ Eco, Umberto. "Sobre la memoria." Directed by Davide Ferrario. Three-part conversation, *Bienal de Venecia*, 2015. <https://vimeo.com/156102819>

³³⁸ Hobsbawm, Eric, and Terence Ranger, eds. *The Invention of Tradition*. Cambridge University Press, 2012. Online edition, July 2014. Online ISBN: 9781107295636. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107295636>.

the intricate relationship between language and the way memories are formed and communicated.³³⁹

This dynamic approach to the past demonstrates the multifaceted role of constructed collective memory, highlighting their contribution to fostering social cohesion, legitimizing authority, and actively shaping belief systems and cultural norms within a society. One way in which the constructed collective memory reinforces itself is through media. Media representations play a crucial role in shaping collective memory. In the realm of cinema, where visual narratives blend with human memory, a profound and intricate interplay unfolds—a symphony of signs, symbols, and narratives that encapsulate the semiotics of memory.³⁴⁰

At its core, the semiotics of memory navigates the realm of signs and symbols to unravel the intricate codes that govern the construction of memory in its manifold forms.³⁴¹ Within the cinematic canvas, this journey gains new dimensions, as the visual medium itself becomes a potent semiotic tool.³⁴²

As Lotman suggests, memory, or the act of remembering, is an intricate reconstructive process, a process of selection and translation, wherein memories are encoded, reimagined, and disseminated. The outcome of this process takes on various embodiments, from texts, practices, spaces, to objects and, in the context of our exploration, films. These cinematic narratives, while diverse in form and content, all serve as embodiments of narratives.³⁴³

In this section, I embark on a cinematic journey to explore the essence of the remembrance of the concept of the body in Japan. I will investigate how the body is represented, communicated, interpreted, and transmitted within the medium of film, aiming to illustrate the construction of collective memory around the concept of the body. The choice of cinema as the medium is motivated by its unique ability to amplify the voices of these bodies. Despite facing audits and

³³⁹ Halbwachs, Maurice, Lewis A. Coser. *On Collective Memory. The Heritage of Sociology.* Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 1992.

³⁴⁰ Chandler, Daniel. 2002. "Semiotics for Beginners." Retrieved from <http://visual-memory.co.uk/daniel/Documents/S4B/>.

³⁴¹ Ibid.

³⁴² Edgerton, Gary R., and Peter C. Rollins, eds. *Television Histories: Shaping Collective Memory in the Media Age.* Lexington, Ky: University Press of Kentucky, 2001.

³⁴³ Lotman, Yuri, Boris Uspenskij, and Vitaly Mihaychuk. "On the Semiotic Mechanism of Culture." *New Literary History* 9, no. 2 (Winter 1978): 211-232, in *Soviet Semiotics and Criticism: An Anthology.*

economic challenges, post-war cinema in Japan witnessed a remarkable and unprecedented surge, entering a golden period that garnered global attention.³⁴⁴

3.2 Bodies on the Screen

Cinema employs a ceremonial historical narrative to create versions of collective memory and identity that it shares with its audiences. As Eric Hobsbawm explains, the history that becomes ingrained in the knowledge or ideology of a nation-state or movement isn't solely what's preserved in popular memory. Instead, it is a curated selection that is written, depicted, popularized, and institutionalized by those tasked with these functions.³⁴⁵

Japanese cinema underwent two golden periods before the onset of occupation and the influence of Westernization had fully taken hold, particularly flourishing during the era of silent cinema. Hence, its rebirth after the devastation of war was not an unexpected phenomenon. There could be a reason that during the second year of occupation, one hundred and sixty films were produced. This rush could be interpreted as a collaborative effort between the occupiers and Japanese filmmakers to swiftly transition from the wartime atmosphere and usher in a new era.³⁴⁶

Both victorious and defeated factions saw cinema as an escape from the ravages of war and destruction. Simultaneously, the audience eagerly welcomed the revival of the Japanese cinema industry for countless reasons, including the fundamental need for entertainment. However, the ultimate goals of Japanese invaders and filmmakers during the cinematic boom differed significantly from the wartime values that were previously emphasized. Pre-war films were full of extreme patriotism bodies while post-war, the situation changed abruptly as American occupiers imposed new values on cinema, aiming to use it as a tool for promoting democracy, women's freedom, criticizing feudal society, and condemning militarism.³⁴⁷

However, in their effort to alter the intellectual tone of films, the occupiers implemented strict censorship against early occupation films that displayed excessive patriotic sentiments. Clear

³⁴⁴ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 17.

³⁴⁵ Edgerton, Gary R., and Peter C. Rollins, eds. *Television Histories: Shaping Collective Memory in the Media Age*. Lexington, Ky: University Press of Kentucky, 2001. 227.

³⁴⁶ MacDonald, Keiko I. *Reading a Japanese Film: Cinema in Context*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2006. 6.

³⁴⁷ Sato, Tadao. *Kenji Mizoguchi and the Art of Japanese Cinema*. Translated by Brij Tankha. Edited by Aruna Vasudev and Latika Padgaonkar. Oxford, New York: Berg, 2008. 88-89.

restrictions were identified and enforced, leading to the reevaluation of pre-war literary or film works and the prevention of any content provoking military pride. Even the samurai genre was banned, and any reference to occupier decision-making over the Japanese government was prohibited. Discussion about the effects of the atomic bomb was also off-limits, and until 1946, no film or research could address atomic bomb-related issues.³⁴⁸

In Lotman's conceptualization, the phenomenon of oblivion unfolds with dual facets: filtering and destruction. This framework aligns with the transitional nature of memory, as discussed in the previous section. Just as Lotman outlines that memory is not a passive recorder but a dynamic process involving filtering and destruction, the narrative on Japanese cinema reveals a transformative journey post-World War Two.³⁴⁹

The Japanese cinema serves as an illustration of how the collective memory, represented by the cinematic narrative, undergoes a process of filtering and destruction. The shift from wartime to post-war values and narratives, as imposed by American occupiers, represents a filtering of extreme patriotic sentiments and the destruction of previous cinematic conventions dominated by wartime values.³⁵⁰

The comparison of pre-war and post-war cinema in Japan reflects the ongoing process of shaping collective memory—a dynamic interplay of selection, reinterpretation, and reconstruction. Moreover, the enforced censorship on specific topics, such as the atomic bomb and samurai genre, exemplifies how memory, both individual and collective, is subject to deliberate filtering and destruction to fit the prevailing narrative and societal context. This dynamic approach to memory aligns with Lotman's perspective and reinforces the idea that memory, including its cinematic manifestation, is a constantly evolving construct influenced by various factors, including societal changes and external impositions.³⁵¹

With this thorough examination, the representation of bodies in cinema undergoes transformative shifts. It reflects the outline of two bodies. The elimination of the samurai body, which is a big part of Japan's history and embodying Japanese masculinity, symbolizes more than just the removal of a genre. It creates a cultural void, distancing Japanese men from their

³⁴⁸ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 80.

³⁴⁹ Lotman, Yuri, Boris Uspenskij, and Vitaly Mihaychuk. "On the Semiotic Mechanism of Culture." *New Literary History* 9, no. 2 (Winter 1978): 211-232, in *Soviet Semiotics and Criticism: An Anthology*.

³⁵⁰ *Ibid.*

³⁵¹ *Ibid.*

bodies and revealing the masculinity of the defeated, wounded, and sick body— the post-war body. However, in the initial post-war years, such representations were denied public discourse in mass media to avoid provocative reminders of past war events and potential conflicts towards occupiers. The observation on male bodies was intense, making sure to keep them anonymous. The observation on male bodies reflects the occupiers' attempt to neutralize any reminders of the past war, imposing an oblivion on certain narratives.³⁵²

In contrast, women's bodies, associated with purity, mystery, and sexuality, could still maintain their significance without causing discomfort to the occupiers, thereby avoiding oblivion. The occupiers stuck to a practical approach favoring masculine values, closely overseeing how male bodies were represented to keep them anonymous. That's why the bodies of samurai and victims were condemned to a profound silence. This reflects an effort to maintain control over the narrative and impose an oblivion on certain representations. It is essential to note that the phenomenon of portrayal of women's bodies in post-war cinema, is not solely a result of the occupiers' preferences; rather, it has deeper origins intricately integrated into the post-war cultural setting.³⁵³

The following section studies the feminist perspective within the realm of Japanese cinema post-occupation, unraveling the nuanced dynamics surrounding the cinematic portrayal of women's bodies, their agency, and the broader implications for gender roles and societal expectations.

3.3 Empowerment or Objectification: Feminist Critique of Cinematic Representations

“It takes a feminist to know a misogynist, and vice versa.”

(Susan Gubar 1994)

Within the realm of Japanese cinema post-occupation, multifaceted reasons behind the role of women in cinema during this transformative period is clarified; Firstly, the impact of Hollywood cinema plays a significant role, aiming to give visual pleasure to male viewers through the act of gaze. Secondly, female actresses in this era played a crucial role in

³⁵² Richie, Donald. *Japanese Cinema: Film Style and National Character*. New York: Anchor Books, 1971. 42.

³⁵³ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. 72. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> .

embodying the newfound freedom of women in the post-war period. Furthermore, a third aspect highlights the significance assigned to vulnerability of Japanese men.³⁵⁴

In my view, the first two reasons concerning female actresses and others play a pivotal role in understanding the third reason. In times of war, men endure or conquest more prominently than women. War, with its specific and distinct nature, is traditionally seen as a man's domain, while women in cities and villages behind the front lines bear the substantial impact of war, supporting soldiers without directly engaging in combat. Despite sharing in the honor of victory, women are not perceived as equals in the humiliation of defeat. In 1945, Japanese men returned home from a war they had little chance of winning. The emperor, considered trustworthy as a deity, suffered not only defeat but also humiliation.³⁵⁵

This triple humiliation for Japanese men resulted from, first, their defeat in the war, second, the collapse of the revered imperial figure, and third, the occupation of their land by imposing American soldiers. Forced into becoming a democratic society, this transformation only weakened the historical role of men, who, throughout Japanese tradition, were regarded as the primary rulers of land and water. In contrast, Germany, also defeated in World War II, did not experience the same level of public disgrace as Emperor Hirohito did in Japan. The apparent contrast between the defeated Germans and the victorious Americans was not as pronounced in Japan.³⁵⁶

Given this situation, how could cinema address and rectify the humiliation and weakening of men in its narrative depths, protected from the hands of invaders and cultural tourists?

One approach involves the objectification and sexualization of women's bodies. These demands weakening the sacred and symbolic significance traditionally associated with the women's body, reducing it to a mere physical entity.³⁵⁷ The act of sexualization, interpreted as a representation of freedom, brings gender significance to the portrayal of the body. In exploring these aspects, it prompts reflection on how this approach aligns with both a male-centric perspective and feminist viewpoint.

³⁵⁴ Izbicki, Joanna. *The Shape of Freedom: The Female Body in Post-Surrender Japanese Cinema*, *US-Japan Women's Journal*, No. 12. Special Issue Gender and Imperialism, 1997. 177.

³⁵⁵ Samini, Naghmeh. *Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema*. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 85.

³⁵⁶ *Ibid*, 85.

³⁵⁷ *Ibid*, 72.

On one side, the perceived vulnerability of the female body in cinema in contrast to male dominance could offer a form of comfort. Despite experiencing humiliation on multiple fronts, men found a realm where they could perceive themselves as the stronger gender, conveying a sense of satisfaction. The fragile and abandoned bodies could face a potential oblivion. This dual nature had the potential to provide comfort to men, easing their feelings of weakness while finding joy in the pleasure of admiring a beautiful woman. Interpreted in this light, the objectified bodies of women in cinema served as a double-edged sword – signifying women's liberty after the occupation, at the same time, reflecting men's desire to uphold their singular position of power in society. Simultaneously, it acted as a means to escape the explicit realities of defense and occupation.³⁵⁸

In simpler terms, the sexualized and liberated representations of women's bodies operated as symbolic triggers of trauma from the occupation era, carrying a dual identity: emancipation from the militaristic historical narrative and trapped in the harsh realities of occupation and defeat. The term "trauma of the occupation period" encapsulates the complex interplay of factors discussed so far, stemming from deep wounds and significant failures within the Japanese collective psyche. These include the fall of the emperor, the devastation shaped by the war, the exclusive prohibition on showcasing traditional women's body, the subsequent fear among men of potential female dominance. The entry of these themes into the formal realm of cinematic representation, marking a transformative period of experiences and interpretations.³⁵⁹

Additionally, a significant aspect of postwar male authors' engagement with the body, emphasizing a focus on "living by the body" as a coping mechanism during the Occupation. However, a critical observation reveals that the body referred to is not that of the male authors themselves but rather that of a woman. These narratives depict a desire for male protagonists to transcend not through their own bodily pleasures and experiences but rather through the transcendence of the female body.³⁶⁰

The use of the female body as a conduit for the male protagonists' escape from the corporeal realm allows them to project onto women various negative qualities associated with the physical—such as vulnerability, violation of bodily boundaries through sexual submission, and

³⁵⁸ Ibid, 86.

³⁵⁹ Ibid, 86.

³⁶⁰ Bullock, Julia C. *The Other Women's Lib: Gender and Body in Japanese Women's Fiction*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2010. 35.

acquiescence to power structures. This projection serves to protect the fragile male sense of agency from perceived threats, reinforcing the notion that objectifying and sexualizing women's bodies may function as a strategy for men to reclaim a sense of control and empowerment.³⁶¹

Hence, recovering the weakened pride of masculinity is more compatible than trying to emancipate the female body. Laura Mulvey, in her article titled “*Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema*” (1975), considers this concern contextual and convincingly argues that, despite the efforts of alternative cinema to declare itself and address the liberation of the female body, it reinforces the patriarchal structure, offering men a gratifying sense of dominance. Feminist film theorists have employed the concept of scopic dynamics to understand the intricate interplay among power, gender, and film spectatorship.³⁶²

Scopic dynamics refer to the relationships and power dynamics involved in the act of looking or visual perception, particularly in the context of film and visual media. In feminist film theory, the term is often used to analyze how gender and power are implicated in the act of viewing and being viewed, exploring how the gaze is constructed and how it influences the representation of gender in cinematic narratives. The concept is closely associated with Laura Mulvey’s influential essay “*Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema*,” where she discusses the ways in which traditional Hollywood cinema structures the visual experience and the implications of the male gaze.³⁶³

Laura Mulvey’s seminal work was the first to critically examine how classical cinema shapes the female body as an object of the masculine gaze. In her essay, she asserts that the spectator finds pleasure in the morbid control and mastery of the onscreen female object, essentially possessing her through identification with the hero of the narrative.³⁶⁴ Similar to Foucault’s theory of panopticism—defined as a system of investigation and control wherein the constant potential for observation induces self-discipline and conformity in individuals within a society—there is an implicit power differential present between the subject and object of the gaze, explicitly coded in gendered terms in Mulvey’s theory.³⁶⁵

³⁶¹ Ibid, 36.

³⁶² Mulvey Laura. n.d. *Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema*, 1975.

³⁶³ Ibid.

³⁶⁴ Ibid.

³⁶⁵ Bullock, Julia C. *The Other Women’s Lib: Gender and Body in Japanese Women’s Fiction*. Honolulu: University of Hawai’i Press, 2010. 54.

Men hold the gaze, while women are subjected to it. In a subsequent expansion of Mulvey's theory, she argues that filmic techniques work so effectively to construct the viewer's gaze as masculine that, for female viewers to derive visual pleasure, they must subconsciously adopt a masculine subject position concerning the women onscreen.³⁶⁶ In association with the preceding argument, Bullock's perspective suggests an interconnection between Japanese traditional patriarchy and American capitalism within the discourse on the body, revealing a shared narrative: the female body's subjectivity.³⁶⁷

The female body's subjectivity was considered essential for the wealth of the capitalist market, while patriarchy sought this body to cure post-war humiliation and wounds. In addition to the earlier discussion on sexual objectification of women's body, an alternative perspective reinforced during the post-war period in cinema was portraying women as fulfilling the roles of "good wives and wise mothers," reflecting an attitude of contribution to the nation's reconstruction.³⁶⁸

However, during the post war occupation, Chizuko Ueno contends that women, despite being urged to engage in social work beyond the domestic sphere in the post-occupation era, faced a dual burden post-war, as they continued to be dominated by both men in their familial relationships and by their employers.³⁶⁹

Chizuko Ueno expressed criticism regarding this emerging model of the working wife and mother, stating:

«This "new sex-role division" is double-edged for women: it has affected the traditional power relationship between husbands and wives, but women have ended up being doubly exploited by men, both at home and at the workplace. As both part-time workers and housewives, women must be content to be "second-class citizens," while feeling guilty for being neither sufficient workers nor perfect mothers-wives. In short, "dual-role" has not solved the "women problem." It is

³⁶⁶ Mulvey Laura. n.d. *Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema*, 1975.

³⁶⁷ Bullock, Julia C. *The Other Women's Lib: Gender and Body in Japanese Women's Fiction*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2010. 155.

³⁶⁸ *Ibid*, 18.

³⁶⁹ *Ibid*, 155.

simply a new compromise between capitalism and patriarchy in the developed stage of capitalism. »³⁷⁰

Essentially, the underlying and deep-rooted cultural norms persisted, with superficial surface-level changes influenced by the occupiers.

The discourse within cinema follows to what Foucault termed the “repressive hypothesis,” When people loudly claim they are suppressing or restricting something, it raises questions about why they believe such suppression is necessary. In this cinematic context, there's a noticeable power structure built on repression, and it's maintained through a kind of protest-oriented discourse. The idea of freedom in the cinema platform looks a lot like the problems they are criticizing in society. It focuses on a specific kind of freedom that relies on a sexualized woman's body seen as an object, found by a powerful male character. Slaymaker suggests that it might be driven by men' feelings of being pushed to the sidelines, especially their worries, about losing their sense of manliness during a time of crisis after a loss and occupation.³⁷¹

In the fictional world analyzed here, a woman's body is portrayed as an object, a tool used through sexual means by male characters to achieve various goals such as communal utopia, connection with others, guidance to another level of existence, or freedom from current oppressions. The concept of “liberation from the body by the body,” as proposed by Tamura primarily translates into the liberation of male bodies (rather than all bodies as assumed) through, with, or from a woman's body. Consequently, the narrative does not reimagine bodies; instead, it centers on the interactions between a strong, angular man and a sexually available woman.³⁷²

Sexual activity is depicted as a form of communion that promises to alleviate profound loneliness. This portrayal of the body is gendered in specific ways that offer insights into the postwar context. Moreover, the understanding of individual identity rooted in the body is not critically examined. The goal of bodily liberation is intertwined with a desire for self-determination and freedom from constraints, including those imposed by a militarized society. While the narrative often depicts liberation from societal restrictions, there is also a persistent

³⁷⁰ Ueno, Chizuko. "The Japanese Women's Movement: The Counter-Values to Industrialism." In *The Japanese Trajectory: Modernization and Beyond*, edited by Gavan McCormack and Yoshio Sugimoto, Cambridge and New York: Cambridge University Press, 1988. 177–178.

³⁷¹ Slaymaker, Douglas. *The Body in Postwar Japanese Fiction*. 0 ed. London; Routledge, 2004. 14.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203300145>.

³⁷² *Ibid*, 14

desire to be free from any demands, whether national, domestic, or individual. Notably, the figure representing the liberation from these constraints is not a domestic woman but sex workers.³⁷³

The complex relationship between cinema and women's body, within a global context of censorship of other bodies, shows the challenge of dealing with the forgetfulness imposed by external forces. We already discussed that the promotion of women's freedom as a key occupier value led to a more liberal display of female bodies in cinema through feminist critique approach. However, it's also Important to be noted that as with global instances of censorship, this interaction also resulted in nuanced and debatable syntheses.

After the occupation, the embrace of “oriental nothingness” and the promotion of national Zen Buddhism, reveal attempts to counteract the cultural oblivion and redefine Japanese identity and bodies.³⁷⁴ Therefore, despite the imposed emancipation of female bodies, the history of the body resurfaces to redefine Japan identity and bodies in its sanctity. In the upcoming section, we will revisit the central question of the thesis, exploring the film "Perfect Blue" in light of the discussed themes and concepts in this chapter.

3.4 Perfect Blue: Complete Metamorphosis

“Correct memory is rather the exception than the rule.”

Stoffels (2013)

Shifting our focus to “Perfect Blue,” we employ the concept of “Collective Memory” as explained by scholars such as Maurice Halbwachs. The film we examine display the fundamental role that collective memory plays in shaping not only individuals but entire communities. This concept allows us to study the communal aspects of memory within the film.³⁷⁵ We delve into how the protagonist's experience is entangled with the collective memory of her fans and society at large.³⁷⁶

³⁷³ Ibid, 14.

³⁷⁴ Kato, Etsuko. *The Tea Ceremony and Women's Empowerment in Modern Japan: Bodies Re-Presenting the Past*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2004. 74. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203748879> .

³⁷⁵ Halbwachs, Maurice, Lewis A. Coser. *On Collective Memory*. The Heritage of Sociology. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 1992.

³⁷⁶ Satoshi Kon, “Perfect Blue”, 1997.

Through the lens of “Imagined Communities,” we explore how the shared language, narration and symbols depicted in “Perfect Blue” shape not only individual identities but also contribute to the construction of broader social narratives. It is within this collective consciousness that societies forge their identities and understand their pasts. The concept of an “imagined community” was introduced by political scientist Benedict Anderson in his influential book *“Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism”* (1983).³⁷⁷

The term refers to the idea that communities are socially constructed entities, and the sense of belonging to a community is not based on direct, personal interactions with all its members, but rather on a shared and imagined connection. According to Anderson, a community is “imagined” because the individuals within it will likely never know or meet the vast majority of their fellow people. Despite this lack of direct personal connection, people share a mental image or idea of their community.³⁷⁸

This mental image is not necessarily based on reality, but it is a product of the collective imagination and a sense of belonging to a larger entity. The imagined community is not defined by its truth or falsity but by the way in which it is imagined. It involves a shared perception and consciousness among its members. The power of this imagined connection can be so strong that individuals may be willing to sacrifice their lives for it.³⁷⁹

In essence, this section begins on a cinematic odyssey through the semiotics of memory, unraveling the intricate dance between signs, symbols, and narratives that define our understanding of the past. Through the lens of perfect blue, we attempt to decode how memory, in its various forms and functions, finds its semiotic expression in the world of cinema. By examining individual, collective, and political memory, we seek to shed light on the enduring and transformative power of the cinematic medium in shaping the stories we tell ourselves about who we are and where we come from.

In the previous section we discussed how media representations play a crucial role in shaping collective memory. Perfect Blue portrays how television, magazines, and the internet influence and perpetuate certain narratives and memories about and also on the protagonist. The semiotics of media representations highlight the power of these symbols in constructing and

³⁷⁷ Anderson, Benedict R. O’G. *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. Revised edition. London New York: Verso, 2016. 16.

³⁷⁸ *Ibid*, 17.

³⁷⁹ *Ibid*, 18.

disseminating collective memory. The film delves into the darker side of collective memory through fan obsession. The semiotics of fan behavior and the creation of collective narration around the protagonist, Mima, illustrate how memory can become a consuming force, blurring the boundaries between individual and collective recollections.³⁸⁰

“Perfect Blue” not only offers a glimpse into the collective memory of fan communities but also serves as a historical embodiment of the evolution of language and societal values. Fans, as members of these communities, collectively craft and preserve their distinctive interpretation of Mima's identity and history, similar to Benedict Anderson's notion of “Imagined Communities.”

This phenomenon extends beyond mere fandom; it reflects how language and narratives have evolved over time, shaping collective memory. Through the evolution of terminology, symbols, and narratives, fan culture becomes a living testament to how language adapts and reflects shifting societal values.³⁸¹ This phenomenon showcases the intricate relationship between language, collective memory, and historical transformation within the context of pop culture fandom.

In Satoshi Kon's “Perfect Blue,” the intricate interplay between the protagonist Mima Kirigoe's personal experiences and the collective memory of her fans and society at large is artfully explored through the lenses of imagined community and collective memory. As a former pop idol transitioning into the realm of acting, Mima embodies a figure within an imagined community, where fans construct a shared mental image of her persona. This collective imagination often remains divorced from Mima's authentic self, encapsulating an idealized version perpetuated by media and public perception.³⁸²

The film skillfully portrays the challenges Mima faces as she navigates her evolving career, disrupting the established narrative woven by the collective memory of her fans. The fervent attachment to the pop idol persona clashes with Mima's evolving identity, introducing a palpable tension between the constructed image and the unfolding reality. The cinematic narrative not only unfolds the external pressures Mima faces but also delves into her internal struggles as she grapples with the expectations placed upon her. The blurring of reality and

³⁸⁰ Satoshi Kon, “Perfect Blue”, 1997.

³⁸¹ Anderson, Benedict R. O’G. *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. Revised edition. London New York: Verso, 2016.

³⁸² Satoshi Kon, “Perfect Blue”, 1997.

fantasy, intensified by Mima's immersion in acting rape scene, further complicates the boundaries between her actual identity and the characters she portrays, and it becomes increasingly ambiguous.³⁸³

This deliberate blurring adds complexity to the imagined community surrounding her. "Perfect Blue" delves into the consequences of media representation and the transformative power of narrative. It intricately questions the manipulability of truth in the public eye and explores the psychological toll on individuals entangled in the complex web of personal experience, societal expectations, and the imagined communities that surround them. The expectations embedded in the body throughout history, as examined in the second chapter, highlight the enduring influence of historical narratives on our physical selves. Through Mima's journey, the film invites observation on the fragility of body, and therefore mind.³⁸⁴

In "Perfect Blue," the exploration of the intricate dance between signs, symbols, and narratives takes center stage, providing a compelling lens through which to analyze how memory, in its diverse forms and functions, finds its semiotic expression in the realm of cinema. The film masterfully weaves a narrative that delves into the complexities of individual, collective, and political memory, shedding light on the enduring and transformative power of the cinematic medium in shaping the stories that define our understanding of the past.³⁸⁵

On an individual level, the protagonist Mima Kirigoe's journey becomes an image for the semiotic expression of memory. As she navigates the challenges of her evolving career and grapples with the blurred lines between reality and fiction, symbols and signs become powerful vehicles for expressing her internal conflicts and fragmented memories. The visual language of the film, coupled with its psychological depth, portrays Mima's struggle with identity, illustrating how cinematic symbols can encapsulate the nuances of personal memory and the ever-shifting nature of self-perception.³⁸⁶

To bring collective memory also under scrutiny in "Perfect Blue," as the film interrogates the constructed narratives surrounding pop culture figures and the imagined communities they inspire. Fans' perception of Mima as a pop idol transforms over time, and the film explores how cinematic storytelling influences the collective memory of a society. The portrayal of

³⁸³ Ibid.

³⁸⁴ Ibid.

³⁸⁵ Ibid.

³⁸⁶ Ibid.

Mima's public image versus her private struggles unravels the layers of collective memory and its susceptibility to media manipulation, making a poignant commentary on the impact of cinematic narratives on shaping societal remembrances.³⁸⁷

Moreover, “Perfect Blue” extends its exploration to the realm of political memory, although indirectly. The film's examination of media's role in shaping public perception touches upon broader societal dynamics, hinting at how political narratives and collective historical memory can be influenced and manipulated through visual storytelling. The film suggests that the power dynamics within society, including political forces, are intricately tied to the semiotic expressions embedded in cinematic narratives.³⁸⁸

In essence, “Perfect Blue” becomes a rich tapestry through which to unravel the complexities of memory and its semiotic expression in cinema. By examining the interplay between signs, symbols, and narratives at individual, collective, and political levels, the film provides a nuanced exploration of how the cinematic medium shapes the stories we tell ourselves about our identities and histories. It underscores the profound impact of visual storytelling in constructing, deconstructing, and reconstructing the narratives that define our understanding of the past and, consequently, our present and future.³⁸⁹

Through the lens of semiotics of memory, it could be also decoded that how the Japanese pop idol culture emerges from the realm of collective imagination and divides its multifaceted functions within the framework of memory studies. As we delve deeper into this study, we embark on a semiotic journey, searching the Japanese comprehension of the body as a locus of discourse for myths, language, culture, and customs—a site where collective memory is not only preserved but actively reshaped.

As it has already been mentioned before, semiotics of memory posits that signs, symbols, and narratives are the building blocks of memory construction. In this context, Japanese pop idols become semiotic markers, embodying and transmitting collective narratives, language, and cultural traditions. This examination, grounded in semiotics, offers valuable insights into how collective memory is both archived and transformed through the cultural phenomenon of Japanese pop idols. In essence, this study underscores the symbiotic relationship between Japanese pop idol culture and the collective memory of its society, all within the framework of

³⁸⁷ Ibid.

³⁸⁸ Ibid.

³⁸⁹ Ibid.

semiotics of memory. It clarifies how these idols become semiotic containers, carrying the shared stories and cultural expressions of a community, actively shaping and reshaping collective memory in the process.

This connection emphasizes the role of language not only in conveying memories but also in the construction of collective memory. The Japanese lexicon acts as a mirror, reflecting the predominant thoughts and values of society in each epoch. It serves as a tool through which the collective memory reconstructs an image of the past in alignment with the prevailing societal narratives—a testament to the intricate relationship between language, memory, and society. The comprehensive exploration of the role of language has already been discussed in depth in the second chapter of this study.

“Perfect Blue” masterfully blurs the boundaries between Mima’s individual memory, and the collective memory imposed upon her. Semiotic elements, such as scenes where personal memories intertwine with external narratives, serve as a visual representation of this entanglement. The film raises questions about the manipulability of memory in the face of collective pressure and societal expectations. Instances of semiotic confusion abound in the film, particularly when reality and fantasy intersect. Signs and symbols become ambiguous or contradictory, reflecting the semiotic disorientation that often accompanies memory reconstruction. This confusion underscores the complex relationship between memory and semiotics.

In conclusion, “Perfect Blue” stands as a cinematic masterpiece that unravels the intricate dance between semiotics of memory and collective memory on the body. Through symbols, signs, and narratives, the film offers a window into the selective and reconstructive nature of memory on both individual and societal levels. By analyzing the semiotic elements at play, we gain a deeper understanding of how memory is constructed, deconstructed, and reshaped within the intricate web of individual and collective recollections.

Furthermore, the protagonist, Mima Kirigoe, experiences a series of haunting and surreal dreams of her becoming involved in a series of concurrent murders as a murderer. This serves as a central theme throughout the film. Her subconscious mind becomes a battleground for the complexities of identity, reality, and memory. These dreams, characterized by their disorienting and symbolic imagery, offer a window into Mima's innermost fears, desires, and conflicts.

These dreams can be analyzed through the lens of studying dreams as moments when individuals exist in a state of “outside” the influence of society. In dreams, the narrative suggests, there is a primary form of social life, and memories within dreams are often characterized as weak due to the absence of a social context to reinforce them. As Mima navigates her own subconscious, she grapples with fragmented memories and distorted perceptions, mirroring the concept of weak memories within dreams.

The dream sequences can be seen as instances where Mima temporarily escapes the influence of societal norms and expectations, allowing her innermost fears, desires, and conflicts to surface in an unfiltered way. The dream sequences in “Perfect Blue” become a canvas for the exploration of Mima’s internal struggles, devoid of the societal influences that shape her waking reality. The dreamworld, as depicted in the film, serves as a space where the constraints of social context are momentarily lifted, allowing for the expression of thoughts and emotions that may be suppressed in the waking state.

This analysis aligns with the notion that dreams offer a unique perspective on an individual’s psyche, providing a glimpse into a more primal and unfiltered version of the self. Mima’s dreams, characterized by their surreal and disjointed nature, illustrate the weakening of social memories within this dream realm. As the film progresses, the blurred lines between reality and dreams contribute to the overall psychological tension, highlighting the intricate relationship between individual consciousness, societal influence, and the subconscious mind in shaping Mima’s identity.

Japan’s cinema doesn’t solely feature perfect blue with female body centrality. Many post-World War II films tackle similar themes, reflecting post-war conflicts over the concept of the body. In the upcoming section, I will briefly highlight other movies and the centrality of the female body to reinforce the arguments presented throughout the thesis.

3.5 Beyond Perfect Blue: Exploring Female Body Centrality in Post-War Japanese Cinema

Japanese cinema of the post-war era was an important wave within this period consisted of realistic family dramas, which focused on domestic relationships. These movies depicted the dynamics between husbands and wives, grandparents and grandchildren, parents and children, and other everyday family interactions. They portrayed ordinary life events such as birth,

marriage, having children, and death. While direct portrayals of war were absent in most of these films, references to it were often limited to husbands who perished or returned home after long absences during the post-war years.³⁹⁰

An inevitable aspect of Japan's societal ideals, with its intricate blend of fantasy and nostalgia, lies in its portrayal and treatment of bodies. Specifically, it avoids certain body positions: avoiding the representation of desires and disease, the portrayal of destroyed and disintegrating bodies, and directing clear of individual conflicts embodied within them.³⁹¹

Examining one of Ozu's, a Japanese director, early films, "A Hen in the Wind" (1948), sheds light on this theme. The story revolves around Tokiko, a woman left alone with her son after her husband fails to return from war. Struggling with poverty, Tokiko sells her *kimono* to make ends meet. The sudden illness of the son worsens the financial crisis, leading the woman to unwillingly turn to prostitution for one night to afford the son's treatment expenses.

After the husband returns from war, the wife confesses her actions to him. Distraught, the husband seeks revenge by visiting the same house of prostitution. He seeks revenge but encounters a young girl forced into the same work due to poverty. Through her perspective, he forgives Tokiko, and life resumes. Although seemingly a simple melodrama, this film, as Ozu's second post-war work, offers insight into his exploration of bodies throughout his career until his death in 1963.³⁹²

There is no explicit mention of war, yet the necessity to sell the *kimono* signifies saying goodbye to conventional standards of bodily norms. This act of selling the *kimono* should be viewed as the film's starting point to understand the subsequent analysis. Then, the illness of the child occurs, leading Tokiko to agree to sell her body to save her child. Although seemingly disconnected from the initial chaos of selling the kimono, there exists a profound interpretative link. Through the lens of the kimono's significance, its loss exposes the vulnerability of bodies to danger. This transition strips the kimono of its symbolic role as a guardian of women's bodies and a marker of aesthetic identity.

³⁹⁰ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 88.

³⁹¹ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 90.

³⁹² Ozu, Yasujirō. A Hen in the Wind. 1948.

As the narrative progresses, with the husband's return from war remaining the filmmaker's ultimate resolution, his portrayal lacks any visible scars of war. The filmmaker intentionally avoids recalling the war's impact on bodies; instead, Tokiko's prostitution embodies the entirety of the war's loss experienced by the characters. In a conversation within the movie, the man's colleague coldly expresses surprise that the man does not sleep at home. This suggests that the insomnia experienced during war has permeated into domestic life.

The escalation of conflict within the household becomes evident when the man resorts to violence against his wife. This physical altercation ends in Tokiko being thrown down the stairs. Ozu's focus on the war within the home underscores the significance of internal conflict over external conflict. Consequently, Tokiko emerges as the true casualty of this war, enduring wounds, humiliation, and violation.

An essential aspect of this portrayal is Tokiko's role as a mother, with her body held sacred according to traditional culture in Japan. The filmmaker carefully avoids portraying her moment of harm from the husband's violence. Instead, Tokiko swiftly rises from her fall. While the post-war era is referenced, the representation refrains from delving into aspects of desire or pain within Tokiko's body. Despite her body teetering on the brink of degeneration, it ultimately finds redemption.

The final image of children playing innocently signifies a desire to move beyond the turbulent past, echoing the husband's suggestion to forget. This represents a return to traditional essence, even in the absence of customary attire like the kimono. This transformation is further emphasized through the actors' movements, particularly Tokiko's portrayal; A body that maintains control over its emotions, even in the most challenging moments, exhibits its physical state and behavior in accordance with customs of respect, particularly towards one's partner.

In an emotional scene, the wife arrives eagerly but quietly takes her place beside her husband's bed, gently waking him with a soft voice after his return from war. Despite their closeness, there is no physical contact; Tokiko refrains from embracing or even shaking hands with him. Instead, she calmly inquires if he is hungry, and upon learning that he is, she promptly leaves to purchase food for him. Such a sequence is characteristic of Japanese films. It underscores

the importance of preserving bodily autonomy and refraining from displaying emotions that might influence upon it.³⁹³

“Late Spring,” produced in 1949, offers a portrayal of occupied Japan that idealizes national culture through its depiction of an imaginary world. The film’s setting revolves around traditional customs, such as the tea ceremony and Kyoto temples, portraying a desire to return to pre-war Japan and revive past relationships. Unlike “A Hen in the Wind,” which subtly hints at the war’s impact, “Late Spring” completely neglects any signs of wartime strife, presenting a peaceful and idyllic narrative.³⁹⁴

The protagonist, Noriko, leads a content life with her elderly father and resists the prospect of marriage, exhibiting a reluctance to depart from the safety of her father’s home. Despite Freudian undertones suggesting potential psychological disturbances related to desires and bodies, Noriko’s lack of overt desire or ambition is masked beneath a surface of contentment. However, a pivotal moment occurs when Noriko’s father suggests the possibility of remarriage, Noriko’s profound upset arises, as it signifies more than just a change in family dynamics. In the context of the film, the prospect of her father remarrying outside the bounds of tradition implies a recognition of his own bodily desires and humanity beyond his societal role as a father.³⁹⁵

Noriko is confronted with the challenge of accepting that the father she resides with possesses human attributes beyond his societal role and paternal responsibilities. However, she struggles to comprehend this reality. Interestingly, even her calm and composed father appears to struggle with this concept, as evidenced by his expedient lie intended solely to ensure his daughter’s acceptance regarding her prospective marriage. This suggests that both Noriko and her father are grappling with the complexities of human nature and societal expectations, although in different ways.

When the girl realizes that her father is seeking individuality beyond the confines of his paternal role, it prompts reflection. According to Russell, the film’s connection to Japan during the occupation period is framing the film as a counter-narrative to modernization. The absence of a war-torn atmosphere serves as a deliberate contrast, emphasizing the film’s celebration of

³⁹³ Bordwell, David. *Poetics of Cinema*. 1st ed. Routledge, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203941898>.

³⁹⁴ *Ibid*, 40.

³⁹⁵ Ozu, Yasujirō. *Late Spring*. 1949.

tradition.³⁹⁶ As Noriko transforms into a bride adorned in a luxurious *kimono*, she embodies tradition and the natural rhythm of life.

Eleven years later, in order to emphasize the closeness of the two works, actress Noriko (Setsuko Hara) appears in the film “Late Autumn” (1960), portraying a mother whose daughter is at the age of marriage but is hesitant to leave her widowed mother alone. Similar to the previous film, the daughter eventually acquiesces to her mother’s request.³⁹⁷ Through her portrayal, Setsuko Hara embodies the ideal Japanese woman, rooted in traditional culture despite the changing times. The recurring roles of mother and daughter, along with Setsuko Hara's depiction, symbolize the continuity of life, transcending wars and economic shifts. Life’s daily rhythms and familial bonds endure, unaffected by external circumstances.³⁹⁸

In the film “Tokyo Story” (1953), elderly parents assume a significant role similar to their portrayal in previous discussed movies. They embody traditional values and support structures that modernization often neglects. Set in Tokyo in 1953, the film portrays the elderly couple as extreme burdens in a city focused on progress while they are visiting their children there. Their children's desire to send them away, symbolized by suggesting a visit to the hot springs, reflects society's tendency to remove the elderly, treating them as disposable bodies.³⁹⁹

This rejection of elderly bodies reflects broader post-war Japanese melodrama, echoing a societal humiliation for the elderly and worn-out. The concept of civilization’s rejection of elderly bodies further underscores this theme, as old age becomes synonymous with waste in the urban landscape.⁴⁰⁰ The film slightly explores the intricate relationship between the body, the home, and the city. The body serves as the primary residence, followed by the familial home and, ultimately, the urban environment, forming an inseparable triad where each element influences and shapes the others.

The theme of the city in “Tokyo Story” is introduced from the film’s title itself. The initial scenes show a calm countryside, with an elderly couple residing in a traditional setting within nature. However, as the narrative transitions to Tokyo, the contrast is stark, symbolized by

³⁹⁶ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 95.

³⁹⁷ Ozu, Yasujirō. Late Autumn. 1960.

³⁹⁸ Bordwell, David. Poetics of Cinema. 1st ed. Routledge, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203941898>.

³⁹⁹ Ozu, Yasujirō. Tokyo Story. 1953.

⁴⁰⁰ Samini, Naghmeh. Wars and Bodies: Body as a Sign in the Japanese Post-War Culture and Cinema. Tehran: Ney, 2019, 99.

towering chimneys emitting black smoke. The sky is covered by wires, emphasizing the urban sprawl's dominance. The couple's son is frustrated by the disruption caused by his parents' presence in his Tokyo home, highlighting the clash between traditional familial values and modern urban life.

In another scene, the dad comes back drunk with his friends to his daughter's house. He awkwardly occupies a chair in a women's hair salon and falls asleep. Meanwhile, the mother is relegated to a small room in her daughter-in-law's home, evoking a sense of displacement and loss. Tokyo appears as a frightening and unfamiliar landscape for the elderly couple, who express concerns about losing each other within the bustling city's anonymity.

Neither Tokyo nor any house provides a refuge for this elderly couple; they feel like strangers everywhere, adding to the city's loneliness. These parents rely heavily on Noriko, their daughter-in-law, who embodies the ideal Japanese woman. Noriko dedicates herself to reconciling them with the city, even arranging a day trip for them around Tokyo. This excursion, particularly their visit to the Imperial Palace, symbolizes Tokyo's rich history amidst modernization. The palace, representing traditional Tokyo, contrasts with the city's modern face, yet offers comfort to the elderly couple. This moment underscores the significance of preserving traditional values, despite the changing times, as Noriko's compassion and the palace's historical significance provide a sense of belonging for the elderly in a rapidly evolving city.

At the end, as they return back to their city, the elderly woman passes away. This event, while not directly linked to their journey, signifies the lack of a place where they truly belong, removing them from a world that doesn't accommodate them. "Tokyo Story" stands out as one of Ozu's most controversial films, reflecting his evident concern about the displacement of traditional symbols and values. This concern is not only evident in the dialogue but also in many scenes throughout the film. A recurring motif is the staging featuring the elderly couple sitting back to back, gazing beyond the frame, suggesting a shared fear about the future. This concern is shared by both the characters and Ozu himself

Despite being seen by some, like left-wing writer Gibbs, as lacking explicit political criticism, Ozu's films, including "Tokyo Story," offer a thought-provoking portrayal of Japanese female body passivity and silence in the face of adversity. The film portrays the old woman's passive acceptance of her circumstances, highlighting the Japanese people's reluctance to protest. In

“Tokyo Story,” the ultimate form of elderly woman is seeking solace in sake, emphasizing her resignation to her fate and ultimately leading to her passing, a destroyed body.

Last word: Concluding Comments and Future Studies

The overarching goal of the present thesis was to investigate potential pathways to outlook the “history of the body” in Japan. To emphasize on the complex interplay between Japanese pop idol culture, societal expectations, and individual identity that can be seen through the lens of the animated film “Perfect Blue.” The thesis critically assesses the impact of language, myth, and cultural narratives on the construction of the body and identity within the Japanese context.

Employing constructivist and discourse analysis approaches, the paper explores how these elements contribute to a hegemonic cultural narrative. I tried to also highlight the role of anime in reflecting and critiquing these cultural dynamics, underscoring the importance of understanding the bio-historical body concept in Japan. This analysis not only sheds light on the nuanced relationship between culture, language, and identity but also on the broader implications for societal norms and individual agency within the globalized world of pop idol culture.

In this final chapter, I will review the main research ideas and methodologies of each chapter contained in the thesis, including the extensive analysis of Japanese pop idol culture, body politics, the intersection between media representations, cultural practices, and individual identity formation, as well as the representation of body in “Perfect Blue.” Then, I would discuss their theoretical implications and methodological limitations, and propose new possibilities for future research by identifying gaps or new questions raised by the research.

4.1 Overview of the Research Idea and Methodology

Chapter One delves into the complex interplay between pop idol culture and the consumption of female idols as visual representations in Japan through a political use of psychoanalysis. It explores how these idols are produced, circulated, and engaged with by audiences, highlighting the role of fiction and fantasy in constructing the idol persona. The chapter examines the idol phenomenon within the broader context of Japanese media culture, touching upon themes such as the no-dating policy, the blending of real and fictional images, and the cultural significance of “kawaii.” An exploration that emphasizes on the socio-cultural, economic, and media dynamics at play.

Through a detailed analysis, it reveals how idols serve as focal points for desire, transforming into commodities that offer fans immersive experiences. The discourse surrounding idols as

soulful bodies delves deep into the intricate relationship between fans, fantasy, and the constructed images of desire. Through psychoanalytic lenses such as those provided by Freud and Lacan, we uncover the complex dynamics at play within the idol phenomenon. These idols transcend mere images, becoming vessels for the projection of fans' desires, aspirations, and emotional energies.

The idol's image, while appearing static, pulsates with the affective force generated by the collective energy of its admirers, blurring the boundaries between stillness and animation, fantasy and reality. Therefore, it integrates a discussion on the impact of idol culture on fan identity, consumer behavior, and media practices, while also considering the implications of this phenomenon for understanding contemporary Japanese society.

The chapter is reflecting on the details of the idol-fan relationship, the commodification of idols, and the role of media in shaping and disseminating idol culture. It would also consider the broader societal and cultural implications, including how idol culture reflects and influences gender norms, consumerism, and media consumption patterns in Japan.

The discussion extends to the economic impact of idol activities and the complex fan-idol relationship facilitated by events like handshake meetings. By weaving together these threads, it offers a comprehensive overview of contributions to the study of pop culture and media studies. The analysis underscores the profound impact of idols on consumer culture, shaping not only visual aesthetics but also emotional and spiritual connections between fans and their objects of admiration.

It invites us to reconsider these images not as static representations but as dynamic entities capable of infusing soul and essence into a wide array of commodities, ultimately blurring the boundaries between image and lived experience in the realm of fan engagement. The chapter concludes by reflecting on the dual nature of idols as both economic and political commodities, shaping and being shaped by the cultural and societal dynamics of Japan.

Overall, the idol's image is not just a representation frozen in time; it embodies purity and idealization, creating a perceptual filter through which fans engage with their objects of desire. Lacanian theory further explains how individuals construct a sense of self through their interactions with these idealized images, projecting onto them a completeness and perfection that may not align with reality. In this way, the idol becomes not only a symbol of cultural significance but also a reflection of the complex desires and fantasies of its audience.

Therefore, our examination in chapter one, of anime and pop idol culture in Japan, has led us to an intriguing intersection: the correlation between the disintegration of the body and the disintegration of the mind within Japanese society. In Japan, where traditional beliefs and societal norms uphold the sanctity of the body as a container for purity and morality, any abnormality from this idealized image carries significant weight. Our inquiry into Mima's transformation serves as a poignant reflection of broader cultural constructs, illuminating the intricate relationship between physical appearance and mental health in Japanese society.

As we embark on the second chapter of our exploration, we are poised to unravel how the body and mind are connected in Japanese society. By dissecting the societal influences that shape perceptions of body, self and identity, we aim to shed light on the consequences of differing from established norms. Ultimately, our mission is to understand how the disintegration of the body manifests as the disintegration of the mind within the context of Japan, offering insights into the complexities of body formation and mental well-being in a society deeply rooted in tradition and societal expectations.

Chapter Two delves into the intricate relationships between the body, culture, and society, exploring various perspectives and historical contexts. It addresses the evolution of medical anthropology, the dichotomy between body and mind, and the political implications of bodily representations. The chapter examines philosophical and sociological theories, including Foucault's analysis of power and the body, Cartesian dualism, and the impact of Japanese mythology and culture on understanding the body.

It highlights the significance of the body in medical anthropology, cultural rituals, and the construction of identity, emphasizing the role of historical, social, and cultural factors in shaping perceptions and treatments of the body. This exploration culminates in a nuanced understanding of the "history of body", bridging disciplines to offer a comprehensive view of how bodies are influenced by and reflect broader cultural and historical dynamics and not only biological factors.

Traditional Japanese culture holds a unique perspective on the body. Through exploration of the history of body in Japan we gain deeper insights into this intricate relationship between the body and the mind within Japanese culture. In my investigation, in chapter two, I delved into the historical evolution of the body's significance in Japanese culture by examining its portrayal in myth, language, culture, and history through the lens of constructivism methodology.

In our exploration of the body in mythology, I explore the centrality of the body in Japan's myths that uncovers a profound intertwining of cultural narratives and embodied experiences. The myths examined illustrate of the body not merely as a physical entity, but as a symbolic and cultural construct embodying fears, transformations, and historical contexts. Moreover, the significance of the body extends to our engagement with language, as emphasized by Pierre Bourdieu's concept of habitus.

Habitual dispositions shape our behaviors, perceptions, and attitudes, revealing the intricate relationship between our bodies, language, and lived experiences. This understanding challenges simplistic views of the body, emphasizing its complexity within the realm of embodied existence. This transitioned us to explore the concept of body in Japanese language. By tracing the linguistic representations of the body in Japanese discourse, I uncovered how language constructs and reinforces perceptions of the body as essential to human existence. By using the term linguistic construct, I challenged the notion that language simply mirrors reality. I explored how language actively shapes and constructs our understanding of physical experiences by relying on constructivist approaches.

The constructivist approach highlights how language influences our understanding of physical experiences and shapes our cultural norms and values surrounding the body. Through this exploration, we gain deeper insights into the intricate relationship between the body and the mind within Japanese culture. This led us to the exploration of body in Japan's culture, practices and symbols associated with the body in established Japanese customs and rituals. These cultural expressions seemed to embody the concept of the ideal Japanese body.

This ideal body is expected to exude a distinctive aesthetic that demands discipline and refinement, and the term that encapsulates this perspective is "mind-body." In this section of Chapter Two, I explored four cultural elements that embody the ideal form of the body in Japan. These cultural phenomena include harakiri and samurai, kimono and geisha, temae and tea ceremony, and traditional theater. These exemplary bodies undergo rigorous training and specialized education to achieve beauty and liberate the soul.

Chapter two ends with an exploration of the body in Japan's history and how, in the aftermath of war and during occupation, the profound assault on Japanese bodies underscored a unique cultural interpretation, where the degradation of the body symbolized a deeper mental decline, marking a poignant contradiction in Japanese heritage. The emergence of "nikutai bungaku,"

or “literature of the flesh,” post-World War Two, served as a response to the wartime ethos, aiming to liberate from societal constraints and explore both physical and emotional realms.

Chapter Three emphasizes on the collective memory surrounding the body in Japanese society. I examined how this collective memory is both preserved and dynamically reshaped, highlighting the enduring centrality of the body in societal narratives. In the realm of culture, memory functions as a dynamic force, both preserving existing information and generating new narratives. Media, particularly cinema, plays a pivotal role in shaping collective memory by intertwining visual narratives with human recollection. This fusion creates a complex interplay—a symphony of signs, symbols, and narratives—capturing the semiotics of memory.

Embarking on a cinematic journey, I explored the essence of remembering the concept of the body in Japan. Through film, I investigated how the body is represented, communicated, interpreted, and transmitted, illustrating the construction of collective memory surrounding this concept. Cinema employs ceremonial historical narratives to craft versions of collective memory and identity shared with audiences, shaping perceptions and understanding of the body within Japanese culture.

As I pivoted to a feminist perspective, my exploration deepened, aiming to comprehensively analyze the social pressures exerted on the gendered body, with a particular focus on women's experiences. By delving into the intersectionality of memory, gender, and cinematic representation, I aimed to uncover the nuanced ways in which societal perceptions and expectations were shaped, especially through the lens of post-war Japanese cinema.

Eventually, Chapter Three sought to address how the concept of “the history of the body,” as elucidated in Chapter Two, was reinforced through the construction of collective memory, particularly within the realm of cinema. Furthermore, I aimed to investigate the heightened impact of these dynamics on women's bodies, offering insights into the complex interplay of memory, gender, and cinematic representation in shaping societal norms and expectations.

Building on our exploration of memory, gender, and cinematic representation, the film “Perfect Blue” emerges as a cinematic masterpiece that delves the intricate interplay within the context of memory, semiotics, and identity, drawing connections to broader societal and psychological themes, particularly concerning the body.

Through its use of symbols, signs, and narratives, the film unveils the selective and reconstructive nature of memory at both individual and societal levels. It explores the implications of the film's narrative and visual techniques for understanding the construction of identity in the digital age, the role of media in shaping personal and collective memory, and the complex interplay between reality and perception. It offers a profound reflection of protagonist Mima Kirigoe's journey, serving as a testament to the semiotic expression of memory and the potent role of cinematic symbols in conveying internal conflicts and fragmented memories. Thus, "Perfect Blue" stands as a nuanced exploration of how cinematic storytelling shapes individual and collective memory, while also offering poignant commentary on the influence of media in shaping our understanding of the past, present, and future.

Further I discussed the intricate relationship between "Perfect Blue" and societal norms, as well as individual identities. I underscored the significant role of media in both constructing and perpetuating these norms, while also examining the psychological impact on individuals. Specifically, it focuses on themes such as identity crisis, objectification, and the struggle between personal agency and societal expectations portrayed in the film. Therefore, the discussion extends to the broader cultural and psychological implications of these findings. It emphasizes the influence of pop idol culture on gender norms, body image, and the commodification of individuals within the entertainment industry. These cultural artifacts contribute significantly to shaping a collective understanding of identity and social dynamics in contemporary Japan.

This chapter aimed to offer a comprehensive analysis, encompassing the critical themes of the thesis, while also reflecting on the enduring relevance of the film's exploration of these issues. Given the background provided, one would expect Mima's fluctuations and illusions to be more accurate. Mima's mental struggle, due to its context, is no longer a natural conflict that has been exhibited with cinematic intensity to dramatize catastrophe for audience attraction and consumer appeal. According to psychoanalysis, the drowned ego, which previously controlled and suppressed the exploded libido from the Id, can no longer maintain the same level of control. When the ego fails to manage the Id, its structural necessity undergoes rapid changes, leading to mental apparatus collapse and an exaggerated manifestation of oscillation.

4.2 Future studies

As our exploration of “Perfect Blue” and its cultural implications draws to a close, it becomes evident that many paths are still available for further investigation. The cinematic portrayal of memory manipulation and fragmentation prompts an urgent need for deeper psychoanalytical inquiries into its societal reflections. Future studies could delve into the psychoanalytical effects of memory manipulation depicted in the film, aligning them with contemporary issues such as information overload, digital identity crises, and the pursuit of authenticity within performative cultures. Also, further research could delve into the psychoanalysis and societal ramifications of the correlation between the disintegration of the body and the mind within Japanese society. Considering how these factors intersect with perceptions of physical appearance and mental health.

Future studies could focus on the role of media, particularly cinema, in shaping collective memory surrounding the body in Japanese society. This could involve analyzing how cinematic representations influence societal narratives, perceptions, and understandings of the body, memory, and identity. Longitudinal studies could investigate the long-term effects of media consumption, particularly idol culture media, on individuals’ perceptions of body image, identity, and social relationships over time. Understanding the lasting impact of media influences can provide valuable insights into the complexities of body formation and mental well-being in contemporary Japan.

With the evolving landscape of digital media, further research is necessary on its role in identity construction. Investigating how social media, virtual reality, and other digital platforms influence individuals’ self-perceptions, interpersonal relationships, and cultural identities can offer a deeper understanding of the intersection between media, technology, and identity. Furthermore, the evolving landscape of digital media calls for studies on its role in reshaping the relationship between idols and fans. By exploring the influence of social media, virtual reality, and other digital platforms on fan interaction, fandom dynamics, and identity construction, researchers can elucidate the transformative potential of digital media in the realm of idol culture.

Critical examinations of gender representation in media, including idol culture media, can contribute to a more nuanced understanding of societal norms and expectations surrounding gender roles, body image, and personal agency. Research in this area could shed light on the ways in which media representations perpetuate or challenge existing gender stereotypes and

power dynamics. In-depth analyses from feminist perspectives could further elucidate the societal pressures exerted on gendered bodies, with a specific focus on women's experiences. By exploring the intersectionality of memory, gender, and cinematic representation, researchers can uncover the nuanced ways in which societal perceptions and expectations are shaped.

These future study suggestions aim to build upon the groundwork laid by the current research, offering opportunities for further exploration into the complex interplay of culture, media, and identity in Japanese society. By addressing these areas of inquiry, researchers can deepen our understanding of how societal norms and individual identities are constructed, negotiated, and transformed within contemporary Japan. Also, by critically reflecting on methodological approaches and theoretical frameworks, researchers can navigate the strengths and limitations of their analyses, thereby advancing our understanding of the intricate relationship between culture, media, and identity in contemporary society.

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